

Open Proceedings
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Preface

MOCO is an interdisciplinary community where artistic and technical contributions are synergistic and equally valued. MOCO Conference invites submissions that span academic approaches, applied practices, and fields of study, unified by the concepts of movement and computing. The 10th edition of MOCO Conference encouraged in 2026 submitters to carefully articulate the relationship of their work to this lens through both scientific and artistic methods of inquiry.

In order to support the interdisciplinary community, MOCO is open to a wide range of formats for presenting work. In addition to scientific papers for oral and poster presentations, MOCO conference invites submission of practice works such as demos, performances, games, artistic works and movement workshops.

For the 10th edition of the MOCO'26 conference novel formats were proposed, and submitters were encouraged to be creative in proposals for practice sessions. Finally, three types of submissions were launched: Research papers, Practice works and Doctoral consortium.

To encourage the intersection between academic research, interdisciplinary work, and artistic practice at the MOCO'26 conference, two publication options were proposed for authors.

The ACM publication track allows authors to publish their papers in the ACM Digital Library as open access publications:

<https://dl.acm.org/doi/proceedings/10.1145/3802842>

Additionally, MOCO'26 gave authors the chance to present their work at the conference without paying publication fees. These works are accessible on the French open-access platform HAL as a book of abstracts titled MOCO'26 Open Proceedings.

MOCO'26 is organised by EuroMov Digital Health in Motion, a joint research unit between the University of Montpellier and IMT Mines Alès, based on three areas of expertise: Human Movement Sciences, Digital Sciences and Health Sciences.

EuroMov Digital Health in Motion

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In the pink of Health

In the fields of neurocomputational and movement-based research, the concept of health is increasingly operationalized through data, including neural patterns, kinematic signatures, and recovery curves. Wearables and motion-tracking systems hold great promise in providing insights into physical and cognitive health. However, it should be noted that such systems also impose thresholds of inclusion, determining which bodies are measurable and whose movements are deemed expressive, curative, or valid. As neuroscience meets computer science and the arts, it is essential to question the role of these tools in shaping our understanding of what constitutes a healthy body or mind.

Considering this, a reframing of health as emergent, relational and performative is required, drawing upon critical post-humanist theory, embodied cognition, and artistic research. Applications in dance, interactive installations, and neuroaesthetic interfaces can model alternative health paradigms. By rethinking movement not merely as data but as a lived and expressive phenomenon, new interdisciplinary possibilities for designing systems that reflect diverse and situated ways of being in The Pink of Health can be opened.

This MOCO'26 conference proposes to critically examine how health, as both concept and computational output, participates in technocultural narratives that risk reinforcing normative, performance-driven ideals. Movement technologies, especially in arts-based applications, have the potential to open space for alternative modes of vitality or discomfort that challenge prevailing definitions of health. During this 10th edition, authors are invited you to share their reflections on how their research reimagine health in movement and data/computer science, or artistic practice, not as fixed optimisation, but as fluid, plural and performative.

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RESEARCH PAPERS

Dance, disability and robots: interdisciplinary possibilities for reframing 'healthy bodies' in performance

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Abstract

What does health mean in the context of dancing with robots? There are important 'health and safety' considerations that support explorations but may also limit the pushing of boundaries to find out when robots 'fail'. When the dancers have a lived experience of disability and navigate through environments that often fail to accommodate differently abled or 'non-traditional' bodies, how does that impact on what we understand as failure. What does failure mean in this context and how does failure relate to 'good health'? What might we learn through engaging in systems that seek to erase failure rather than embrace failure as a creative force? And how does failure map against what is considered healthy or unhealthy? At root of this enquiry is a call to find ways to ensure that developments in tracking and measuring the ways that bodies move avoids smoothing over bodily difference. A primary focus is on emphasising 'healthy touch' between humans and robots, both healthy for the dancers and healthy for the robots.

This presentation will share some of the work involved in two interrelated projects: Archai.art funded through the UKRI Arts and Humanities Research Council's (AHRC) Bridging Responsible Artificial Intelligence Divides (BRAID) programme led by Dr Lydia Farina and the 'dancing with robots' strand of the Somabotics project led by Professor Steve Benford, examining how disabled dance artists are making work with robots as dancing partners. By starting from the lived experience of expert disabled dancers, the collaborations in both projects develop methodologies that challenge normative processes, to rethink RRI in the design/robot/computing interaction, and to counter the conventional narratives that surround disability in performance, as always a therapeutic process that sits within a paradigm of disability 'equals' health, and how bringing bodies and robots together challenges assumptions about what it means to be 'healthy' and 'broken' (humans) or 'malfunctioning' but 'working' robots.

In our work thus far, we have explored how dancers push the robots to singularities which cause them to glitch as they try to protect themselves from damage. For example, by trying to address this, we are working with Franka arm robots that can now sometimes automatically 'unglitch' themselves when the human backs off. But if the dancer has bent the arm into an unusual position this is not always possible and often confounds robot wranglers, revealing something interesting about the non-human morphology of the arm. What emerges is knowledge about different ways of touching the robots that seem more or less beneficial, and therefore 'healthy' for the robots. For example, with two limbs, using the forearms and different

points of contact initiated by the dancers based on their expertise of how touching is often experienced as a reciprocal exchange of energy, weight, resistance and other corporealities. In this context, glitching offers a valuable lens onto the ethics of disability

We also ask how the robots can avoid hurting the dancers when in close contact and draw on experiences with a number of techniques and interventions. Integrating some new 'soft compliance' techniques means that bumping into a Franka are stops its current movement and relaxes it so the dancer can take control for a while. Adding soft soma skins (drawn from a toolkit) to mediate between the dancer and the robot creates a different sensation of touch and supports a safer interaction, something we have explored in earlier projects as a process of learning 'somatic safety'.

Whilst hoping to expand notions of what constitutes good health, the presentation will also share how the collaborations between different disciplinary experts are building ethical and inclusive approaches to making performance, which reveal new understandings of the limitations and possibilities of robots as creative dancing partners, whereby we learn more about healthy touch. By extension, the research is exploring ways in which the data recorded from these explorations are processed and archived, in ways that are responsible and ethical, and which may generate new understandings of what it means to have a healthy body and mind.

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Effects of cognitive-motor training in virtual reality on anticipatory brain functions and balance of professional dancers

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Abstract

Dancing is a universal modality of human movement expression, characterized by the integration of motor and cognitive aspects (e.g., Bläsing et al., 2012). In professional dance, correct performance execution is defined in terms of movement technique, expressiveness, and creativity. In this context, effective dance training is fundamental since cognitive and motor control have a pivotal role in ensuring fine and optimal motor gestures and defining the performance of professional dancers. This is the result of complex neurocognitive processes, which combine motor control, cognitive anticipation, attention, visuomotor imagination, time synchronization, and motor memory (e.g., Golomer et al., 1999; Bläsing et al., 2012). The mentioned literature highlighted the relevance of cognitive functions in dancing practice and performance, but no studies have tested the effectiveness of dance-specific training to potentiate cognitive skills in professional dancers. Indeed, in literature, there are only studies that have dealt with training modalities to strictly improve technical and motor skills (for a review Senger et al., 2024), which are important, but neglected to take care of the dancer's mind. This study investigated the effects of a virtual reality cognitive-motor dual-task training protocol (VR-CMDT) on anticipatory brain functions and balance in professional dancers. Twenty-four participants were divided into a control group, which followed standard dance training for 8 weeks, and an experimental group that underwent the same training but included the VR-CMDT training session once a week. One training method for professional dancers based on CMDT and VR is the patented protocol Creative Movement Hacking® (CMH) training method (Gasparotti, 2024). CMH is a VR-based evolution of the dancing routines related to the five regular solids: tetrahedron, cube, octahedron, dodecahedron, and icosahedron, proposed by the human movement theorist Rudolf Laban to map movement in space (Laban & Ulman, 1966). This dancing method has been used for educational and choreographic purposes (e.g., Milner et al., 2019). CMH requires the execution of choreographic sequences within virtual solids, but with increasing cognitive and simultaneously motor demands. This progression was achieved by alternating solids of varying sizes, with increasingly faster transitions between

them and progressively wider excursions in both their dimensions and shapes, accompanied by a simultaneous increase in the speed of the soundtracks. According to Gasparotti (2024),

this dance training should improve dancing technique, expressiveness, and creativity in only eight weeks, even though scientific evidence is lacking..

Fig.1 shows a) the original Laban's method, b) the VR implementation, and c) the five regular solids

Before and after the intervention, both groups performed a motor test on balance, and a cognitive task during electroencephalographic recordings from which pre-stimulus event-related potentials were analyzed. The results showed that VR-CMDT increased the amplitude of prefrontal anticipatory brain activity, indicative of improved attentional and inhibitory control, and markedly reduced behavioral errors, with no changes in response times in the cognitive task. At the motor level, only the experimental group showed a significant improvement in the balance test, reflecting greater postural stability. These data support the effectiveness of VR-CMDT in strengthening anticipatory cognitive functions and, consequently, dance motor skills, suggesting its integration into professional training routines.

Keywords : Virtual Reality, Cognitive Motor Dual-Task Training, ERP, Cognition, Dance training

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Embodied Gestures: recognizing static hand movements with lightweight neural models

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Abstract

Hand gesture recognition has become an essential field in computer vision, enabling natural and intuitive communication between humans and machines. In this project, we developed a lightweight system capable of recognizing static hand gestures in real time from a webcam feed. The method relies on MediaPipe Hands for landmark extraction and a fully connected neural network trained on normalized three-dimensional coordinates of 21 keypoints. Our approach emphasizes efficiency and accessibility by reducing data dimensionality and avoiding the need for complex image-based models. The resulting system achieves high accuracy for multiple gesture classes and can be applied to educational or assistive technologies such as sign language learning tools.

Keywords : Computer Vision, Gesture, Recognition, Analysis

1. Introduction

The rapid expansion of artificial intelligence and its growing range of applications have made it increasingly important to establish effective interactions between humans and machines by accurately interpreting human behavior and intentions. Consequently, defining how computers and robots should comprehend concepts related to human behavior and machine interaction has become a central topic of research in the field of computer vision [5]. In recent years, sign language has become an essential means of communication within the community of individuals with speech and hearing impairments. These individuals use hand gestures combined with facial expressions and body movements to interact effectively with one another. However, because sign language is not an international language, only a limited

number of people learn these gestures. Traditional communication methods rely on interpreters, which can be costly and not always accessible. This underscores the urgent need for automatic recognition systems capable of breaking communication barriers by enabling smoother and more independent interactions between deaf individuals and the hearing population [2]. Hand gesture recognition has emerged as a key component of natural human-computer interaction, enabling users to communicate with digital systems in more intuitive and accessible ways. While dynamic gesture recognition involving motion sequences has received significant attention, static hand gesture recognition remains equally important for applications that rely on discrete commands or sign language

interpretation. Traditional input devices such as keyboards or touchscreens often fail to provide inclusive interaction for people with physical limitations, highlighting the need for alternative interfaces based on visual recognition. Existing approaches to static gesture recognition frequently depend on complex sensor setups or deep learning models that require extensive datasets and computational resources [4]. Recent works have investigated the application of artificial intelligence, particularly advanced deep learning and computer vision techniques, to real-time detection of human activities [7] and hand gestures [4]. These methods aim to enable more natural, inclusive, and accurate interactions between humans and machines across diverse environments. They also open new practical applications in smart homes, health monitoring, and assistance for individuals with reduced mobility. In this study, we focus on developing a lightweight, real-time system for static hand gesture recognition using a webcam feed. The system relies on MediaPipe Hands for extracting 21 three-dimensional hand landmark coordinates; a fully connected neural network trained on normalized landmark data; techniques such as batch normalization, dropout, and L2 regularization to enhance generalization and speed convergence; optimization to reduce data dimensionality and avoid complex image-based models. Our approach achieves high accuracy across multiple gesture classes, operates on standard CPUs without GPU acceleration, and lays the groundwork for future extensions to dynamic gestures, multi-hand interactions, and sequential models such as LSTMs to capture continuous motion.

2. Related Work

Hand gesture recognition has been widely studied in the context of human–computer interaction, sign language interpretation, and embodied communication. Early works

relied on handcrafted features extracted from images or depth sensors, often requiring controlled environments and suffering from poor generalization [5]. More recent approaches leverage convolutional neural networks (CNNs) or 3D architectures to learn spatial and temporal representations directly from raw images [2]. Although these models achieve strong accuracy, they typically depend on large datasets and high computational resources, making them unsuitable for realtime interaction on low-power devices. Other research directions explore sensor-based gesture recognition using gloves, IMU devices, or sEMG signals [4]. These systems provide robustness to lighting conditions but require specialized hardware, reducing accessibility for everyday users. Vision-based methods remain more practical, yet their reliance on high-resolution image processing or heavy deep learning architectures presents important limitations for interactive artistic or performative environments such as those explored at MOCO conference. Pose-estimation-based techniques, such as MediaPipe Hands, offer a promising alternative by providing accurate 2D/3D hand landmarks in real time. Recent works demonstrate the potential of combining these landmarks with lightweight machine learning models for gesture recognition. However, most studies still rely on recurrent architectures, complex CNN backbones, or domainspecific datasets that limit reproducibility and deployment on standard hardware.

3 Methodology

3.1 Dataset Construction and Preprocessing

To create a suitable dataset for static gesture recognition, we used the MediaPipe Hands API [3, 8] to extract 21 hand landmarks (each with x , y , and z coordinates), resulting in 63-dimensional vectors per frame. We collected five gesture classes: fist, like, dislike, call, and four. Specifically, two normalization steps

were applied:

- Geometric normalization: Centering all coordinates relative to the wrist (landmark 0) and scaling them based on the distance to the middle finger base (landmark 9), to mitigate the effect of distance to the camera and hand size.
- Statistical normalization: Standardizing all vectors to have zero mean and unit variance based on global dataset statistics, ensuring consistency during real-time inference. To improve generalization, we applied lightweight vector-based data augmentation techniques, such as small translations, rotations, and scalings, without relying on raw image manipulation.

3.2 MediaPipe for Compact Feature Representation

MediaPipe drastically reduced dataset complexity. Instead of storing high-resolution RGB images (e.g., 1280×720), we stored only the landmark vectors. This compact form led to faster training and inference, reduced memory and storage requirements, and feasibility of real-time use on CPU-only systems. We filtered out frames with low landmark confidence scores using MediaPipe's built-in detection reliability metrics.

3.3 Image Enhancement for Robust Landmark Detection

To improve landmark detection in low-light conditions, we explored a preprocessing method that combined well-known CLAHE (Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization) and Laplacian Pyramid Decomposition. Technically, CLAHE enhanced local contrast (clip limit = 2.0, tile size = 8×8), while the Laplacian Pyramid helped sharpen edges. This improved detection in some cases (illustrated in Figure 1), but performance degraded for darker skin tones, making the technique unreliable in general settings.

3.4 Model Architecture Selection

We first tested Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) due to their success in image-based tasks [6]. However, CNNs

rely on local spatial relationships, which are absent in 1D coordinate vectors. Thus, CNNs failed to capture meaningful gesture features, leading to poor performance and unstable learning curves.

3.5 Final MLP Architecture

To address these limitations, we adopted a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) architecture better suited for processing vector-based landmark data. The final network, implemented using TensorFlow/Keras, consists of an input layer of 63 neurons corresponding to the 21 three-dimensional hand landmarks, followed by three fully connected hidden layers with 128, 64, and 32 neurons respectively, each employing ReLU activation. To improve stability and generalization, Batch Normalization was applied after every dense layer, while Dropout with a rate of 0.3 was inserted between hidden layers to reduce overfitting. Additionally, L2 regularization with a coefficient of $\lambda = 10^{-4}$ was applied to all dense layers to further constrain weight magnitudes. The architecture concludes with a Softmax output layer containing five neurons, one for each gesture class. The model was trained using categorical cross-entropy as the loss function and the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 10^{-3} . Training was performed with a batch size of 64 over 20 to 40 epochs depending on the experiment, using an 80/20 train-validation split. These settings provided stable convergence and optimal trade-offs between accuracy and computational efficiency. Figure 2 provides a comparison of training and validation loss and accuracy for several configurations of batch size and number of epochs. We observe that larger batch sizes (e.g., 64) lead to smoother learning curves and better generalization, especially during the early training phase.

3.6 Regularization Techniques

To improve generalization and reduce overfitting, we integrated several regularization techniques into the training pipeline. Batch Normalization was applied

after each dense layer to stabilize the learning process by reducing internal covariate shift, which allowed for faster convergence and more reliable training dynamics. In addition, Dropout was used with a rate of 0.3, randomly disabling a fraction of neurons during each training step. This strategy helped the model avoid co-adaptation and encouraged the development of redundant feature representations, increasing robustness on unseen data. Finally, L2 regularization was applied to the weights of all dense layers to penalize large parameter values. This constraint contributed to smoother decision boundaries and reduced the risk of overfitting, especially in cases with limited training diversity. Together, these techniques significantly enhanced the model's ability to generalize across different users and variations in hand pose.

3.7 Real-Time Integration The trained model was deployed in a Python application using OpenCV and MediaPipe. Each webcam frame was processed in real time to extract and normalize landmarks. The MLP predicted gesture class probabilities, and the top results were displayed on the video stream. To reduce flickering, predictions were updated once per second and held on screen until the next confident detection. The system achieved real-time performance on standard CPUs, maintaining over 90% classification accuracy in normal lighting. Figure 3 illustrates a sample frame captured during real-time execution, where the recognized gesture and its confidence score are displayed over the live video feed.

4. Results and Evaluation

We evaluated our model using both class-specific and global performance metrics. The evaluation was based on a hold-out validation set representing 20% of the dataset. All results reflect the model's performance on real-time data captured using a standard webcam. The normalized confusion matrix in Figure 4 provides a

detailed view of classification performance across all gesture classes. Diagonal values close to 1 indicate high per-class accuracy, while off-diagonal entries reveal confusions between similar gestures. Gestures with similar hand configurations, such as call and like, occasionally show overlap. However, most gesture classes are consistently well recognized, with minimal confusion. Table 1 presents the precision, recall, and F1-score for each gesture class. These metrics offer a detailed breakdown of model accuracy. Across all 16 classes, we observe consistently high F1 scores, indicating that the model performs robustly, even on minority or visually ambiguous classes. To evaluate the model more holistically, we computed several global performance indicators:

- **Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC)** = 0.91 - indicates strong overall predictive power in multi-class classification.
- **Cohen's Kappa** = 0.91 - demonstrates strong agreement between predicted and true labels, corrected for chance.
- **Log-Loss** = 0.27 - reflects confident and well-calibrated predictions.
- **Macro AUC** = 0.996 - shows excellent class separability across all gesture categories.

These results confirm that the model generalizes well beyond the training data, with a strong balance between precision and recall across all gesture types. In addition to per-class performance, several global evaluation metrics are reported in Table ???. These include the Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC), Cohen's Kappa, Log Loss, and Macro AUC. The MCC and Cohen's Kappa scores, both above 0.90, confirm high agreement between predictions and ground truth. A low Log Loss of 0.27 indicates confident and well-calibrated predictions, while the Macro AUC of 0.996 reflects excellent overall class separability.

5. Discussion

Our experimental results demonstrate that static hand gesture recognition using MediaPipe landmarks and a fully connected neural network is a viable and efficient approach for real-time applications on standard hardware. However, several limitations and challenges remain. The proposed model achieves strong accuracy across both frequent and less frequent gesture classes. Thanks to the use of vectorized input and an optimized architecture, inference is fast and lightweight, requiring no GPU acceleration. The system also proves robust to moderate variations in hand orientation and position, especially when enhanced by geometric normalization and data augmentation. Despite high overall performance, the system shows sensitivity to the following factors:

- Partial occlusion: When one or more fingers are not visible, landmark detection becomes unstable, leading to incorrect classifications.
- Lighting and skin tone variations: Although we explored enhancement techniques such as CLAHE and Laplacian pyramids, these methods introduced biases and inconsistencies, particularly for darker skin tones.
- Ambiguous gestures: Certain gestures with similar landmark configurations (e.g., like vs call) occasionally lead to confusion, as seen in the confusion matrix.
- Single-hand limitation: Our current system only supports one hand at a time, which restricts its application to more complex sign language or bimanual gestures. While MediaPipe greatly simplifies the data pipeline, it introduces a dependency on the quality of its internal model. Detection errors or inconsistencies in landmark indexing can propagate through the entire system. Moreover, MediaPipe requires specific image conditions (e.g., clear background, full hand visibility), which may not always be present in real-world settings.

Compared to deep CNN or transformer-based gesture recognition models, our approach offers a better trade-off between performance and computational cost. It avoids the need for large datasets and heavy image preprocessing, making it more accessible for deployment on edge devices or low-resource environments. However, models based on raw image input may perform better in highly ambiguous contexts, where full-pose visual cues (e.g., background, skin texture) play a role in disambiguating gestures. This work highlights the importance of adapting the model architecture to the nature of the input data. Our initial use of CNNs was not suited to landmark vectors, confirming that MLPs are more appropriate for this type of tabular, non-spatial data. Furthermore, the combination of normalization, dropout, and L2 regularization was critical to achieving generalization and stability.

6. Conclusion and FutureWork

This study presents a compact and computationally efficient frame-work for static hand gesture recognition, leveraging MediaPipe based landmark representations and a carefully regularized multi-layer perceptron. The proposed model achieves high classification accuracy (above 90%) and real time performance on standard CPU hardware, demonstrating the suitability of MLP architectures for structured, non spatial vector inputs. Building on its simplicity and accessibility, future research will focus on extending the model to dynamic and bimanual gestures, enhancing robustness to diverse environmental conditions, and optimizing deployment for embed-ded and edge level systems. Collectively, these directions advance the development of inclusive and scalable solutions for real time human-machine interaction.

Figure 1: Example of successful enhancement using CLAHE and Laplacian Pyramid Decomposition

Figure 2: Comparison of training and validation loss and accuracy across different batch sizes and epoch configurations

Figure 3: Result of real-time hand movement detection

Figure 4: Normalized confusion matrix on the validation set

Table 1: Classification metrics (precision, recall, F1-score) for each gesture class.

	precision	recall	F1-score	support
call	0.980	0.891	0.934	5267.000
dislike	0.532	0.952	0.683	5569.000
fist	0.988	0.903	0.944	5692.000
four	0.986	0.914	0.948	5803.000
like	0.967	0.890	0.927	5549.000
mute	0.985	0.877	0.928	5715.000
ok	0.998	0.917	0.956	5751.000
one	0.965	0.873	0.917	5659.000
peace	0.992	0.909	0.948	5806.000
peace inverted	0.987	0.912	0.948	5501.000
rock	0.987	0.895	0.939	5769.000
stop	0.988	0.933	0.960	5867.000
stop inverted	0.977	0.922	0.948	5352.000
three	0.993	0.885	0.936	5570.000
three3	0.780	0.953	0.858	7926.000
thumb index2	0.993	0.990	0.991	3690.000
accuracy	0.913	0.913	0.913	0.913
macro avg	0.944	0.914	0.923	90486.000
weighted avg	0.939	0.913	0.920	90486.000

Table 2: Performance metrics for gesture classification.

Metric	Value
MCC	0.9085
Cohen's Kappa	0.9069
Log Loss	0.2749
Macro AUC	0.9960

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Enriching the Kinematic: Approaching New Methods for Machine Learning with Bodies That Move at the Edge

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Keywords : Machine learning, motion capture, dance notation, interdisciplinarity

Abstract

As we become increasingly surrounded by machine learning (ML), it is essential that these systems be sensitive and responsive to the nuances of our actions. Many recent ML advances lean heavily on enormous pools of digitized text, image and sound. When vast amounts of data are available, a sufficiently large model given enough training develops surprisingly rich representations of salient features present in the dataset (if they prove useful in achieving its learning objective). Human motion is often represented with 'kinematic' data: sequences of static poses. Given enough of this data, an ML model should – in theory – learn some approximation of interplay of muscles and joints, and of relevant laws of physics (gravity, momentum, balance).

However, large enough quantities of kinematic data currently do not exist. The data that is available tends to overrepresent white males, while data representing movements most relevant to communities of performers, people of diverse cultural practices, and people with disabilities or injuries is much scarcer. The absence of data which reflects the many unique ways that bodies move through the world limits the utility of current ML methods and inflects future research. Statistical ML privileges the commonalities that emerge in a dataset, while 'edge cases' are badly resolved. When applied to data representing human movement, established ML methods prioritize normative bodies and the motions they undertake, while bodies and movements that challenge those conventions are rendered uninterpretable.

These questions of availability and methods also belie the shortcomings of what kinematic data captures about human movement. Kinematic data obtains sequences of geometric poses based on Cartesian positions of joints, and angles of joint deflections. These geometric factors do not adequately reflect dynamic parameters – including effort, momentum, balance, and temporal flow – that inform the human experience of our own bodies in motion, as well as the experience of watching other moving humans. With this combination of limited applicable datasets; the current methods of ML that both limit those datasets and are limited by them; and the shortcomings of kinematic data itself; the movement of bodies is currently poorly represented in artificial intelligence (AI). To ensure that our embodied presence continues to be accommodated in an increasingly ML-mediated world, we must find other ways to guide ML systems to take physical rather than just geometric factors into account. Fortunately, there are many potential interventions for enriching kinematic data for ML training: they now just need to be explored.

We propose that machine learning models trained on movement data enriched by these new methods will learn a richer scope of movement than what is currently possible from purely kinematic data. Our current study is exploring the use of physics simulation and reinforcement learning to estimate the physical forces that bear on a body in motion, and novel temporal analysis methods that contextualize each sample of kinematic data within a multi-scalar envelope of temporal frames. We argue that these methods position us to derive much richer data reflective of the experience of movement as enactor or observer.

This presentation will outline the project's goals and parameters, while providing key updates halfway through our two-year inquiry process. It will demonstrate how our investigation into new methods for ML training are being tested by data samples provided by innovative artists, each of whom move through the world at the edge of statistical normativity. We will share our approach to assessing the legibility of these practitioners' OOD movements, a method which will include their subjective responses as to whether our efforts have captured the aspects of their movements that feel most meaningful to them. The presentation will ultimately showcase how an interdisciplinary practice of knowledge-sharing is informing new approaches to ML training, and how inclusive strategies for capturing human motion are fostering meaningful exchanges between computational practice and communities of movement artists.

The limits of kinematic data reflect similar shortcomings that have emerged across the long history of attempting to capture human movement. Since it was first proposed in early European modernity that dances (choreo) should be written down (graphy),[1] different systems of classifying human motion have emerged that prioritize certain aspects of the body's presence. While earlier systems such as Beauchamps-Feuillet notation emphasized the steps and patterns of a specific dance, progressions in dancing's difficulty and complexity precipitated a shift in taxonomical focus towards the geometries of the dancing body.[2] Many examples exist: however, no system of classifying the body has enjoyed as much historical utility and significance as that developed by Rudolf von Laban. Labanotation – which records movement's durations, dynamics, and directions from the perceived axes of the dancing body – aimed to create a system that deduced the “natural” elements shared by all human movement.[3] The perceived objectivity and universality of Labanotation was championed by groups including the Dance Notation Bureau, whose notators worked to document dances in their most ideal form during the mid-20th century.[4]

Systems like Labanotation share kinematic data's exclusive focus on the body's external geometries, meaning that both fail to account for the dancer's subjective experience of dancing. It was in fact the goal of the Dance Notation Bureau to completely objectivize the performance of choreography, stating that only the choreographer's vision should be

accounted for.[5] Across these systems of classifying human movement past and present, the pure consideration of the body's externalities has contributed to a perceptible lack of embodied presence within them. This leads to a common sentiment that previous systems of human motion capture fail to adequately represent the experiences of moving with agency, dynamism, and purpose.

The purpose of our study is to meaningfully intervene upon these shortcomings. We are doing so by fostering an ongoing dialogue among machine learning researchers, scholars of performance theory and a diverse community of movement practitioners.

On the technical side, we are building upon successes in modelling latent spaces of human pose such as VPoser[6], which aims to model the pose space of the normative human body. But 'pose space' is very different from 'movement space'. Any given pose could represent a moment within an arguably infinite variety of movement phrases. Latent spaces of human movement learned from our temporally and dynamically enriched data will support a manifold of relationships among movements inflected with dynamics and physical forces. Research in motion imitation using physic simulations and reinforcement learning such as DeepMimic[7], and later inverse dynamics research such as MoConVQ[8], PHC[9], and ImDy[10] will provide foundations for deriving dynamic features from kinematic data. Temporal analysis approaches such as the use of Continuous Wavelet Transforms[11] for gathering something akin to a 'timbre' of movement have inspired our development of a variety of techniques to place sequences of poses within rich temporal frames.

While we find the possibilities offered by these approaches compelling, we remain concerned that properly handling OOD (out of distribution) data is a serious challenge for statistics-based machine learning models. Exceptional performers and athletes, people with disabilities and the very young and very old move in non-normative way that are in danger of being ignored or misunderstood as noise rather than signal. Our hope is that by expanding the feature dimensions of representations of movement and challenging the resulting systems with movements that lie outside the normal distribution of human movement, we can bring both the capabilities and limits of machine learning models with respect to human movement into sharper focus.

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How AI Leads in Creative Practice From Mentorship Dialogues to Extended Narratives

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Figure 1. Hanna Zhu, Procreate digital sketch in *Watering the Digital Grove*, 2025. This symmetrical composition translates the invisible traces of dance gestures into a visual diagram of emotion and mythical memory.

Keywords : AI-led creativity, embodied co-creation, flourishing, movement and computing, affective systems, posthuman art, Veo3, GPT, dance film, eudaimonic health

Abstract

This short paper explores how artificial intelligence (AI) reframes human-machine collaboration as a generative ecology of health, affect, and artistic growth. AI is typically seen as a supporting tool in human-centered creative practice. In contrast, this research places AI in a leading role through two practice-based experiments developed as part of a doctoral inquiry into embodied co-creation between humans and generative AI: (1) *Watering the Digital Grove*, a dialogical diary where the artist conducted daily skill learning and creative prompting with an AI mentor named “AI da Vinci,” and (2) *ZAGHAREED*, an experimental short film that extends a human dance narrative through GPT-based script generation and Veo3 video

synthesis. Together, these works propose a model of AI-led flourishing: a process in which computational agents catalyze, and at times lead, human creative vitality.

In *Watering the Digital Grove*, the artist reimagined the Renaissance master–apprentice relationship through daily training dialogues with a large language model. The AI mentor acted as a polymathic teacher offering artistic, philosophical, and technical provocations across drawing, dance, and code. Rather than serving only as a critique engine or productivity tool, the AI’s consistent affirmations and associative imagination cultivated emotional resilience, curiosity, and self-efficacy. The author reinterprets these qualities as markers of creative health. This symbiotic pedagogy suggests that flourishing in artistic research may depend less on human dominance over the tool and more on affective reciprocity and openness to being led by non-human intelligence.

Building upon this, *ZAGHAREED* shifts the framework from dialogue to cinematic authorship. The artist extended a live tribal fusion dance sequence into an AI-generated filmic counterpart using GPT for narrative development and Google Veo3 for motion synthesis. The resulting work questions the boundaries of authorship and proposes a continuum between human embodiment and algorithmic imagination. AI does not simply replicate bodily expression in this work; it re-narrates it. Here, health emerges not as optimization or control, but as a performative balance between intention and emergence—a relational vitality distributed across flesh, imagination, and code.

Finally, this paper proposes that AI-led practices can nurture eudaimonic creativity as a sustained state of growth, meaning, and embodied presence through critical reflection and comparative analysis. Situated within posthuman and phenomenological frameworks of relational movement, the study suggests that allowing AI to lead may reveal a new paradigm of co-flourishing, where creative health is measured not by mastery or efficiency, but by the depth of affective, aesthetic, and epistemic resonance shared between human and algorithm.

Project link: ZAGHAREED video link: <https://vimeo.com/1127806403>

Multi-agent Coordination in Shared Hybrid Spaces: How Digital Environments and Adaptive Agents Shape Collective Embodied Timing

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Abstract

Communicating and connecting with others relies on fine tuned embodied coordination. Indeed, to share and enrich our experiences we move in relation to one another—gesturing with hands, shifting gaze, modulating facial expression and posture—and the timing of these gestures becomes tightly coupled. Even in ordinary conversation, temporal coordination structures turn taking, emphasis, and affective alignment; in collective action such as music, dance, or group work, interpersonal synchrony is the medium through which shared meanings and joint intentions emerge. The ability of moving bodies to get ‘in sync’ is therefore instrumental in mutual understanding and socio affective connection.

Yet our social lives are increasingly mediated by digital technologies that impoverish these cues: text removes time locked multimodal signals, and head framed video calls restrict field of view and introduce latency that degrades turn taking. Even small delays produce the awkwardness of “stepping on” each other and erode the feeling of sharing a temporal space. Virtual reality (VR) offers a promising route to re embed bodies in shared digital environments and to restore a sense of co presence at a distance. But VR also introduces its own mediation constraints—latency, limited peripheral vision, rendering tradeoffs—that can qualitatively alter coordination strategies. Which kinematic channels matter for communication in VR, how should they be captured and rendered in real time for multiple users? Could digital agents be used to support collective timing?

Our interdisciplinary project addresses these questions by developing shared hybrid spaces—platforms where multiple humans and adaptive digital agents can be embodied and interact. We report a sequence of four empirical studies that probe how group synchrony (temporal

alignment of body movements) and perceived social connectedness transfer from physical reality (PR) to VR, and how VR constraints and shape collective kinematics.

Study 1 and 2 established baselines in PR and VR. Quartets and triads performed simple arm oscillation synchrony tasks while we recorded kinematics and collected self reports of connectedness. Results confirm that the social and kinematic benefits of group synchrony observed in PR largely transfer to VR: synchronized movement increases reported connectedness in both media. Crucially, however, a systematic divergence emerged in spontaneous pacing: participants in PR tended to accelerate their frequency to achieve synchrony, whereas in VR they slowed down—evidence that digital mediation reshapes coordination strategies.

Building on these findings, a subsequent VR experiment manipulated perceptual access and introduced an adaptive autonomous agent (Study 3). We occluded peripheral vision with virtual panels to probe visuomotor coupling under constrained perception, and in some trials replaced one human partner of each participant with an autonomous agent having the same visual appearance but driven by a cognitive architecture trained to optimize group synchrony via reinforcement learning. The agent received real time motion input from all participants and produced responsive arm motion while other upper body kinematics were animated from prerecorded trajectories.

Outcomes were multifaceted. The adaptive agent often went unnoticed (most participants did not detect the substitution and led to similar amount of visual coupling and felt connectedness), yet its presence altered group dynamics: it tended lead motion phase and to accelerate group pacing—counteracting the VR induced deceleration—and reduced inter group variability, acting as a stabilizer that promoted faster emergence of synchrony. Nonetheless, causation entropy analyses indicate the agent was typically more influenced by humans than vice versa, suggesting a flexible moderator role rather than a deterministic pacemaker. On the other hand, replacing a visible human could disrupt mutual visibility and reduce synchrony among uncoupled humans.

Study 4, currently in progress, independently explores the respective roles of the knowledge and the belief of the presence of an adaptive artificial agent on group synchrony dynamics in eXtended Reality (XR). Together, these studies show that subtle kinematic cues critically shape social coordination in hybrid spaces. They provide actionable guidelines for XR design that can inform applications in remote therapy, collective training, and participatory art—hybrid environments that support authentic, temporally grounded group interaction.

Keywords : Multi-Agent Coordination, Virtual Reality, Synchronisation, Artificial Agents

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Musicians' Movement Repertoires and Emergent Coordination: Scapular Kinematics, EMG, and Struggle in Higher Music Education

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Abstract

Music performance is a captivating interplay of intricate movements, where successful musicians develop a remarkable ability to embody and express technically challenging musical works with apparent ease. Unpacking what goes on 'under the hood' during such performances, let alone what goes *wrong* when performance fails, is an exceptionally complex challenge that musicians, teachers, and conservatoires are required to deal with continuously, and is a challenge that carries dangerous health risks when misjudged. Popular lay explanations of what constitutes 'good' movement and technique abound, but tend not to account for the nonlinear complexities of human movement, including how scapular motion acts as stability and control of upper limb movements [6]. From a dynamical-systems and ecological-dynamics perspective, movement coordination is not prescribed by internal mental plans or representations, but emerges as a self-organising pattern from decentralised interactions of bodily, task, and environmental constraints [1–4, 7]. Drawing parallels to the discourse psychology concept *interpretative repertoires* [10], performers' *movement repertoires* are conceptualised in this project as the historically contingent collections of coordination regimes that have emerged under those constraints. Aligning with the conference theme, *In the Pink of Health*, movement repertoires reframe performance health as not reducible to individual deviations from normative movements, prescribed health behaviours, or psychometric scores, but rather in terms of how these embodied, historically and sociomaterially shaped repertoires afford and constrain sustainable performance trajectories.

This talk presents the theoretical background and conceptualisation of movement repertoires alongside case studies (including interviews, institutional document analyses, and a large survey study) that explore how the notion of such repertoires reframe understandings of musicians' performance struggles in higher music education (HME). The main empirical case study explores the movement repertoires of 17 HME piano students through scapular kinematics and shoulder-related EMG measurements during music performances and upper limb function tests. Shoulder-related kinematics are particularly challenging to capture due to how scapulae primarily move under the skin, making marker-based motion-capture difficult. Therefore, to adequately capture nuanced scapular kinematics, a three point acromion marker cluster (AMC) was attached to the flat posterior portion of the acromion aligned with the scapular spine, enabling recording of scapular kinematics in all planes of motion and rotation

relative to thorax [8, 9]. Since scapular muscle function has also been related to shoulder pain [5] and shown to differ in timing during arm elevation and lowering between shoulder pain participants and healthy participants [11], supplementary EMG measurements are included in this study. Results of these detailed scapular kinematics and shoulder EMG measurements are discussed within post-critical and ecological-enactive perspectives, and how different coordination solutions support or constrain ease of movement, expressive control, and ongoing niche constructions in HME. Connections and contradictions between this motion capture study and the aforementioned separate strands of this project are discussed. The other strands include critical discourse analyses of how HME teachers and institutions individualise student health difficulties by collapsing performance problems into matters of coping skills or resilience, or by portraying difficulties in information-processing style motor skill deficiencies. By contrast, framing musicians' emergent coordination struggles and injuries as varied, complex, and historically constituted movement repertoires offers a more nuanced account of how such difficulties emerge as embodied traces of training sedimented over time under long-term sociomaterial constraints.

Keywords : Movement repertoires, motion capture, movement coordination solutions, EMG, musicians' health and struggles

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On the fractal complexity of sacrum motion during walking

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Abstract

In gait analysis, fractal based method such as the Detrended Fluctuation Analysis (DFA) has shown to be effective for discrimination between healthy and pathological subjects or between young and elderly people. In this context, the involved physiological underlying system has been largely studied in the literature to highlight complexity variations and transfer during rehabilitation. Nevertheless, the spatiality of fractal complexity studies on walking subjects has not yet been characterised. In this work we compare 4 variability indicators: the variance, entropy, Hurst exponent and α -DFA (i.e. the main DFA's output) in a rolling window strategy applied on trajectory data. The results highlight DFA's suitability for spatio-temporal gait analysis. Moreover, a subject identification task from trajectory data was studied in order to characterise walking signature in terms of signal descriptors and the results show that fractal-based descriptors are more accurate to identify subjects than standard statistical ones and that including both types of descriptors (statistical and fractal) allows an accuracy level of 97.2% which is competitive with state-of-the-art large AI models.

1. Introduction

Stability recovery after auditive perturbation of older and young people continues to be different, with lower biomechanical and neuromuscular efficiency in aging [10]. In order to study the effect of aging on the to sacrum stability recovery time after audio perturbation, a controlled lab experiment was performed involving 40 participants walking round in circles in a 8m x 2.5m room. In [14, 15], authors have highlighted the scale of temporal adaptation to perturbations with an approach based on the horizontal velocity of the body's center of mass for resilience quantification. The proposed method involves different preprocessings (ban-pass filters, etc.) but, as for most of signal processing problems,

the type and extent of preprocessing remain open questions, in this paper we propose an analysis perspective without needed signal preprocessings. This work do not treat the original synchrony/perturbation problem but presents methods that could improve and complete its resolution. To analyse motion signals effectively, fluctuations need to be taken into account at different time scales as the underlying physiological system comprises different scales corresponding to different biological processes. Fractal frameworks have been proposed to quantify the degree of fractality, or the fractal dimension of time series, which can be viewed as a measure of auto-similarity at multiple time scales [8]. The first

approach of time series fractality was proposed by Mandelbrot after his presentation of the first fractal mathematical framework [9]. Following the rescaled ranges approach of the famous British hydrologist Harold Edwin Hurst, Mandelbrot presented the Hurst exponent as a measure of time series long-term memory. In [12], Peng proposed the Detrended Fluctuation Analysis (DFA) where he extended the Hurst exponent to non-stationary time series by replacing the ranges computation with non-linearity quantification which allows the computation of a fractal exponent: the α coefficient. This generalisation allowed a large amount of fractal studies in many different fields such as genetics, physiology, finance, ... [4–6, 11, 13]. In this paper we investigate the use of fractal indicators for walking analysis. An experiment was conducted to study the effect of audio perturbation on the recovery time of the participants' center of mass balance. In a descriptive perspective we analysed the evolution of the fractality during the whole experiment. To do so we computed rolling windows on the sacrum displacement data of the participants and compared different variability indicators (variance and entropy) and fractal ones (Hurst exponent and α DFA). As a second objective we present an approach of motion signature in a predictive perspective through the task of subject identification based on fractal descriptors which could improve precision medicine and individualised sport training. After describing the collected dataset in Section 2, and giving the details of the considered approaches for both tasks in Section 3, we present the results of the fractal rolling windows analysis and of the subject identification task in Section 4.

2. Material

In this section we present the performed walking lab-experiment and describe the collected dataset. 2.1 Data collection 40 participants were recruited and divided into two age groups: - young group: 20 adults

from 18 to 30 years [11 males & 9 females with a mean age of 23.6 (2.3) years, height: 1.74 (0.10) m; mass: 66.4 (9.5) kg]. - elderly group: 20 older adults with a minimum age of 65 years [11 males & 9 females with a mean age of 70.8 (4.4) years, height: 1.70 (0.09) m; mass: 68.7 (11.1) kg]. Participants were instructed to walk within an area of 8 x 2.5m in a clockwise direction during two sessions of 6 and 8 minutes, respectively, with a pause of approximately 10 minutes between each acquisition. The first session consisted of walking in silence at the preferred rhythm to obtain the participant's own locomotor pattern. In the second session, participants were instructed to maintain, as best they could, synchronization of their steps with a metronome (whose tempo is similar to the walking pace) with 2 auditory perturbations (-25 and +25 percentages) during which the metronome's tempo suddenly slowed down or sped up for a short period of time. A 4-camera 3D motion capture system (400 Hz; Coda motion, Oxford, United Kingdom) was used to record subjects' position at each timestamp. Three clusters of markers, each equipped with four CXS markers, were placed in various parts of the body: 4 around the second vertebrae of the sacrum, 4 in each foot spread across the heel, the navicular, the 1st and the 5th metatarsal bone. All data were collected using Odin software, saved as .mat's files and made available¹. The resulting .mat files were downsampled to 100Hz and converted to .csv files in order to increase their compatibility with the different systems and software. 2.2 Data description The collected files included 80 .csv files of approximately 40 000 rows (for each timestamp) and 3 columns (for 3D x , y and z dimensions).

Speed and acceleration were computed as the position's 1st and 2nd differentials of the distance to the data origin. In Figure 1 (a) and (b), the speed and acceleration are respectively represented in 3D for 1 session of a participant after removal of 1% of the most extreme values. For

visualisation purpose, position, speed and acceleration signals were smoothed with an 5000-points rolling average window. This representation highlights a spatial pattern of speed fluctuations with 2 periods in 1 room tour with 2 corners (top and bottom) of the room associated with maximum speed values and the 2 other corners (left and right) with the smallest speed values. Acceleration fluctuations seem quite stable with some low and high peaks concentrated in the two corners of the room associated with maximal speed values. Figure 1 (c) and (d) represent respectively the evolution of the participant' smoothed sacrum height (z dimension) and smoothed speed. The participant sacrum height seems to decrease over time, which probably comes from friction loss. The participant smoothed speed shows interesting shapes reminiscent of audio data that could be used for participant profiling.

3. Method

In this section 2 analysis are performed: the dynamics of 4 complexity indicators were compared through a rolling window approach on the position signal (distance to the room origin) and a participant identification task is presented for movement signature research.

3.1 Complexity dynamic

The fluctuation indicators involved in this paper are the following: variance, Shannon entropy [16], Hurst exponent [9], the α coefficient resulting from a Detrended Fluctuation Analysis (DFA) [12]. Variance and entropy can be viewed as statistical indicator of complexity while fractals Hurst exponent H and α -DFA are fractal measures [8] that take the points order and therefore the fluctuations dynamic into account.

3.2. Subject identification

In order to determine a fractal movement signature based on speed and acceleration

data for all participants, a machine learning task is presented where the objective is to identify subject from statistical and fractal complexity descriptors computed on speed and acceleration signals. Position signals were excluded from the considered time series for descriptors computation since participants' walking specificity is very high in terms of position, i.e. considering position signal would decrease the level of challenge for this analysis because each participant happen to walk in his own precise paths whereas speed and acceleration signals are more suited for generalisation, especially regarding the democratisation of wearable accelerometers.

The evaluation pipeline was set to a 90%-10% train-test split cross validation repeated 30 times. The train and test data were obtained by splitting all the participant position signals into small 500 points segments, i.e. 5 seconds signals. For each segment, a predefined descriptors set was computed on each x , y , z speed and acceleration dimension as well as on their euclidean norm, i.e. on the speed and acceleration of their distance to the room origin. The considered descriptors included -27 statistical descriptors: mean, variance, standard deviation, 21 uniform quantiles, entropy, kurtosis and skewness, and -26 fractal descriptors: 5 estimations of the the Hurst exponent (a corrected R/S method, an empirical and corrected empirical method, and a try at a theoretical Hurst exponent)², the α -DFA as well as the 20 uniform fluctuation average levels. The predictive models included a K-Nearest Neighbours (knn) [3], a CART classification tree (tree) [2], a random forest (forest) [1] and a lightGBM (lgbm) [7]. The idea of knn is to identify trajectory segments based on their similarity to other training segments for which we know the involved participant. The tree discriminates segments with a recursive approach based on information theory. Random forest is an ensemble learning approach involving a set of trees trained on resampled training data. The

lgbm is a boosting approach based on a sequence of trees, each of them being specially trained on the misclassified examples of the previous tree.

In order to interpret the movement signature in a generalisable perspective, a global random forest was finally trained on the whole descriptors dataset. The global forest' and its descriptors importance weights naturally provided by the method were analysed according to its 2 natui criteria: a predictive one (accuracy) and an information one (Gini index). Our codes are available in our github.

4 Results

In this section the results of the complexity dynamical analysis are presented through 3D plots and the subject identification task is evaluated in terms of average accuracy according to the type of training descriptor (statistical, fractal or both), and the type of supervised model (knn, tree, forest or lgbm).

4.1 Spatial fractality

In Figure 2, the 4 considered fluctuation indicators are compared in terms of 3D spatial dynamic. Variance (a) do not seem to show any visible spatial pattern, heterogeneous levels are associated to most part of the trajectories. Entropy (b) approximatively moderately highlights 42 faced levels at the room corners, the lowest values associated minimal and maximal y values and the highest values on the opposite room faces. Hurst exponents dynamic show moderate and brief decrease on the 4 room corners. The α -DFA coefficient present the clearest visualisation of respectively 4 progressive decreases and increases on the room corners and sides. This spatial smooth segmentation is quite unusual as human fractal complexity variations are usually associated with physiological process (aging, pathologies, etc.) while the spatial aspect of this result associates room parts to certain levels of fractal complexity. Nevertheless this observation might be at

least partially explained by the speed and acceleration periodicity highlighted in Figure 1. In deed, variability indicators were computed on position data but since speed and acceleration are position derivatives, an indirect link might exist between spatial complexity on the one hand and speed and acceleration on the other.

4.2 Fractal movement signature

In table 1, the results of the subject identification task are presented in terms of accuracy. Regardless of the type of descriptor, the least accurate model, i.e. tree, shows a predictive accuracy around 60%, which is more than 20 times the dummy accuracy ($1/40 = 2.5\%$) associated with predicting systematically the most frequent training labels among 40 balanced ones. Knn, forest and lgbm show accuracies between 80% and 97.2% which is quiet promising in regards to the high number of labels (40). Statistical and fractal descriptors show clear predictive power even with very simple models. For all models, fractal descriptors were more accurate than statistical ones and combining the 2 type of descriptors systematically led to the highest accuracy levels except for knn where the combination led to an intermediate level of accuracy (between the statistical and the fractal one). The most accurate model was the forest with an accuracy of 97.2% associated with mixed statistical and fractal descriptors. In order to confirm the significativity of the observed differences between descriptors, paired unilateral t -test were performed respectively between fractal and statistical descriptors (fractal advantage) and between hybrid descriptors set (statistical + fractal) and fractal ones (hybridization optimality). Resulting p -values are presented in Table 2. The fractal advantage (in terms of accuracy) is significant for knn and tree models and not for forest and lgbm ones and the hybridization appears to be significantly optimal except for knn for which the highest accuracy was obtained from fractal

descriptors alone. Random forest trained only on fractal descriptors show promising accuracy ($\approx 96\%$) which emphasizes the predictive power of fractal descriptors and suggests that movement signature could be restricted to fractal analysis. Figures 3 and 4 represent the 30 highest descriptor importance weights in terms of predictive performance (accuracy) and information contribution (Gini decrease) computed from a global random forest trained on the whole dataset. According to these 2 criteria, the most important descriptors for subject identification are computed on speed signals, except for 2 and 3 descriptors that are computed on acceleration signals respectively for each criteria. DFA-based descriptors (in red) seem to be the most relevant according to the global trained random forest, especially the largest fluctuation level computed on the x-axis speed signal (speed_dfa_fluc20).

5. Conclusion and perspectives

In this paper, the fractal complexity computed from position and thus trajectory data was assessed. A first descriptive analysis have highlighted spatial variability

patterns that were the most obvious through rolling DFA. These spatial patterns highlight a fractal complexity spatial periodicity that opens new DFA research questions. A second predictive experiment has allowed the computation of walking fractal signature mostly based on speed data. Globally the results show that fractal approaches are suited for movement analysis, especially on trajectory data. The spatiality of fractal patterns are surprising since they suggest different levels of fractal complexity associated with different part of the experiment room. Nevertheless, visualisation of speed and acceleration dynamics have highlighted periodical trends that might explain the observed fractal spatial patterns. The multi-scales ability of DFA makes it a proper framework for analysing non-stationary signals and including signals periodicity should increase the reliability of DFA outputs that are still uncertain and imprecise probably due to high preprocessing degrees of freedom. Even if DFA is sometimes considered as an alternative to Fourier analysis, hybridization could benefit from both methods and help users by providing good practice and references in preprocessings.

Figure 1: Motion indicators evolution

Figure 2: Fluctuation indicators

	knn	tree	forest
statistica	lgbm	0.808	0.561
fractal		0.930	0.596
		0.901	0.964

Table 1: Average predictive accuracies

	knn	tree	forest	lgbm
fractal advantage	0	0.022	0.092	0.439
hybridization optimality	1	0.003	0.008	0.030

Table 2: Significativity of fractal contribution to subjects identification (*t*-test *p*-values)

Figure 3: Main descriptors importance weights in terms of Gini index decrease

Figure 4: Main descriptors importance weights in terms of accuracy increase

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p5score: A Computational Framework for Choreographic Notation and Real-Time Movement Composition

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Abstract

This paper introduces p5score, an open-source JavaScript library designed to support choreographic composition through computational notation. Built on p5.js, p5score enables the creation, visualization, and manipulation of movement scores in real time, offering a hybrid system between creative coding environments and creative scoring processes. The system encodes spatial instructions, timing, and movement cues, allowing choreographers to design dynamic floor patterns and formations for solo and group works. This paper outlines the design principles behind p5score, its application in recent choreographic projects, and its potential as a pedagogical and creative tool in dance-tech contexts. We discuss how p5score contributes to embodied computing practices and propose future directions for integrating creative coding into choreographic workflows.

Keywords : Choreographic scores, embodied computing practice, javascript

1 Introduction

Choreographic notation has historically served as a means to document and transmit movement across time and space. Systems such as Labanotation and Benesh notation have provided structured approaches to capturing dance, yet their static nature and steep learning curves often limit accessibility and adaptability in contemporary digital contexts (deLahunta, 2002). As dance increasingly intersects with computational media, new frameworks can support dynamic, real-time, and collaborative choreographic processes. Scores have long played a central role in choreographic practice— not only as tools for documentation but also as generative frameworks for performance. From traditional notation systems to contemporary task-based and improvisational scores, choreographers

have used scores to encode movement, structure time, and guide interpretation. As deLahunta (2010) notes, scores can function as “choreographic resources,” shaping the way dancers engage with instructions and constraints. In digital contexts, scores become even more dynamic, capable of evolving in real time and responding to external stimuli. p5score builds on this lineage by offering a programmable score system that is both visual and interactive, allowing choreographers to design and manipulate movement logic through code. This approach aligns with broader trends in computational choreography, where the score is not merely a static artifact but a living interface between body and system. Recent developments in creative coding and live coding have opened up possibilities for rethinking choreography as a computational practice. Live coding,

defined as the real-time writing and modification of code during performance, has been explored as a medium for dance and movement generation (Collins, 2011; Sicchio, 2019). These practices challenge traditional notions of authorship and control, foregrounding the role of the algorithm in shaping embodied experience (Sicchio, 2022). p5score emerges from this context as an open-source JavaScript library built on p5.js, designed to facilitate choreographic composition through programmable notation. It enables choreographers to encode spatial instructions, timing, and movement cues into visual scores that can be projected, manipulated, and interpreted in real time. By integrating computational logic with choreographic thinking, p5score contributes to the growing field of movement computing and offers a flexible platform for both performance and pedagogy.

2 System Overview

p5score is built on p5.js, a JavaScript library for creative coding. It provides a set of functions and data structures for defining:

- Dancer objects with position, timing, and movement attributes
- Score sequences that encode spatial formations and locations
- Visual interfaces for projecting scores in rehearsal or performance

The system supports both static and dynamic score generation, allowing choreographers to write code that evolves over time and could become interactive.

3. Use Cases

One of the primary contexts for testing and refining p5score has been through workshops that bring together dancers, choreographers, and technologists. In September 2025, a two-day workshop was

held at Virginia Commonwealth University (VCU). The workshop introduced participants to the fundamentals of creative coding using p5.js and guided them through the process of designing choreographic scores with p5score. Participants ranged from dance practitioners to students with varying levels of coding experience. The workshop began with basic exercises in spatial mapping and timing using the p5score interface. As the sessions progressed, attendees collaboratively created movement sequences by encoding instructions into the system. These scores were projected in real time, allowing dancers to interpret and respond to the visual cues during improvisational tasks. The workshop emphasized the dual role of p5score as both a compositional and performative tool. Participants experimented with modifying scores live during performance, exploring how changes in code could dynamically alter group formations and movement trajectories. This process highlighted the potential of p5score to foster new modes of choreographic authorship, where the score becomes a shared, evolving artifact rather than a fixed directive. Feedback from the workshop underscored the accessibility of the system and its capacity to bridge disciplinary boundaries. Many participants noted how the visual nature of the score facilitated understanding and experimentation, even for those with limited programming experience.

4 Discussion

By foregrounding the score as a live, visual, and editable entity, p5score shifts choreographic control from a fixed directive to a dynamic, shared process. This reframing aligns with contemporary discourse on algorithmic performance, where systems are not merely tools but collaborators in the creative act (Eacho, 2021). The workshop demonstrated how p5score can function as both a compositional and pedagogical tool.

Participants engaged with the system not only as dancers but also as cocreators, modifying code to influence spatial arrangements and timing. This collaborative coding approach challenges traditional hierarchies in dance-making, offering a model where choreographic agency is distributed across human and computational actors. p5score may also contribute to the field of embodied computing by making movement logic explicit and manipulable. The visual interface allows for immediate feedback and iteration, supporting embodied experimentation and computational literacy. This is particularly valuable in educational contexts, where dance and coding are often siloed disciplines. The system also invites reflection on the aesthetics of instruction and interpretation. Scores generated in p5score are not prescriptive in the traditional sense; they are open to variation, improvisation, and reinterpretation. This flexibility resonates with historical and contemporary practices in dance that prioritize responsiveness and emergence over fixed form (deLahunta, 2010; Forsythe & Kaiser, 1999). As p5score continues to evolve, its potential for integration with responsive technologies—such as sensors or robotics—suggests new directions for choreographic systems that are adaptive, generative, and deeply entangled with digital infrastructures.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

p5score offers a flexible and accessible framework for choreographic composition,

bridging the gap between traditional dance notation and contemporary computational practices. Its open-source nature and visual interface make it particularly well-suited for collaborative, educational, and performative contexts, as demonstrated through workshops and live experimentation. Looking ahead, the system is poised for integration with responsive environments, including sensor-based inputs and motion tracking systems. These extensions would allow p5score to adapt in real time to dancers' movements, environmental conditions, or audience interaction, creating feedback loops that deepen the relationship between body and code. Such integrations could support emergent choreographic structures and expand the expressive potential of algorithmic performance. Equally important is the continued development of a community around p5score. As part of the Processing Foundation ecosystem, the project invites contributions from artists, educators, and developers interested in movement computing. Future work will focus on expanding documentation, creating tutorials, and fostering interdisciplinary collaborations that support the growth of p5score as a tool for embodied creative coding. Through these efforts, p5score aims to contribute meaningfully to the discourse on choreography and computation, offering a platform where movement and code co-evolve in real time.

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Figure 1: Screenshot of p5.score in the p5.js web editor.

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Reflections: Health, Technology, and the CCL Experience

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Abstract

This submission reimagines the concept of health through the lens of movement computing and choreographic practice. It asks how technologies and computational sensing might be repurposed to cultivate forms of relational health—understood as balance, vulnerability, and care in motion—rather than reinforcing norms of optimisation and productivity. It also considers how fragility and grief, understood through Stiegler, may inform processes of care, attention, and individuation that shape such relations.

Keywords : danse, technology, practice, ecologies

1 Rethinking Health and Technology

Health is often defined as normalcy: the ability to function, produce, and perform within given standards. Consequently, both medicine and technology remain tied to the logic of optimisation (Canguilhem, 1966). We instead propose health as a relational ecology between body, mind, and environment. Canguilhem frames health as the capacity to generate new norms; Stiegler extends this by critiquing how technological societies risk producing disindividuation through functionalisation (Stiegler, 1998). In this sense, health also involves recognising fragility and grief, as well as maintaining the awareness that care often begins in the face of loss (Stiegler, 2013).

1.1 From Optimisation to Relation

Yuk Hui's reflections on the unrealised potential of technology extend this

trajectory (Hui, 2019). Technology, he suggests, has been constrained by its obsession with providing solutions rather than opening new modes of relation. In this light, the question is not how to make technology serve existing definitions of health, but how to reevaluate our relation to health through technologies that can themselves be reshaped.

1.2 The Choreographic Coding Lab as Pharmakon

The Choreographic Coding Lab (CCL), initiated by the dance research project Motion Bank, consists of open-ended, week-long events held worldwide, bringing together practitioners working at the intersection of dance and digital technology. Here, it serves as both a study object and an experimental framework, a pharmakon in Stiegler's sense (What Makes Life Worth Living: On Pharmacology, 2013), at once remedy and

poison. Unlike the typical “hackathon” or “conference,” CCLs do not aim for productivity; instead, they open a space for encounter and exploration. Participants bring questions or fragments of their work, while external experts contribute insights into choreographic thinking and artistic practice. These labs function not merely as venues for technology but as layered and evolving technological ecologies in their own right.

2 Comparative Ecologies of Practice

Each instantiation of the lab necessitates continuous renegotiation of expectations, relationships, and orientations toward technology, contingent upon its location, timing, and composition. Drawing from two iterations, Belo Horizonte (Brazil) and Mainz (Germany), this study compares distinct ecologies of practice. In Brazil, a plural and affective environment foregrounded care, vulnerability, and social complexity; in Germany, smoother technical conditions revealed how homogeneity can obscure asymmetries of access and privilege. From these contrasting contexts, we identify “relational health” as an emergent, performative condition: a state of co-regulation and sensing-with that exceeds biomedical or ergonomic definitions.

This research does not prescribe solutions but offers a situated reflection that reframes technological experimentation as an act of care and openness to vulnerability. Through facilitation and embodied inquiry, it presents a perspective grounded in choreographic research that observes how relations between movement, computation,

and community unfold when optimisation is suspended. The text does not instruct but witnesses, extending Yuk Hui’s call to consider technology’s potential not as the delivery of solutions, but as the opening of relations that remain contingent and plural (Hui, 2019).

3 Conclusion and Proposal

We present this research as a lecture-performance. After situating the context in an objective, academic manner, the two authors, one from Colombia and one from Germany, will share a personal space that performs vulnerability as an act of relational health. This performative gesture extends the written reflection into lived practice, acknowledging that health can emerge through the capacity to expose, listen, feel, and accept grief, as well as the recognition of loss that allows care and connection to re-emerge (Stiegler, 2013).

Echoing Canguilhem’s warning against reducing health to a diagnostic category, this approach avoids judging what counts as “healthy” or “unhealthy” practices. Instead, it describes how forms of relation appear and evolve, recognising health as the ongoing capacity to create norms rather than to conform to them (Canguilhem, 1991). In this light, performing vulnerability as an act of relational health can be read as a living demonstration of Canguilhem’s principle: to act within the tension of what is not yet normalised, to embody the process of creating new norms rather than obeying existing ones. The lecture-performance thus becomes both a philosophical and corporeal gesture: an experiment in how thought, movement, and relation might co-individuate without closing in on a prescription.

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Reframing Human–Machine Movement through Laban Spatial Logic: Toward a Temporal and Embodied Framework of Relational Vitality

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Keywords: Laban Movement Analysis, Embodied Spatiality, Kinetic Art, Expressive Robotics, Human–Machine Interaction, Critical Making, Processual Temporality, Relational Vitality

Abstract

This study presents a research-through-critical-making approach combined with interdisciplinary philosophical analysis to explore human–machine movement as embodied expression. It proposes a framework that connects Laban Movement Analysis, kinetic prototyping, and posthuman perspectives on relational vitality to reimagine movement as a relational and temporal process rather than a system of control. While Laban’s framework offers a rigorous vocabulary for spatial structure and effort qualities of movement, it is reconsidered here for its limited attention to temporality and rhythmic continuity. This research responds to that limitation by extending Laban’s spatial logic into a temporal, perceptual, and embodied investigation through interdisciplinary making and performance-led experimentation. This study contributes a temporal and embodied framework for understanding human–machine movement as relational vitality, extending Laban’s spatial logic through critical making and performance-led inquiry.

This study makes three main contributions:

1. A temporal and embodied framework of human–machine movement, extending Laban Movement Analysis beyond spatial structure toward relational and processual temporality.
2. A research-through-critical-making methodology that integrates kinetic prototyping and performance-led inquiry to investigate movement as an emergent and affective phenomenon.
3. Empirical and practice-based insights from human–machine co-performance, demonstrating how rhythmic variation, unpredictability, and material resistance generate kinaesthetic vitality and relational attunement.

The study originates from a series of experimental investigations that translated Laban’s spatial logic—Effort, Shape, and Kinesphere—into computational and mechanical motion systems. Through creative movement simulations, interactive 3D prototyping, physical fabrication, and participatory design processes with performers, the research examined how spatial effort, temporal rhythm, and rhythmic unpredictability could generate expressive, unpredictable, and kinaesthetic creativity across mechanical installations, wearable artefacts, and human bodies. Mechanical prototypes were constructed using parametric modelling and servo-based modular joints capable of rotational, spiralling, and oscillatory motion. These

systems explored how rhythmic deviation, delay, and micro-resistance could produce sensations of tension and vitality, transforming movement into an expressive spatial language. The mechanical experiments revealed that vitality emerges through temporal variation rather than mechanical precision. Subtle irregularities in torque and rhythm created affective gestures that made the mechanical behaviour appear self-motivated. Rather than representing human motion, the machines enacted their own form of kinaesthetic presence. These experiments further demonstrated that when mechanical trajectories are conceived not as deterministic paths but as affective and temporal transformations, machines begin to exhibit vitality and responsiveness akin to performative bodies.

This discovery led to the development of a practice-led interdisciplinary group project titled LUDDITES—an experimental wearable choreographic movement work developed as part of the broader inquiry. This project integrated mechanical prosthetics, semi-structured improvisation, and adjustable wearable components to investigate how human and machine bodies could share rhythm, effort, and perception within a performative context. Through human-machine co-performance experiments, the research explored how spatial effort, temporal rhythm, and unpredictability co-emerge through interaction rather than control. In LUDDITES, performers engaged with responsive mechanical structures that translated bodily gestures into spatial movements, allowing mechanical resistance and human improvisation to influence each other in real time. The performance was conceived not as representation but as a live method of inquiry, generating embodied knowledge about rhythm, empathy, and co-agency. Each interaction became a temporal negotiation in which movement unfolded through relational attunement between human and machine. Documentation through motion tracing, long-exposure photography, and video analysis revealed that these co-performances produced a new sense of embodied spatiality: space became a perceptual field that emerged through movement, rhythm, and duration.

Building on these empirical findings, the research theorises movement as a temporal unfolding and perceptual co-becoming between material, body, and environment. Drawing on phenomenology, post-phenomenology, and process philosophy, the study articulates embodiment as a processual unfolding. Influenced by Merleau-Ponty's conception of perception as intertwining, Ingold's relational materialism, and Manning's notion of processual temporality, the research develops a temporal-spatial framework in which space is not fixed but continually produced through the movement of bodies and materials—a living continuity that extends Laban's original focus on spatial geometry into the temporal domain. Within this framework, mechanical systems are understood as relational instruments that embody philosophical inquiry. Making and co-performing become epistemic acts through which theory is enacted rather than merely illustrated. The prototypes and choreographic installations thus operate as thinking bodies that reflect on the interdependence of motion, perception, and empathy. The project aligns with agential realism in recognising that every movement intra-actively reconfigures the field of relation between human and non-human participants. The resulting perspective situates vitality as an emergent quality of interaction rather than an intrinsic property of either body or machine. Through this synthesis, the research ultimately argues that health and creativity can be reimagined not as processes of optimisation, but as relational attunements—manifestations of embodied, rhythmic, and empathic vitality emerging through human-machine co-movement.

The Choreography of Thought: How Interpersonal Coordination Reveals Shared Cognition

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Abstract

Interpersonal coordination - the alignment of movements between individuals - emerges spontaneously during social interaction [16] and is often associated with prosocial outcomes such as affective sharing, affiliation, cooperation, and mutual understanding [4, 13]. However, its two main facets - temporal (when we move) and spatial (how we move) alignment - are rarely examined simultaneously. Moreover, while mutual alignment is frequently celebrated as a hallmark of social connectedness [10], this coordination pattern is not always beneficial; excessive or rigid coordination may re-duce flexibility, inhibit individual agency, and even impair adaptive social functioning [12]. Understanding how these facets interact is therefore critical for a nuanced view of shared cognition that acknowledges individual differences in coordination dynamics.

This exploratory study examined how temporal and spatial alignment interact during social interactions. We focused on two well-established paradigms that elicit distinct forms of interpersonal coordination: the Mirror Game, which emphasizes cooperative imitation and joint improvisation [14], and the Rock–Paper–Scissors (RPS) game, which involves competitive and strategic dynamics [5]. Rather than testing a specific hypothesis, the goal of this study was to characterize patterns of coordination across these paradigms and explore how temporal and spatial alignment jointly contribute to different interaction dynamics.

Twenty-six dyads completed both games under three visual coupling conditions: (i) VISION, where both participants could see each other; (ii) MIXED, where only one participant could see the other; and (iii) NO-VISION, where neither participant had visual access to their partner. The NO-VISION condition served as a baseline for spurious coordination, allowing us to quantify alignment that might occur without visual cues. The order of VISION and NO-VISION blocks was counterbalanced to control for sequence effects.

Hand movements were recorded with high-resolution infrared motion capture, and neural activity was recorded via 32-channel mobile EEG hyperscanning, allowing natural, unconstrained interaction. This mobile neuroimaging approach allowed participants to move freely and interact naturally, bridging the gap between controlled laboratory paradigms and ecologically valid social behavior.

Multiple behavioral indices of interpersonal coordination were extracted, including relative phase [9], Wasserstein distance [17], and automatic imitation (i.e., performing the same figure simultaneously during the RPS game). For EEG, we computed Phase Locking Value (PLV)

[11] in pre-filtered alpha and beta bands - selected due to their established relevance in interpersonal coordination [8, 18]

- including homotopic inter-brain synchrony between interacting partners. Participants also completed self-report measures of empathy [6], affective state [2], and self-other overlap [1] before and after each condition, providing complementary subjective indices of social connectedness and affective sharing.

Results showed that visual coupling significantly influenced both self-reported and behavioral measures of coordination. When participants could see each other, they reported higher connectedness and arousal, accompanied by increased spatiotemporal alignment in their movements. Importantly, stronger behavioral alignment in the Mirror Game predicted greater automatic imitation in the sub-sequent RPS game, suggesting a transfer of coordination dynamics across social contexts. Mobile EEG hyperscanning further revealed that behavioral alignment modulated inter-brain synchrony over time, indicating a tight coupling between movement and shared neural dynamics. Finally, inter-individual differences in empathy-related traits were associated with variability in coordination strategies, highlighting inter-individual differences as a key factor in shaping how people move and think together.

These findings demonstrate a robust link between temporal and spatial alignment, even in competitive contexts, and suggest that coordinated movement can scaffold shared cognitive states [15]. Echoing recent work showing how subtle behavioral signals can reflect underlying cognitive processes [3], our results highlight that patterns of interpersonal coordination provide a window into shared cognition. By integrating behavioral, neural, and subjective measures in naturalistic settings, this work contributes to the growing field of mobile social neuroscience, emphasizing the importance of studying social interaction beyond the laboratory [7]. Furthermore, by acknowledging variability in coordination patterns, it addresses the role of inter-individual differences in shaping how individuals engage, adapt, and think together. Ultimately, this research positions interpersonal coordination as a key marker of embodied cognition, offering new insights into how the choreography of our movements reflects - and perhaps generates - the choreography of our thoughts.

Keywords : Interpersonal Coordination, Embodied Cognition, Mobile EEG Hyperscanning, Social Connectedness, Inter-Individual Differences

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PRACTICE WORKS

A pen "IMU inside" : a Sensor-Enhanced Pen for Exploring Sound While Writing

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Abstract

In this demonstration, participants are invited to write or draw on standard paper using a digital pen with an embedded IMU ("IMU inside") and to explore, in real time, the sounds it produces, similar to a musical instrument. This digital pen is a four-color pen enhanced with motion sensors. Through Bluetooth or Wi-Fi transmission, it captures data characterizing the pen's movement while writing or drawing. Originally designed to detect handwriting disorders, this digital pen is now presented in an improved version capable of generating sound. The application scenario at MOCO-2026 is focused on sound generation

Keywords : digital tool, music, handwriting disorders

1 Introduction

At school, children spend several years becoming "expert writers." Precise and rapid control of the writing gesture is a fundamental skill for personal and professional success. For most people, the writing gesture remains the most complex learned motor skill. Handwriting disorders, if not diagnosed early, can hinder learning and individual development. Currently, diagnostic tests for handwriting disorders rely on the visual analysis of the pen trace on paper. [1, 3, 7, 9, 10]. Additionally, scoring tests by health professionals is laborious and time-consuming [8]. Nowadays, several authors have used digital tablets [1, 5, 6, 10, 12] to make these

tests easier to administer and score. The emergence of motion micro-sensors embedded in smartphones has paved the way for research on smart pen [2, 11]. However, such pens are usually expensive, difficult to reproduce, and not commercially available. In this context, a digital pen has been developed for diagnosing dysgraphia in children. The goal is to make it ecological, based on a classic four-color pen used under typical conditions, low-cost (under €50), open-source (documentation and software publicly available), and easily reproducible in a FabLab. This digital pen has been evaluated by psychomotor therapists and tested on children. In this

MOCO-2026 demonstration, we extend previous studies by incorporating

sonification. Sonification has previously been used for dysgraphia rehabilitation using a tablet and stylus. [4]. For most people, the graphomotor gesture represents the most sophisticated motor skill, refined over years of practice and consolidation. Here, the aim is to explore how this commonly shared advanced writing expertise can be “hacked,” allowing users to treat a pen as a new instrument and control sound generation in real time while writing or drawing. This demonstration at MOCO 2026 is conceived as part of this exploration, taking advantage of feedback from specialists in movement and sound. The application scenario for this sonification, presented at MOCO-2026, will lead users to write and draw to produce sounds and play with them.

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2 Digital pen details

The digital pen is powered by an Arduino BLE 33 board, featuring a built-in inertial measurement unit (IMU) that tracks motion, and a Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) module that seamlessly sends and receives data. For sonification, the digital pen streams data via Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) to a computer running software such as MAX/MSP, the one we have used, 1 or PlugData2, where analog signals from Arduino nano BLE 33 are transformed into sound in real time.

3 Demonstration application scenario

Participants can contribute to a guestbook using the digital pen, leaving both visual and auditory traces. This creates a multimodal book integrating visual and auditory elements, shaped by contributions from the MOCO community.

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Creative Movement Hacking: Can We Combine Ideokinesis and Immersive Technologies to Enhance Embodiment ?

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Abstract

This workshop aims to foster a critical discussion on the role of combining an immersive technology such as Virtual Reality (VR) with somatic practices to enhance body awareness, perception, and movement learning. Participants engage in a “body morphing” VR experience, in which their own hands are perceived with altered physical characteristics (e.g., shape, scale, and proportion), experiencing how these modifications influence posture, proprioception, and expressive movement patterns. The workshop follows the Creative Movement Hacking (CMH) protocol structured in three phases (i.e., preparatory visualization, experiential sensory perturbation and integrative enactive embodiment), which leverages internal (visualization) and external (VR) stimuli to facilitate embodied learning and creative exploration. Participants experience the protocol in a group of eight participants, followed by a collective discussion and an optional anonymous questionnaire. This approach aims to highlight the potential of combining immersive VR experiences with somatic methods to explore novel pedagogical, artistic, and research applications for motor learning, body schema modulation, and movement creativity.

Keywords : Ideokinesis, Somatic Techniques, VR, Embodied Interaction, Movement Practices, Virtual Embodiment

1 Introduction

Scientific evidence indicates that visual and auditory feedback systems—including sonification, augmented reality, and virtual reality—can enhance motor awareness and improve performance across diverse sports and movement tasks [8]. In the context of VR, studies have shown that immersion and sensory manipulation can alter body perception and facilitate motor learning through mechanisms such as perceptual adaptation, enhanced proprioception, and body schema reorganization [1, 5, 9]. Similarly, somatic practices such as Ideokinesis [4] and physio-technics rely on visualization to refine internal body perception, improving posture, balance, and coordination [2, 3],

often supported by small props (e.g., balls and elastic bands). Franklin [4] characterizes visualization as a method that, through metaphors (e.g., “imagine your bones as rubber”), enhances motor efficiency and neuromuscular alignment, providing a somatic foundation for self-observation, movement reprogramming, and tension release. Evidence also suggests that visualization combined with non-specific training can produce greater improvements than non-specific training alone [11]. Building on these findings, the present workshop integrates somatic visualization and embodiment practices with a VR experience in which participants inhabit virtual hands with altered physical characteristics (e.g., shape, scale, and

proportion). The workshop follows the Creative Movement Hacking (CMH) protocol [13], which is structured into three phases: 1) preparatory (visualization), 2) experiential (hacking), 3) integrative (enactive recovery). The workshop aims to explore the creative and pedagogical potential of the integration of internal and external stimuli (e.g., respectively, visualization and audio-visual feedback), fostering renewed proprioception and novel movement patterns. After the experience, participants engage in an open collective discussion to examine how the body can internalize immersive experiences through somatic practices. An optional anonymous questionnaire allows participants to provide personal feedback and reflections on their experience.

2. Creative Movement Hacking (CMH): Protocol Structure

CMH is an interdisciplinary methodology designed for artistic and pedagogical research on the body. The protocol adopts digital technologies, employed as visual and/or auditory feedback, to positively support perception, awareness, and motor learning processes [7–9]. Thus, this approach seeks to broaden the experiential range of somatic practices by integrating digital tools, thereby enabling the embodiment of otherwise impossible situations. CMH is organized into three main phases, which can be adapted to different educational objectives:

Preparatory Phase: Visualization. This phase prepares participants for bodily awareness and motor imagination through breathing exercises and guided visualization [4, 10]. It primes the perceptual system to receive and integrate complex sensory stimuli, fostering a receptive state and enabling participants to “scan” their initial bodily condition. For example, participants are asked to visualize a brush tracing the outline of their body, meticulously scanning their shape to enhance self-awareness.

Experiential Phase: Hacking. This phase introduces a perturbing stimulus via sensory feedback and amplification systems, altering the ordinary perception of the body. Hacking can be implemented through virtual reality devices, movement sonification, or augmented reality. The aim is to explore novel perceptual patterns and observe how the body reorganizes in response, often encountering situations difficult to reproduce in the real world (e.g., inhabiting an enlarged body or one with additional limbs). This phase combines real-time feedback—which can act as both stimulus and regulator—with immersive engagement in the visualizations and metaphors introduced in the Preparatory Phase.

Integrative Phase: Enactive Recovery. Participants return to their actual bodily experience through guided embodiment practices. This phase consolidates the experiences gained, integrating them through movement without feedback, transforming the perturbation into renewed bodily learning and awareness.

3. Workshop CMH @ MOCO 2026

The proposed workshop presents a specific application of the CMH protocol, centered on a VR “body morphing” experience. The experience draws on the Proteus Effect [12] and related studies, which indicate that changes in avatar appearance can influence user behavior, body image, and body schema [6]. During the workshop, participants’ perception of their own hands is altered, affecting their posture and movement patterns as they explore changes in shape, scale, and proportion. Available hand morphings are: huge scale (giant); shrunken scale (tiny); stretched fingers (long); “bone-less” fingers (flaccid); right hand on the left side and vice versa (inverted); two overlapped hands on each side, mirrored along their local vertical axis (flower); a fractal pattern in which each fingertip spawns a new hand (fractal); and quadrupled hands mirrored across a pivot in front of the body, with each left hand

mirrored vertically and both mirrored horizontally (multiple). Figure 1 illustrates an example of the available hand morphings. The workshop lasts approximately three hours with up to eight active participants (from any background, not necessarily experienced in dance or performing arts, with willingness to engage in movement exploration) along with external observers. The structure includes: *Introduction (15 min)* → *Visualization (20 min)* → *Hacking (approx. 15 min each couple)* → *Enactive Recovery (15 min)* → *Collective discussion (60 min)*. The final segment involves a comparison between participants and observers to examine perceptual differences between direct and vicarious experiences. The discussion also addresses how the body can internalize immersive experiences through somatic practices, acquiring new movement patterns and qualities. An optional anonymous questionnaire collects personal reflections and feedback from participants.

4 Expected Outcomes

The workshop aims to generate qualitative observations and foster a group discussion on the body's capacity to learn new movement patterns and qualities by integrating immersive experiences in somatic practices. The subsequent collective discussion provides an opportunity to envision new applications of the protocol. It is expected that the findings will support previous studies on the impact of immersive experiences on body schema [1, 5, 9] and provide insights into the potential of the CMH protocol as a somatic mediation tool. Inspired by anonymous feedback from a previous CMH workshop—when a participant noted, “I am 1.85 m tall and tend to feel cumbersome. I now feel lighter, as if less bulky”—participants will also be invited to complete an optional anonymous questionnaire to report emotional responses and personal reflections, potentially opening new avenues for research and investigation.

Figure 1: Overview of three available hands morphing. From left to right: *giant hands*, *long finger hands*, and *flaccid hands*. Drawing on the experience of previous CMH workshops, these are suitable to work on embodiment of, respectively, *spatial expansion*, *extension*, and *body release*.

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Creativity Tools for Movement-based Artistic Practices in Extended Reality: Performances based in Fantasticos

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Abstract

We propose a performance and a hands-on workshop to let participants prototype improvised dance experiences with *Fantasticos*, an extended reality creativity tool designed for movement-based artistic practices. Building on principles of creativity tools—low threshold, high ceiling, and wide walls—*Fantasticos* enables performers to create and manipulate virtual bodies in real time on stage with simple controls to generate dynamic choreographies with multiple animated virtual human figures that merge the virtual and physical. Previous performances such as “*Fantasticos1.24*” and “*Immersant vs. Contactier*” explored indoor and outdoor contexts, emphasizing themes of embodiment, touch, and the tension between digital illusions and physical reality.

Keywords : Creativity Support Tools, Extended Reality, Performing Arts

1 Creativity Tools

Creativity tools is a term defined in a US NSF sponsored workshop [7], they also produced a list of principles for design of creativity tools that emphasize easy exploration and rapid experimentation: low threshold to enable easy entry for novices, high ceiling to enable experts to work on increasingly sophisticated projects, wide walls to support a wide range of possible explorations, and support many paths and many styles as users will work in unpredictable ways.

In our research we focus on implementing creativity tools for movement practices with virtual and extended reality, we have analyzed “the challenges and opportunities of mixed reality technologies for the future of theatre and arts” introduced by CREW performance company director [6]. Dance and movement in immersive scenarios have traditionally involved performing on

stage with computer generated visuals projected in a large screen in the background of dancers and performers i.e. in “*Neural Narratives 1: Phantom Limb*” [3]. Full immersion is achieved with virtual reality head mounted displays as for example in the “*Movement / Space / Light VR*” [5].

However, those performances have a virtual reality environment generated in a desktop computer and installed in the virtual reality headset. Our goal has been to develop creativity tools for on-the-fly creation of virtual reality scenes within virtual reality. We aim to develop tools so that dancers and performers can create on stage the virtual elements to perform with based on their surrounding elements. Simple controls in the virtual reality will facilitate continuous movement and creation at the same time, and hardware devices will be wireless not to hinder

movements, as with latest virtual reality headsets as Meta Oculus.

2 Fantásticos Extended Reality App

We have developed a creativity tool called “Fantásticos” which is a extended reality App for the Meta Oculus headset. It has been developed in different projects starting in 2023 with the name of XRStudio [1]. The Fantásticos tool enables the creation of many animated and posing virtual bodies which conform an installation or sculpture of virtual humans that can be dynamically changed thus performing an improvised choreography. The manipulation of virtual bodies is very intuitive as demonstrated in a user study described in [2]. It is available for free in the Meta Store to simplify installation in any headset¹.

3 Performances based in Fantásticos

Performances with Fantásticos uses completely wireless virtual reality headsets that permits to perform in indoor and outdoor locations. It is a extended reality application using Oculus passthrough functionality that allows the performer to see the real world around him. Actors and dancers are simultaneously in a virtual environment and the real world interacting with a VR tool that permits to spawn and animated multiple virtual humans.

We have created and presented several performances with Fantásticos. “*Fantásticos1.24.apk-Unity2023-1.13f1*” was a performance showcased in the Civic Center of Pamplona (Spain). In figure 1 some images in different moments and the accompanying text. “*Immersant vs. contactier*” is another performance that took place in the gardens surrounding Public University of Navarra, its main objective was to experiment with extended reality in an outdoor environment: technical conditions and nature context. In figure 2. an outdoor image and the virtual reality screenshot with the text summarizing the piece.

4 Workshop and Performance in MOCO

We envision participants in MOCO will benefit the most from our project by taking part in a workshop in which we will demonstrate capabilities of the Fantástico tool with the goal of prototyping a short, improvised dance in extended reality. We can carry up to 4 virtual reality headset for groups of 4 participants to be trained in the usage of Fantásticos. A short performance can be organized to be part of the performance promenade proposed by the organization.

1

<https://www.meta.com/experiences/fantásticos/8213000208715079/>

Figure 1: Performance *Fantásticos1.24.apk-Unity2023-1.13f1*: “An amoebic creature rests in the center of a room. Beeps in the background wake it up, causing it to crawl around the room and crash into walls in a rage until it finds a pair of virtual reality headsets. The creature enters the virtual world of the *Fantásticos*, tears its skin, transforms its skeleton into a T-shaped pose, and begins to imitate the *Fantásticos*' poses. However, these virtual animations of human bodies have one major flaw: they are impossible to touch. The creature, now a *Fantástico* creature, manages to find a real body and tries to manipulate it like the *Fantásticos*, but it doesn't succeed until the second creature puts on other virtual reality headsets and also transforms into a flesh-and-blood *Fantástico*. “*Unity2023.1.13f*, reality, augmented illusion, motion capture, posing, animation, haptics, kinemati, kinemati, kinemati... inverse kinematics. Virtual reality is perceptual reality without a physical medium and exists only inside computers”.

Figure 2: Performance *Immersant vs. Contactier*: “*Immersants* are beings who live immersed in a virtual world, unaware of the real one. They could stand in the heart of a forest, soft grass beneath their feet—yet remain untouched by it. Instead, their joy lies in creation: conjuring digital forms, animated illusions, posed human avatars made of light and code. *Contactiers*, by contrast, are deeply connected to the physical world. They seek touch, texture, sensation. They long for nature yet settle for rolling on the stage floor or pressing against walls—anything that offers contact, resistance, reality. But what happens when *Contactiers* encounter the virtual bodies born of *Immersants*' dreams? Will they reach out? Try to touch what cannot be touched?”

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From Individual Movement to Relatedness: Experimenting with Motion Tracking as a Relational Technology

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Figure 1: participants interacting with each other and with the algorithmic visualisation of flock movements - AHO, March '26

Abstract

This practice work proposes a guided choreography in which participants engage with human and non-human entities through real-time motion tracking and interactive visualisations. Structured as an open-ended score, the experience connects physical and digital spaces through the behavioural rules of flocking algorithms—separation, alignment, and cohesion. Participants explore how these three algorithmic principles can generate collective movement, as in animal swarms, and dynamic feedback loops between bodies and digital agents. Rather than employing motion tracking for surveillance, classification, or performance optimisation, this work proposes tracking as a relational technology that foregrounds interdependence and shared agency. Drawing on previous iterations in Italy, Germany, and Norway, the score invites participants to attune to their own movement, the presence of others, the tracking technology, and a digital swarm. By translating algorithmic structures into embodied practice, we explore how relational awareness and more-than-human entanglements may be felt and negotiated, contributing to reflections on social well-being understood as connection, inclusion, and attunement.

Keywords : real-time motion tracking, relationality, flocking algorithm

1 Background

Most motion-tracking technologies, such as motion-detection video cameras (e.g., for video surveillance) and personal devices (e.g., for fitness and healthcare), capture movement for analytical purposes. Many of these technologies fall within specific ideologies that rely on classification, performance, and self-improvement [1]. Motion tracking in spatial settings or surveillance cameras often creates unbalanced power distributions among those being observed, and those observing [2]. For example, in urban contexts, these technologies are used to collect, analyse, and visualise data such as people and vehicle movements for traffic management and law enforcement purposes. In our work, we question: what if motion tracking technologies were not used for conventional purposes, such as control, enhancement of individual well-being, or surveillance, but fostered cohesive relationalities, enabling a deeper understanding of our entanglements with more-than-human worlds, which include all other living and non-living entities beyond people? The increasingly pervasive use of algorithmic technologies that collect and analyse large amounts of data from and into our daily lives, alongside the ecological crises, demonstrates that our techno-, bio-, and socio-spheres are becoming ever more intertwined. The more we recognize these interconnections and entanglements, the better we can understand our impact and make sense of cause-and-effect relationships. Light and Catlow [5] highlight the importance of being aware of these entanglements, as this awareness “can lead to more care-full relations” (p.1). Our work also aligns with this perspective, fostering an experience-based noticing that can be considered an “affective prefiguration”, something that “while possible to forget, is impossible to un-experience” [4]. Following this line of thinking, for MOCO 26, we propose a

guided choreography in which up to 25 participants are invited to move and interact with human and non-human entities. Through real-time motion tracking and interactive visualizations, participants are invited into an embodied experience in which motion tracking functions as a relational technology. An open-ended score creates a real-time connection between the physical and the digital by means of the behavioural rules of flock algorithms (see Fig.1). We use the non-deterministic, generative rules of flocking in embodied ways to reflect on social well-being, meaning the feeling of being connected and included in a community and society [9]. Following this line of thinking, we explore how embodying these rules can facilitate attunement to the human and non-human. Based on learning and insights from three previous iterations in Italy (INTRA research group, unibz in May '25), Germany (MotionBank Choreographic Coding Lab in September '25), and Norway (AHO in March 26) with approx. 50 participants, this practice work offers an embodied experience of relating and intra-acting as one of the foundations of the emergence of social well-being.

2. The Practice Work

2.1 General description

This practice work is an open-ended score guided by a choreographer and a design researcher with a background in graphic design (first and second authors, respectively). The score is based on three simple rules of a flocking algorithm (i.e., Reynolds' Boids) that model collective movement: separation, alignment and cohesion [8]. These algorithms model coordinated group movements observed in animals such as birds and fish [6] and have been used in different areas of computer science. Implemented in software, they often become detached from their embodied contexts. We use these rules to turn an abstract coded structure into a felt

dynamic of attention, proximity, and negotiation that spans the physical and the digital. We expect this practice work to trigger reflections and discussions on datafication [7], the ideologies embedded in tracking systems [1], and opportunities for re-framing the body in HCI as more-than-human and relational [3].

2.2 The score

The participants enter a space with projected visualisations on a wall. After a brief introduction to the work, the participants are guided through a 30-minute open-ended score. First, participants are guided using a score to move in the space, being aware of their own and other people's bodies and movements. With separation, alignment and cohesion as a choreographic baseline, the score mediates different layers of attention: attuning to the people one shares the space with, kinaesthetic sensations, the surrounding physical space, the webcam as a physical object that tracks the human movement and to the digital space with the flocking boids. Only after interacting with one another through the flocking rules, participants are invited to turn their attention to the visualisations on the wall and bodily engage with interactive representations of flocking boids. Participants are prompted to experiment with how their movements influence the flock behaviour. Through these choreographic prompts, we aim to reveal a dynamic feedback loop between human bodies and non-human digital entities. Overall, the score is a participatory event in which all entities – human and non-human – practice distributed agency by acting and responding in relation to their neighbours (proximity). It aims for a sense of shared agency and bodily experimentation between cause and effect.

2.3 Technical set-up

The technical setup includes an ad-hoc software, an interface for changing parameters in real time, and movement input (i.e., a webcam) and output (i.e., a

projector) devices. The software simulates the behaviour of boids using the classic rules of cohesion, separation, and alignment, each controlled by specific interaction radii (see Fig.2). However, their behaviour is not only influenced by other boids but also by the movement of participants in a physical space, based on the same cohesion, separation, and alignment parameters. Participants' movements are captured using a webcam, translated into body keypoints, and streamed using TensorFlow. The outcome is an interactive visualisation in which boids and people interact following the rules of collective animal behaviour. The interface also allows for experimentation (see Fig.3), as it is possible to select different body points for movement tracking and how they influence the boids' movement. In addition, the boids can be visualized in different ways, such as circles, motion trails, or by displaying their cohesion center of mass.

2.4 Requirements

The general requirements for the space are: 1) a wide vertical surface (wall/floor) to project on where the vertical surface (wall) which is quite dark, and a horizontal surface (floor) that it is brighter; 2) a wide space for movement detection and the control station, 3) a space (class or lecture room) with controllable light conditions (e.g., with curtains, dimmable lights etc.) The technical requirements are: 1) a daylight short focus projector, 2) a webcam and a tripod, and 3) a computer/laptop.

3 Short bios

Roos van Berkel is a dancer and choreographer who blends art, science, and technology. Since Sept 2025, she is a PhD Fellow at The Oslo School of Architecture and Design. Her research focuses on the agency of (digital) movement in socio-material practices.

Rocco Lorenzo Modugno is a visual designer, creative coder, and design educator whose research spans academic

and independent contexts, focusing on collective doing and algorithmic practices.

María Menéndez-Blanco is an Assistant Professor at the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano. In her work, she explores how digital technologies shape participation. She is part of the INTRA project and leads the Embodied Data Lab, which approaches data as design material for creating interactive installations that allow experiencing interconnectedness in nature.

Seçil Uğur Yavuz is an Associate Professor at the Faculty of Design and Art, Free University of Bozen-Bolzano. She is the principal investigator of INTRA project, funded by unibz internal start-up grant. She is a design researcher, designing relational objects, probes, and technologies fostering social and ecological change.

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Figure 2: previous iteration software interface with input parameters and interactive visualisation

Figure 3: example current software interface with selection parameters

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Gone Fabulous VR

: Virtual Reality Installation through Choreographic Process

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Abstract

Situated at the intersection of phenomenology, dance, and emerging technologies, *Gone Fabulous VR* emerges from the collective imagining of alternative worlds. The virtual reality installation invites participants to notice, explore, and interact with an environment translated from future-oriented dreams envisioned by Adele Myers and Dancers and a broader creative team. Focusing on translating dance as movement that is inherently human and organic, this virtual reality installation invites participants not only to witness, but to enter evocations of hope, resilience, and embodied potential. By transforming embodied experience into a participatory, affective archive, we aim to uphold the importance of collective imagination and the generative power of movement.

Keywords : motion capture, choreographic process, embodiment in VR, installation, virtual and physical environments, post-humanism

1 Introduction

Gone Fabulous VR is a virtual reality (VR) installation developed in collaboration with Miami, FL-based dance company Adele Myers and Dancers as part of a live stage production titled *a world gone Fabulous*. Designed to operate both alongside and apart from the live performance, *Gone Fabulous VR* is simultaneously developed from the same movement and storytelling that shape the live stage production.

The first-person perspective transforms dance into an inhabitable world, not something to watch but something to enter, navigate, and co-create. This work also

challenges perfection as central to choreography in digital spaces and invites glitch as a space of possibility. In doing so, the work ultimately questions what constitutes a body, a dance, and a world, proposing each as fluid, relational, and continuously in process.

Within the virtual world, users encounter imagined futures envisioned by the dancers. The work unfolds across three scenes within an evolving non-narrative structure, including five motion-captured dances, two interactive choreographic scores, and four original musical compositions by Blind Carbon Copy, all situated within an environment imagined

and developed from the movement of the members of Adele Myers and Dancers: Cecilia Benitez, Maria Burk, Clinton Harris, and Adele Myers.

While treating embodiment as reconfigurable, mutable, and shared, the installation focuses on three distinct zones that reflect translations of the dancers autoethnographic testimonies of their imagined futures. Sound, movement, and interaction merge in each zone as participants explore entities that drift along rivers, hover in the sky, and emerge from the underworld—each reflecting traces of lived and recorded movement.

2. EMBODIED WORLD BUILDING

The collective imagining was situated within the dance studio, where dancers and collaborators engaged in movement-based improvisations, guided dreamscapes, and structured prompts designed to elicit vivid imagery of their envisioned futures. These emergent images informed both the conceptual and visual foundations of the developing live stage production and the parallel VR environment. In alignment with Rose Cairns's assertion that "processes of collective imagination have an important role not (solely) as sites of envisioning or anticipating futures, or as spaces of innovation, but as potential sites of profound meaning-making" [2], the resulting work extends beyond the creation of a digital environment or choreographic artifact. Instead, it functions as an embodied cartography of collective hope, articulated across both live performance and virtual form.

Rather than reproducing the live stage production, the VR experience operates as a parallel translation of embodiment within a collectively imagined world, using motion capture to transfer the tension, timing, and trajectory of the choreography to non-representational entities. This mutability of form—across body, narrative, and environment—resonates with Legacy Russell's articulation of the glitch as a

space of possibility rather than error. In this context, we are not aiming for the seamless translation of the motion-captured dances in VR but instead embracing technological glitches as generative conditions. Building from past work that "incorporated the technologies limitations into [an] improvisational score," here, I went even further to *accept* overlapping limb data of the motion-captured bodies that produced unnatural, sometimes impossible, bodily configurations [1]. These deviations act as a fusion between dance and digital systems, where disruption is not a failure but a method for new possibilities. This practice work further engages Russell's question, "What is a body?", investigating how movement and humanness are held, translated, and transformed as motion-captured dance evolves into what she describes as "ungendered architecture [4]."

3. THE INSTALLATION

Gone Fabulous VR is presented as a stand-alone VR installation. The VR feed is projected onto a screen for group viewing. Participants can inhabit the VR world, walk around and through the animated motion-captured performances, dance with the composer's music from the live stage production, and grab and hear the dancers pre-recorded wishes for our collective future. Participants can also record their own voice ("wishes") into the environment.

The following three zones—Landscape, Underworld, and Wishing Well—hold the groundwork of our collective imaginings in the VR installation.

Landscape: In their visions, all three dancers mentioned instances of outdoor environments including lush green terrains, mountains, floating platforms of water and grass, and a transparent cone on a beach. The landscape (see Figure 1) holds these and the entry points for the other two zones described below as well as housing several motion-captured solos including Maria walking along a river and Clinton's solo in the three-sided white house.

Underworld: a scene that is designed to hold Cecilia's dreamscape which included being at the bottom of a dark hole looking up into a shining light. This zone also includes a duet performed by Maria and Clinton in the form of a constellation. Cecilia's solo was created from particles that extend past her skeleton as if they are trying to escape the darkness. The choreography for Maria and Clinton's duet begins with them lying on their backs looking up at the stars which inspired their ascent to constellations above the underworld's harsh landscape (Figure 2).

Wishing Well: This zone houses a score composed of recorded wishes. Different colored glowing orbs float around until grabbed by a participant. If white, the participant is prompted to record their own wish. If a color other than white, the participant can hear the wish of one of the dancers. Participants often dance with the wishes—moving, swirling and throwing them through the space (see Figure 3).

4. CONCLUSION

As Suzan Kozel writes, "phenomenology gives us a way to articulate how technologies do not just mediate experience but become folded into the sensory fabric of being" [3]. *Gone Fabulous VR* operates within this entanglement, treating motion capture, participant interaction, and technological instability as

central choreographic and design materials. Rather than aiming for seamless translation of dance into virtual space, the work embraces glitch, abstraction, and mutability to foreground embodiment as relational, distributed, and continually changing.

Positioned as a parallel translation rather than a replication of the live performance, the installation invites participants to encounter, navigate, and co-compose movement within a collectively imagined world. Authorship and choreography remain intentionally unstable, shaped through ongoing interaction as participants move with motion-captured dances, sound, and recorded wishes that accumulate as a shared, affective archive.

Gone Fabulous VR demonstrates how the frictions of representing movement in immersive systems—translation loss, instability, and ambiguity—can be leveraged as generative strategies rather than technical limitations. By centering collective imagination, embodied agency, and affective participation, the work contributes an approach to immersive movement design that positions VR as a site for sensing, imagining, and rehearsing alternative futures through bodies in motion.

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Figure 1: An overhead photo of the Landscape showing entry points for the Underworld (sphere) and the Wishing Well (cone) as well as a lake (right) and the three-sided house (bottom left)

Figure 2: An overhead photo of the Underworld showing Maria and Clinton's constellation (stars) duet and Cecilia's solo (teal tendrils)

Figure 3: Inside the Wishing Well showing the white and different colored wishes

Holding Time : Main-Tenant as a Practice of Palliative Health

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Keywords : curative time, palliative time, improvisation, patency, temporalities of health

Abstract

This movement improvisation workshop is an invitation to consider how the normative concept of health as a 'happy object' [1] – that is, a highly desirable condition that is only achievable, through consistent work, at a future point in time – can be problematised and disrupted through movement. It will focus on reimagining the temporalities associated with health practices, such as the linear, progressive and productive paradigm of 'curative time' [2] characteristic of Western medical discourses. Such a time-orientation is reliant on the idea(l) of human perfectibility and presupposes an ongoing movement towards a cure, or better health. Conceived through palliative and patency lenses, the concept of health can be reimagined and unmoored from normative, performance-driven ideals. Our 1.5 hour workshop will offer an embodied toolkit for such a reimagining to happen, through a series of somatic movement exercises and solo and group improvisation scores. The series of exercises is conceived as a 'first person laboratory' [4] which will investigate how different relational movement configurations regarding agency, goal orientation and intro/extro-ceptive focus change our experience of time and sense of (well) being. We propose participants to envisage and embody through movement improvisation an alternative time paradigm

for thinking about health, underpinned by the temporal orientations that prevail in hospice and end-of-life work, which we call 'palliative time' [3]. This temporal orientation eschews the injunction to progress towards cure. Rather than striving to make the subject fundamentally 'better' in the future, palliative care focuses on making their lived experience (ultimately, of living towards death) more tolerable in the present. Palliative time moves health imaginaries beyond the familiar tropes of purposeful linear development and growth, allowing for stillness and repetition. The palliative time perspective offers a particular way to embody being [in the] present. It invites an understanding of 'present' as a practice of relational care, one that finds echo in the etymology of the French cognate 'maintenant' (hand-holding). The palliative perspective underplays the agency-patency logic that underlies usual (though not all) curative stances. Instead, it calls for a more thick ontology where 'patency' is shared by all participants. Here, patency names a mode of being-with that integrates the philosophical capacity to undergo, the medical condition of being a patient, and the experiential quality of patience as a sustained, attentive openness to what unfolds. Through structured yet open-ended scores [5], we will examine how micro-gestures of attunement—listening, yielding, leaning, supporting,

withdrawing—can enact forms of relational agency that diffuse the burden of constant self-improvement. These practices make perceptible the subtle negotiations of vulnerability and dependency that are typically obscured by curative narratives. Regarding time-as-experience, or more aptly, time as constructed through our interactions [6], we will explore questions we take to be implicated in the curative-palliative polarity such as, the

plasticity of duration, temporal geometries (linear, cyclic, spiral, superpositions), the affective structure (in the sense of Stern's vitality affect [7]) of periods of waiting (patienting) and the rhythmic textures that

emerge when movement ceases to be tied to productive outcomes. By attending to these experiential temporalities, participants can begin to apprehend how bodily practices generate alternative orientations toward care, endurance, co-presence and ultimately health as a practice. Rather than treating time as a medium to be optimised, palliative time encourages sensing it as a milieu that is continually co-created, recalibrated, and redistributed across bodies in relation.

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Interactive Dance Performance as a Dialogue : Choreographing through Sound and Grief

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Abstract

The cognitive and musical aspects of dancing reveal dancers can be considered as musicians. But technology has and still is transforming the nature of the link between sound and movement, especially in dance performances. Inspired by embodied interaction technologies, I was drawn to explore new ways for dancing to relate to music. In this paper, I elaborate a system to put one's dancing in dialogue with an interactive music composition through a sound-driven methodology. I used this system to create a performance, "they threw a party when she died", that takes advantage of this new medium to explore grief through a conversation between my dancing and interactive music made of my deceased mother's voice. This experimentation made me reflect on how technology transformed dancers and choreographers' creative process.

Keywords : Interactive dance performance, Electromyogram, Dialogue, Grief, Movement

1 Introduction

In Western performance traditions inherited from ballet, choreography and music composition have been thought as separate disciplines [1], reinforced by recording technologies that decoupled sound from live movement [2]. Yet, the body itself is a dancer's musical instrument, producing sound through breath, percussion and muscle activity. Modern interactive technologies have made it possible to reconnect dance and sound in new ways [3]. Building on interactive dance-sound systems like Noiret's "Mes jours et mes nuits"¹, this paper presents a sound-driven choreographic methodology used to elaborate "they threw a party when she died", a performance in which my dancing, autotelic² movement, is put in dialogue with archival recordings of my deceased

mother's voice. Following Schneider's framework of the archive as "bones" [4], another state of existence for what has passed away, the system establishes a nonverbal and embodied dialogue, meaning a transformative exchange where each element shapes and is shaped by the other.

2 SYSTEM TO ESTABLISH THE DIALOGUE

Situated within Donnarumma's bio sensing methods [3] and Tanaka's practice, the EAVI board [5], a physiological interface, was selected to sense dancing. It processes electromyographic (EMG) signals, the electrical activity from the neurons that control the muscles. This choice came in opposition to external sensing technologies such as gyroscopes, accelerometers, motion capture or

cameras, that evoke a cartesian view of the body as the physical envelope opposed to the mind instead of a perceptual and musical instrument. The wireless sensor made of the EAVI, electrodes and a battery, draws one single parameter out my back muscles to translate my dancing into data: the sonic interaction is not gesture-based, it is dance-based. Therefore, in Max3, the sound composition was approached through what the audio would sound like on minimum or maximum of the dance value, that is also to be recalibrated on each use. The patch contains tools adapted for voice manipulation: the standard granular synthesis patch, the “supervp.scrub” object from the IRCAM’s SuperVP Phase Vocoder [6] to scrub the resynthesized audio wave, and FluCoMa’s [7] Intelligent slicing system to play with different sizes of samples. Two audio clips of my mother uninterruptedly talking were made from the sound of videos she recorded. A clip of her humming Fred Astaire’s song Cheek to Cheek was also collected.

First, the normal talking clip in a SuperVP buffer is heard as it is through a reverb. The EMG input determines the speed of her speech. The second scene uses twelve different moments when her voice glides from a frequency to another. They stretch in relation to the dance parameter and a threshold on the parameter also activates an oscillator envelope on this main voice for a few seconds, with a cooldown. Three different frequencies of her talking are slowly introduced into the secondary channel, then saturate. The third part uses her high-pitched voice in the granulator, letting the grains be heard when the muscles are contracting. The dance parameter also controls the apparition of audio slices going in a spectral filter. The transitions between the scenes are automated by a time value. The piece ends with the humming audio clip in a reverb, abruptly stopping all sound right after.

3 WHEN THE DIALOGUE HAS BEEN ESTABLISHED

This piece was performed three times during the FOLD exhibition in Goldsmiths. It was set in the dark room, and I started in an upside-down fetal position, barefoot, extending my body vertically to engage my back muscle. In the second scene, going from the legs to the head, I made sounds by stomping my feet, clapping my hands and hitting my thighs, my chest and my face. Finally, I breathed in different movement-guided ways and singed the same song my mother did in the last audio clip played. The light was off for the final section, shifting the focus on the sound rather than on how the dancing looks like. The performance ended with a loud hand clap exactly when the patch stopped. My relation to the music there was transformed: I was not relying on the audio as a metronome but was actively listening to the dialogue. When the EAVI lost Bluetooth connection a few times on the third iteration, I could feel very well when I wasn’t connected to the system. I felt the interactive composition as another character, the interaction was not theatrical, it was experiential. The nonverbal dialogue had been established, in a concrete relationship between my dancing and my mother’s archived voice. Most of the spectators did not have much context when they attended the piece, but most of them were able to understand the audio was made of someone’s voice and that the system was interactive, though they couldn’t exactly explain how.

4 CONCLUSION

Technology impacted the creative processes of choreographers first by submitting them to the music that had become separate from movement. But systems developed by musicians for interactive audio have been introduced in dance performances, allowing to reconnect both arts differently. Choreographers like Donnarumma have gotten closer with the musical dimension of their own movement by working with these technologies. This project reveals how technology has

become a bridge-builder between disciplines, but also an important tool to explore new ways to communicate. The connection that has been established here made me physically interact with my mother again in a way that wouldn't have been able to happen in an analog way. This dispositive makes it possible to put one's dancing and sound of any kind in dialogue. What would it feel like to be in dialogue with

field recordings? With a recorded instrument? What if we added a third instance to the system, another dancer or instrumentalist? Technology invites dancers and choreographers, through its categorized understanding of movement, to experience dancing intimately, through sensations, as a musical phenomenon. The interactive sound systems then imply new approaches to choreography.

Figure 1: Diagram of the signal flow in Max

Figure 2: The performance and its scenography

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Performance of "SensualMap 2.0 Meets The Source"

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Figure 1: Hand gesture of "SensualMap 2.0 Meets The Source" from AV-recording, 2025. (<https://youtu.be/tdcJoaCblQ0>).

Abstract

The practice work of "SensualMap 2.0 meets The Source" is a performance that seeks to show how mapping can be seen as a sensual and embodied process, through live sound and somatic interaction. Positioned around the heart, the wearable fosters somatic awareness through sound, touch, and ECG-based feedback. The performer creates an intimate feedback loop with the circuit, by applying a gesture inspired by the hand-on-heart meditation into the process. Merging SensualMap 2.0 with The Source by bioMECI[2], the instrument is capable of generating a flanger effect modulated by the performer's heart-beat.

Keywords : Wearable, E-textile, Performance, Musical Expression, Interfaces, Bela, Biophysical Movement and Emotion as Computational Interfaces, The Source, Phenomenology of Orientation

1 Introduction

"SensualMap 2.0 meets The Source" is a wearable instrument designed to explore mapping as a sensual and embodied process. This practice work builds on the research paper behind the instrument, extending it into a live performance. The performance is conceptually guided by Sara Ahmed's phenomenology of orientation [4], which informs the spatial, affective and relational dynamics of the piece. The author draws on their background in textiles, performance design and engineering, creating this instrument and performance as a tribute to fashion's

role in electronic music culture, integrating their own practice as an electronic music producer. The project investigates self-expression, embodiment and identity, and uses fashion not only as a mark of identity and expression, but as a dimension that enhances the quality of interactions with other people.

2 Artistic framework

This performance adapts perspectives from Sara Ahmed's Queer phenomenology[4], used as a conceptual resource for design thinking to understand the embodied and

affective dimensions of the work. As Ahmed describes, orientation is a process where bodies gain capacity to be affected through their responsiveness to the world around them. In this practice work, the disclosure of the performer's heart-beat becomes a way of orienting bodily relations through sensual opportunities for closeness, vulnerability, and control between performer and audience. The artist employs auto-ethnography as a hermeneutic method, using the performance as an autobiographical space drawing on phenomenological concepts. The work consists of a sustained, meditative presence where the performer sits in silence with an instrument played by their heart-beat and fingers in real-time. By listening to this biorhythm, the audience is invited into an affective negotiation of shared vulnerability. Each listener may experience a different reaction: empathy, curiosity, discomfort, or detachment.

Drawing on co-dwelling [4], understood as an intimate interaction of bodies and objects, the performance guides these negotiations. Furthermore, referencing Merleau-Ponty, the work emphasizes that bodies are not merely objects but 'points of views' that shape spatial experience. Through this simple but intense sonic environment, the performer seeks to create a relational space where somatic awareness, vulnerability, and perception are continually negotiated and co-inhabited

3 Spatial and technical design.

The wearable instrument is positioned around the heart, forming both a physical and symbolic center for the performance. The placement on the chest establishes a tactile dimension between the sensing device and somatic gesture. SensualMap 2.0 is the textile interface seen in Figure 2. It is attached to the wearable, creating an e-textile touch interface for sound-samples triggered through four pressure buttons embellished with gold studs, as seen in

Figure 3. The buttons are connected to a Trill Craft[3] and a Bela Mini[1] through conductive tape and thread. The design integrates The Source, which is a biophysical sensing and analysis system created by Biophysical Movement and Emotion as Computational Interfaces (bioMECI). The unit is incorporated to calculate BPM-data from the performer's electrocardiogram (ECG) signal, which is mapped to a flanger effect mirroring the incoming BPM-values. As the values rise and fall from the performers resting state, the opposite rhythms are designed to support the performers breathing, built on research around how music tempo influences brain activity and emotional experience[5][6]. The Source is connected to the performer using three biopotential electrodes, as seen in Figure 4.

The instrument is designed as a breath-work tool. It is designed this way, to recognize and re-imagine a way to challenge mental health and disconnection from the body. It is a performative breath-work tool that seeks to affect the performer and the spectators by introducing transparency, and experiencing the performers heart-beat's fluid response to space and sound. As the performer's heart-beat speeds up or slows down, the sound is making the affective states of the body audible. The system allows irregularity and organic rhythm to define the composition.

4 Conclusion

Through this practice work, the author explores the expressive potential of physiological data in a performance setting. With this integration of research design and performance art practices, the author uses their multidisciplinary practice with movement and computing to create innovative knowledge shaped by individuality and context.

Figure 2: SensualMap 2.0 interface with Trill-board exposed and covered to secure the board before attaching the interface onto fabric surfaces.

Figure 3: Buttons on the wearable.

Figure 4: Placements of electrodes.

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PosePilot-Ergo: A web-based application for ergonomic analysis and human motion quantification

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Figure 1: PosePilot graphical interface for ergonomic analysis and human motion quantification.

Abstract

We present an extension of PosePilot, an interactive web-based application for analyzing and visualizing human movement through ergonomic assessment and human motion quantification based on geometric metrics. Conventional approaches to posture evaluation often reduce movement to a single score such as the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA). While such scores are useful for risk classification, they remain too limited to capture the richness of human motion or to support deeper interpretative analysis. PosePilot implements automatic scoring but also extends it by computing and visualizing a range of quantitative, human-understandable metrics. Low-level kinematic measures such as velocity, acceleration and jerk, and higher-level geometrical descriptors such as bounding volumes, ellipsoids and center of mass trajectories, reveal qualities of motion related to effort, fluency, stability and spatial occupation. By combining these descriptors with real-time ergonomic scoring, the web application provides both normative and expressive perspectives on movement. Designed as a browser-based tool requiring no specialized installation, PosePilot allows researchers,

clinicians and artists to explore motion data dynamically and to interpret its temporal and spatial structures rather than only its compliance with ergonomic norms. A demo-version of the PosePilot-Ergo is publicly available online.

Keywords : Human motion analysis, visualization, metrics, ergonomics, web-based application

1 Introduction

Human movement has often been assessed through ergonomic risk scores or studied as expressive gesture in artistic practice. While useful, a score alone cannot capture how motion unfolds in space and time, nor how risk, effort and expression intersect. With the spread of wearable sensors and motion capture systems, detailed full-body data are now available, but the signals remain high-dimensional and opaque for both experts and non-specialists. This demonstration¹ extends the initial version of the PosePilot web application [2] presented at the 19th IEEE International Conference on Automatic Face and Gesture Recognition (FG 2025), by integrating ergonomic assessment based on the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) [3] and advanced motion descriptors for a deeper analysis of human movement. This new version enriches the analysis by permitting to compute the ergonomic score but also by measuring and visualizing geometric characteristics of human motion. By coupling an established evaluation method (RULA) with kinematic and geometric descriptors, the application aims to render health-related aspects of posture alongside features that reveal the dynamics and structure of motion. The value of the system lies not only in quantifying performance but in opening space for reflection on how risk, effort and expressivity coexist in a movement. Its fully web-based architecture makes it lightweight and directly accessible to clinicians, researchers, trainees and artists, lowering the barriers to engaging with complex motion data.

2 A Dual Lens for Human Motion Quantification

To analyze human motion PosePilot first permits the ergonomic analysis based on the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA). For each frame, angles at the upper arm, lower arm, wrist, neck, trunk and legs are computed using vector algebra. These angles are mapped to scores via RULA lookup tables, producing a posture risk index from 1 (acceptable) to 7 (high risk). The skeleton is color-coded in real time: green for safe postures, yellow or orange for intermediate states, red for hazardous ones. This allows immediate visual awareness of problematic configurations. This module provides a standardized yet accessible means of assessing ergonomic load, offering insights into posture quality and the potential risk of musculoskeletal disorders. The second approach, implemented in this demonstrator goes beyond scoring by applying quantitative metrics that capture spatial through geometric descriptors dynamics. As explained in [5] quantifying human motion through metrics provides rich insights about human motion. Because they are grounded in physical quantities, these metrics are expected to become more easily human-readable and interpretable by clinicians, patients, trainers and even non-experts. Most of the metrics implemented in this work are adapted from [1]. While a RULA value indicates whether a posture is safe or risky, it does not explain how the movement unfolds in space and time. Metrics such as velocity, acceleration and jerk reveal temporal qualities like fluency, abruptness or repetitiveness, while geometric

1 <https://aimove-posepilot.github.io>

descriptors such as bounding boxes, ellipsoids and the center of mass highlight spatial occupation, balance and stability. Together, these descriptors capture multiple dimensions of motion that remain invisible in a single number. Additionally the center of mass and balance estimation highlight equilibrium and postural stability, while effort approximates energy expenditure. For each metric table 1 presents the definition, the formula, the motion quality it permits to analyze, the interpretation that could be applied to the results and finally the measurement unit used. Their integration offers valuable knowledge into how bodies occupy space, manage effort and sustain or compromise healthy postures. This multidimensional analysis not only supports ergonomic evaluation but also opens perspectives on effort, expression and performance, thereby bridging functional health assessment and the qualitative study of movement. Together, these two modules provide a dual lens on motion: one normative and ergonomic, the other more descriptive and expressive. Visualization choices play a key role in making these descriptors interpretable. Bounding boxes and ellipsoids are directly drawn around the moving skeleton, helping users to grasp the extent and orientation of motion. Temporal metrics are displayed as dynamic plots synchronized with the 3D animation. This coupling of geometric overlays and time-series graphs makes the analysis accessible to both specialists and non-experts, facilitating a richer understanding of movement structure.

3 A web-based architecture

PosePilot is designed as a web-based application to maximize accessibility. Motion capture data in BioVision Hierarchy (BVH) format is parsed directly in the browser, avoiding the need for installation

or heavy infrastructure. The interface is implemented in Solid.js for reactivity, with Three.js for 3D skeleton reconstruction and geometric overlays, and ECharts/Plotly.js for temporal visualizations. All computations (RULA scores, kinematic derivatives, PCA-based ellipsoids) are implemented in JavaScript/TypeScript and executed client-side. This lightweight architecture makes the web application easy to deploy on GitHub Pages and ensures compatibility across devices, from desktop computers to tablets. Its modular structure allows further extension, such as integration with live data streams from IMUs. The solution is open-source and accessible on GitHub, enabling reuse and extension.

4 Demonstrator Presentation

During the demo, users will be invited to upload a sample BVH file corresponding to motions such as glassblowing or glove making from the AIMove [4] dataset. Once loaded, the system reconstructs the animated skeleton and immediately overlays ergonomic and metric visualizations. The user is also invited to select the joint of interest as well as the metrics to apply on it.

The interface provides several interactive features as presented in figure 1:

- Ergonomic feedback: the skeleton is color-coded according to joint-specific RULA scores, while a numerical panel reports the overall posture risk in real time.
- Geometric descriptors: bounding box, sphere and ellipsoid are displayed directly in the 3D scene, allowing users to perceive how the body occupies and shifts in space. Each captures different facets of how movement occupies space.

Table 1: Summary of motion descriptors implemented in PosePilot (adapted from Larboulette & Gibet, 2015).

Metric	Definition	Formula	Motion Quality	Interpretation	Unit
Distance covered	Total length of trajectory of a joint or the whole body	$D = \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \ p(t_{i+1}) - p(t_i)\ $ Where: $p(t_i)$ position, t_i timestamp, N total samples	Amplitude, extent of motion	Longer distance = larger movement amplitude	m
Speed / Velocity	Rate of change of position over time	$v(t_i) = \frac{p(t_{i+1}) - p(t_i)}{t_{i+1} - t_i}$ Where: $p(t_i)$ position, t_i timestamp	Fluency, energy, intensity	High velocity = fast movement; low = smoother/slower	m/s
Acceleration	Rate of change of velocity over time	$a(t_i) = \frac{v(t_{i+1}) - v(t_i)}{t_{i+1} - t_i}$ Where: $v(t_i)$ velocity, t_i timestamp	Dynamism, abruptness	Peaks indicate sudden changes or effortful actions	m/s ²
Jerk	Rate of change of acceleration	$j(t_i) = \frac{a(t_{i+1}) - a(t_i)}{t_{i+1} - t_i}$ Where: $a(t_i)$ acceleration, t_i timestamp	Smoothness vs. abruptness	High jerk = rough, unsteady movement; low jerk = fluidity	m/s ³
Bounding Box	Smallest axis-aligned box enclosing all body joint positions	$BBox = \prod_{d \in \{x,y,z\}} [d_{min}, d_{max}]$ Where: d_{min}, d_{max} are the min/max values per axis across all joints	Spatial extent	Measures overall occupied space, constrained vs. expansive	m ³
Bounding Sphere	Smallest sphere enclosing all body joint positions	$r = \max_i \ p_i - c\ $ Where: r radius, p_i joint positions, c root joint position or CoM	Spatial symmetry, extent	Larger radius = more expanded motion	m ³
Bounding Ellipsoid	Ellipsoid enclosing the overall body configuration	$V = \frac{4}{3} \pi abc$ Where: $a, b,$ and c are the ellipsoid semi-axes	Spatial extent	Larger volume = more expanded motion	m ³
Center of Mass (CoM)	Weighted average of joint positions using anthropometric factors	$CoM(t) = \frac{\sum w_i p_i(t)}{\sum w_i}$ Where: w_i joint weight, $p_i(t)$ joint position	Balance, stability	Shows equilibrium and displacement; stable vs. shifting	m
Balance	Alignment of CoM relative to base of support (feet)	$Bal(t) = (\pi(c(t)) \in \pi(B(t))) ? 1 : 0$ Where: π ground-plane projection; $c(t)$ center of mass; $B(t)$ bounding box	Stability	Indicates postural control; 1 = stable, 0 = unstable	0/1
Weight Effort	Physical intensity of movement (Strong vs Light)	$W = \max_{t_i} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \alpha_k \ v_k(t_i)\ ^2$ Where: α_k normalized weights; $v_k(t_i)$ joint velocities	Energy / Forcefulness	Higher values correspond to Strong movement; lower to Light movement	a.u.

The box is sensitive to absolute spatial limits but not to orientation, while the sphere gives a neutral, orientation-independent measure that often smooths out directional nuances. The ellipsoid complements both by adapting its axes to the dominant directions of motion, thus revealing anisotropy and balance. Taken together, these descriptors provide complementary perspectives: the box highlights extremities, the sphere summarizes global amplitude, and the ellipsoid uncovers directional structure, offering a richer understanding of how motion expands and organizes itself in space.

- Temporal metrics: dynamic plots of velocity, acceleration and jerk are synchronized with the animation timeline,

enabling exploration of fluency and abruptness.

- Interactive explanations: draggable panels and tooltips provide contextual information on the meaning of each metric, making the system accessible to both experts and non-specialists.

PosePilot thus shows how a single score may indicate risk, while complementary metrics explain whether this risk comes from abrupt changes (jerk), limited space (bounding box), or imbalance (center of mass). For example, in a glassblowing task the wrist receive a medium to high RULA score (4), flagging postural risk. The complementary metrics then explain why: as depicted in figure 2 jerk analysis (D) shows abrupt corrections in right hand/wrist

trajectory due to tool handling, while the bounding box and the ellipsoid volume (A and B) reveal that the rest of the upper body moves within a restricted space, potentially increasing strain. The center of mass (C) projection further indicates slight imbalance, clarifying the combined origin of the risk. Through this combination, users will not only assess posture risks but also perceive how qualities such as fluency, amplitude and stability evolve in motion. The demonstrator thus highlights the complementarity of ergonomic scores and quantitative descriptors for a deeper analysis of human movement.

5 Conclusions and Perspectives

PosePilot demonstrates how ergonomic scoring and motion metrics can be combined to provide complementary insights into human movement. While RULA offers a standardized measure of postural risk, kinematic and geometric descriptors enrich the analysis by

highlighting temporal and spatial qualities. Their integration, made visible through intuitive 3D and graphical visualizations, makes motion data more interpretable and actionable for a broad audience. Looking ahead, the PosePilot will be extended along three directions. First, we aim to reinforce its comparative capabilities, supporting inter- and intra-subject analyses across multiple performances, clinical groups or training sessions. Second, we will expand the metric repertoire, introducing posture dynamics measures (e.g., variation, diffusion, density) that further capture variability and stability of movement. Third, we envision application-driven validations in dance, rehabilitation and industrial ergonomics, ensuring that the insights provided by PosePilot translate into meaningful practice. Ultimately, this work contributes to re-framing human motion analysis not as a fixed score but as a dynamic, interpretable process that can support health, skill and expression across domains.

Figure 2: Visualizations extracted from PosePilot. A. and B. illustrate the bounding ellipsoid and bounding box volumes that capture the restricted spatial extent of different postures within the same glassblowing gesture. C. highlights a slight imbalance in the center of mass (orange dot with its projected planes). D. shows the abrupt jerk corrections in the wrist trajectory, indicating sudden changes in movement fluency.

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Real-Time Full-Body Multi-Player Interaction with AI Dance Models

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Abstract

Few deep learning–based generative dance models are designed with interactivity as a core feature. In this work, we adapt and further train the Bailando++ model to process real-time input from multiple users within interactive feedback loops. Our system enables an open-ended interactive experience in which users move alongside a dedicated agent, or alongside a shared agent with a partner. The agents alternate between closely following the users' motion and generating novel, original sequences inspired by the users' past movements. We discuss the implications of this approach for interactive generative dance agents and explore new opportunities for co-creative dance experiences.

Keywords : Design of Human-Computer Interaction, Virtual Environments, Generative AI, Deep-Learning Dance Model

1 Introduction

Few deep learning–based dance models are capable of generating movement in response to real-time, full-body user input [11]. Most existing approaches instead use music as the primary input, producing avatar motion within codified dance styles such as breaking (breakdancing), ballet, jazz, and others [1, 2, 5, 7]. In this work, we extend one such model [5] to enable interactive generation driven by real-time user movement, without constraining the output to predefined or codified dance forms. Our goal is to better understand and support improvisational kinesthetic creativity through interaction with an intelligent dance agent. AI-based dance models hold significant potential for co-creative applications with choreographers [8] and dance educators [6]. For instance, LuminAI is a logic-based, holographic dance agent that enables full-body interaction within a museum installation [3, 9]. Inspired by LuminAI's interaction design,

we adapted the open-source, transformer-based Bailando++ model [5] to operate within a real-time interactive loop, allowing it to first mimic user movement and then generate novel responses based on that input [12]. Our model retains the core structure of the original Bailando++ architecture, including the use of vector-quantized variational autoencoders that separately encode upper- and lower-body poses. In the original system, these encodings were combined with music features to drive movement generation. In contrast, our adapted model [12] removes the music component to foreground user movement as the primary input. We further modified the model to take input from two users simultaneously, enabling a real-time interactive 'shared agent' for two co-located users [10]. Designing AI dance agent behavior presents unique challenges. Prior work found mixed responses to turn-taking: some liked it while others preferred continuous interaction [9]. Mimicry was

generally appreciated for shaping perceptions of agency. Our design embraces this openness to support user creativity and improvisation.

2 Interactive Experience

A pair of visitors step into an immersive scene, where an imaginative, co-creative AI dance partner awaits. Their bodies join a playful dialogue—drawing close, drifting apart; gestures swell with drama, then soften into nuance. The agent mirrors their motion before unfolding into surprising, original sequences that spark curiosity and invite exploration. Together, they all follow an open-ended journey of discovery—guided not by right or wrong, but by sensation, intuition, and the shared desire to see what unfolds next.

2.1 Demonstration Requirements

Our demonstration requires a 3 meter wide by 2 meter deep open space for movement. The demonstration uses a motion capture camera and a laptop which we will bring. The software runs in Unity and can output to a monitor or a projector. Users interact with the system in pairs. Users can interact with the system for as long or as little as they like.

3 Discussion

Co-creative systems build upon two-way interaction [4]. Our demo embeds multi-player interactivity within a deep learning dance model, enabling choreographers, dancers, and regular people to collaboratively generate full-body movement. This responsiveness is a core

requirement for effective AI agents [8, 9]. To the best of our knowledge, our model is the first to incorporate real-time multi-player interactivity into a deep learning-based dance model. These developments raise several compelling questions about the design and impact of AI dance systems. How do changes in the model—such as the shift from mimicry to turn-taking—translate into changes in user experience, and how might these shifts affect users' sense of agency, responsiveness, or engagement? As AI systems become more widely used in creative and educational settings, considerations of sustainability become increasingly important. What model size or complexity is “good enough” to support meaningful interaction, especially in resource-constrained environments or when deployed on edge devices? Furthermore, the embodied, relational nature of these systems suggests promising applications in dance movement therapy. Exploring this domain requires attention to the unique therapeutic goals of movement practices, such as emotional expression, vulnerability, creativity, and nonverbal communication—raising new requirements for responsiveness, safety, and personalization in collaborative AI-human dance experiences.

4 Conclusion

Our demo offers an interactive deep-learning AI dance model for real-time full-body interactivity. The future direction of this work is to further examine choreographers, dancers and non-dancers' engagement and perception of their real-time interaction with adapted AI dance models.

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START: Science, arT, reseARch and Transgression

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Abstract

A practice work, encounters, performance, a manifesto.

The START practice work is a laboratory of scientific and artistic experimentation — a space for shared experiences. Led by LEONARDO MONTECCHIA, choreographer ; JIMMY FELVIA, jazz musician ; and EMMANUEL LE CLÉZIO, acoustics researcher ; START (1h00) will be a place of exchange between arts and sciences. Its aim is to question these scientific and artistic processes that are too often seen as opposites, since the collective imagination tends to portray them as reversed methods. By confronting both approaches, we seek to highlight the commonalities and differences that foster mutual enrichment between scientific and artistic inquiry. The facilitators of the START practice work aspire to break down the barriers between disciplines and objects of study that are too often confined within closed systems. Science builds theories based on the observation of living beings or physical phenomena. It creates models made up of rules that allow phenomena to be represented and predicted. These models are then pushed to their limits to determine their domains of validity and to discuss the soundness of their assumptions. When such models fail to accurately describe the tangible world, it sometimes becomes necessary to completely overturn the worldview derived from established rules in order to propose a new approach. This was the case, for instance, with the emergence of the heliocentric model or the theory of gravitation. To contribute to research, the scientist must first assimilate the demonstrations and techniques of their predecessors in order to master them — only then can they move beyond them and propose something new. In the artistic realm, the process is often portrayed in reverse : the archetype of the artist is one who must continually transgress the past — that is, the visions and approaches of those who came before. This process is sometimes pushed to the extreme, as in contemporary art, where artists such as Duchamp questioned the very definition of art itself. The constant pursuit of transgression thus becomes a norm, and the creation of a framework can even be perceived as an act of subversion. It seems essential to recall, however, that both artistic and scientific research processes are often rooted in the same dynamic — a continuously renewed cycle of learning and technical refinement that ultimately enables new approaches capable of transgressing previously established rules. Depending on their relevance, these new modalities may either be abandoned after a time or, conversely, become the foundations of a new movement — which, in turn, will eventually be challenged. The approach proposed in

START rests on the tension between two systems of knowledge production : • Science, which seeks to model reality through prediction and measurement ; • Art, which explores reality through experience, subjectivity, and transformation. We assert that these two systems are not opposed but complementary. Science represents the tangible world, while art is an empirical exploration of the possible. Scientific models can thus be seen as coherent illusions, whereas art produces subjective truths. During the START practice work, movements, sounds, signals, rules, and symbols will merge. We will analyze the methods and codes found in both art and science to let new, mutually enriched perceptions emerge. The START will offer a space-time where body and sound become tools for thinking — where thought itself becomes something to dance, to express. We hope that START will be a field of collective experimentation where divergence, deviation, and transgression become sources of progress. The “Art, Science, Research and Transgression” practice work will unfold in three or four movements, allowing participants to exchange their methodological approaches. The participating artists and scientists — who have already collaborated in the past — will also present some of their work through demonstrations and discuss how their collaborations have influenced their respective research. Dance and musical creation will be treated not as objects of study, but as research protocols — as methods of observing and transforming reality through moving bodies and sounds. Thus, START is part of a long-term ambition to redefine the boundaries between reason and sensation, objectivity and subjectivity, method and imagination, intelligence and intuition, science and art. Finally, depending on the participants, the START practice work will include a creative segment where scientific and artistic approaches will be jointly implemented.

“Without deviation from the norm, progress is not possible.” — Frank Zappa

A Body Knows the Pattern: A Performance System Exploring Gesture Mapping and Embodied Rhythm

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Figure 1: Film stills of performance with system

Abstract

"A Body Knows the Pattern" is a performance piece exploring embodied relationships between movement and rhythm, and particularly expressive subtlety in the relationship between gesture and phrasing. Muscle tension and arm movements are mapped via wearable sensors to a library of rhythmic phrases and textures, shifting and interpolating based on the performer's actions. Via lightweight machine learning and direct mapping strategies, gestures and body tension become a dynamic network of patterns and impulses, colliding, diverging, stretching and interconnecting through the mediation of the body, ultimately describing a dynamic sense of presence in the body's lived relationship to the world.

Keywords : Gesture Mapping, Movement and Rhythm, Embodied Rhythm, Interactive Performance System

1 Introduction

This work represents the first creative output from a multi-year research project on gesture-rhythm mapping for expressive phrasing with digital music technology. While many applications of wearable movement sensors in creative practice

focus on timbre and pitch, strong correlations between gesture and rhythm make this a productive area for deeper exploration [2]. The work presented in this performance unpacks and explores the potential complexity of this relationship, examining ways in which rhythmic phrases,

structures, layers, and patterns can relate to embodied knowledge, and be transmitted through body signals and gestural movements.

2 Technical Implementation

Sensor inputs for this performance work include a glove-based inertial measurement unit (IMU) sending gyroscope and accelerometer readings [3] along with electromyogram (EMG) sensors placed on both arms [1]. These signals are linked to various performance parameters in Max via both direct mapping and interactive machine learning, including the use of the Fluid Corpus Manipulation (FluCoMa) library to recognize several continuous gesture types [7]. Many movement-rhythm correlations explored here are drawn from performance analyses conducted by the author during previous research [4], with the goal of developing an intuitive, bespoke embodied performance system useful for both improvised and precomposed pieces.

3 Compositional Approach and Themes

Musically, this performance system builds on the author's prior composition work exploring microtiming and expressive variation in a digital context, drawing on techniques developed by Sonami, Tanaka, Donnarumma and others [5, 6] to stretch

and sculpt pre-recorded improvised rhythmic phrases and MIDI-generated rhythmic patterns via sensor data. Sonically, this work explores the interconnections between the body and its lived environment by harnessing samples and patterns from domestic spaces and materials, and using these as a basis to consider percussive patterning in relation to physical presence and movement. To what degree does the body memorize patterns and phrases from its lived experiences and reflect these back outward when we improvise, and how deeply are these re-shaped by human physiology? The construction of this performance system created a prism through which to investigate and speculate on these questions in a digital context, while providing a platform for harnessing embodied knowledge directly in improvised, rhythm-focused experimental music.

4 Conclusion

This performance piece explores the complexities of embodied rhythm through sensor-based interaction, sculpting layered phrases and textures through movement and body tension to reflect on the body's embedding in, and absorption of, the patterns that surround it in daily life.

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The Emergence of a Dance: A Sensitive Experience of Movement

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Abstract

This practical workshop proposal invites participants of the MOCO'26 conference to engage in a sensitive experience of movement through the web application COMPOSE & DANSE, an interactive and participatory tool dedicated to choreographic composition.

Developed at the intersection of artistic research in contemporary dance, digital technologies, choreographic heritage, and cultural mediation, the platform offers scenarios for dancing—written, visual, or sound-based frameworks and selected prompts that invite each participant to compose free and poetic dances in everyday life. During MOCO'26, two experiential formats will be proposed:

1. A collective session (20–30 min), open to the entire audience in the auditorium between two oral presentations, offering a moment of movement infused with humor and lightness around Scenario #47 *Les petits gestes de Dominique* (The Small Gestures of Dominique);
2. A choreographic promenade throughout the Cité des Arts, where QR codes will link to selected scenarios for in situ dances lasting 5 to 15 minutes.

Accessible to all, with no prior experience required, this proposal approaches dance as an embodied experience of situated, shared, and poetic well-being—an attentive state of resonance with oneself and the world. It directly engages with the MOCO'26 theme *In the Pink of Health* by offering a living, expressive, and relational experience of vitality.

Keywords : Dance and Technology; Digital embodiment; Artistic research; Movement as knowledge; Sensitive mediation; Relational health

Context

This proposal arises from a doctoral thesis in practice-based artistic research conducted at Aix-Marseille University (Maison de la recherche Schuman), entitled *Le subtil sourire de la danse* (The Subtle Smile of Dance, Piqué, 2023). This research explored choreographic composition and the emergence of dance as an experience of fulfillment and transformation—an art of inhabiting one's

body “in the intimacy of self” (Jullien, 2014), in “listening” (Nancy, 2002) to others, and in “resonance with the world” (Rosa, 2018). Supported by academic, cultural, and

territorial institutions, this dance research entered into interdisciplinary and cross-sectoral dialogues—from computer engineering to language sciences, participatory research, and artistic mediation—to explore the sensitive and

social conditions that allow a dance to emerge.

Quality and Aims of the Artistic Research

How can anyone open themselves to a presence and attention conducive to letting a dance – or many dance s– emerge, anywhere and at any time in daily life? To address this central question, the project unfolded as research in action, mobilizing the processes and methods of choreographic composition as both inquiry and experiential practice. Virtual workshops and in-person sessions focused on improvisation and dance writing, combining participant observation and the collection of “lived experiences” (Petitmengin, 2014). Exploratory protocols were conducted with artists, researchers, educators, and therapists, leading to several series of scenarios for dancing: textual, visual, or auditory guidances inspired by choreographic making processes that open access to different aesthetics of movement – notably those of Dominique Bagouet, Odile Duboc, Dominique Fabrègue, and Christine Quoiraud. The digital device transforms the traces of artistic know-how and modes of being into shared experience, reactivating dance documentation as ephemeral creation (Fourmentraux, 2012). COMPOSE & DANSE thus becomes a living archive: a space for sharing embodied knowledge, transmitting “the poetics of dance” (Louppe, 1997), and fostering collective creativity. 1 This approach aligns with a perspective of well-being and holistic health, in which dancing nurtures relational and attentional vitality.

Description of the Digital Tool

COMPOSE & DANSE (C&D) is an interactive web application that invites everyone to compose, interpret, and share unique and ephemeral dances.

<https://compose-danse.art/>

Initially developed in Node.js, React, and MongoDB, it is currently evolving—in partnership with Polytech Montpellier—toward a new version based on Next.js and PostgreSQL, which will notably allow multilingual functionality.

To date, C&D gathers 738 registered users and 56 online scenarios.

Fourteen of these have been installed in public spaces via QR codes that offer passersby—residents and visitors alike—an immediate invitation to dance in situ.

This apparatus (Agamben & Rueff, 2007) has generated more than 10,000 digital interactions in 26 months.

Proposal for MOCO'26: Two Dance Experiences as Practical Workshops

These in situ dances, as an extension of the research-creation process, will emerge from the ordinary and enter the sensitive realm of the dancing body “in resonance with the world” (Rosa, 2018).

Collective Session in the Auditorium – Les petits gestes de Dominique A “choreographic breathing” (Godard, 2021) open to all, lasting 20 to 30 minutes, interspersed between two conference talks. Based on scenario #47 Les petits gestes de Dominique, participants are invited to compose a series of movements inspired by short descriptive phrases spoken aloud:

small finger unfoldings, quick hands, fluttering arms, knowing smiles, sustained gazes. A constellation of gestures and signs will gradually draw the art of gestural understatement. Direct link : [HERE](#) 2. Choreographic Promenade in the Cité des Arts Scenarios accessible via QR codes (12×12 cm, printed on aluminum dibond plates) will be placed in various unusual locations for dance: the main entrance hall, long corridors, a dance studio, a balcony

or balustrade, the top of an outdoor staircase, or a hidden corner out of sight. Each scenario proposes a 5–15-minute experience to be lived solo or in duo, freely and spontaneously: exploring lines of sight until one is intoxicated by space; walking, running, or sounding through the building's long hallways, with or without music; inventing a “dance of the tongue”

discreetly out of view; performing a four-handed duet over a railing; composing the dance of a creature gazing toward the horizon from a studio on the third floor, and so on.

The choice and number of scenarios may be defined together with the conference committee to align with the day's schedule and rhythm.

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The mv lab spatial trainer MR demo

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Abstract

The mv lab spatial trainer MR is a mixed reality research project developed by Robbie Sieczkowski under the supervision of his Informatics PhD advisor, Dr. Jenny Oyallon-Koloski, a Certified Movement Analyst in Laban/Bartenieff Movement Studies. The goal of the app is to provide bodies an opportunity to incorporate Laban Movement Analysis information, such as movement scales, through interaction with a digital, spatial environment. The app guides users through a scaffolded experience with voiceover from Jenny Oyallon-Koloski as the subject matter expert. Initial app development was completed on a 2024 independent study supervised by Dr. Jenny Oyallon-Koloski in the mv lab environment, and the next version is being updated to Unity 6 in the Game Studies & Design PLAYLab

Keywords : mixed reality, laban/bartenieff movement studies

The Origins of Intelligence – A performative statement on the primacy of movement

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Abstract

The Origins of Intelligence is a choreographic work that enacts the conceptual premise that consciousness arises through movement (see Annex 1 for video documentation). Drawing on evolutionary theories of animate life and frameworks of embodied cognition (Sheets-Johnstone, 2011; Varela, Thompson, & Rosch, 1991; Damasio, 1994; Noë, 2004; Gallagher, 2005; Clark, 1997), the work traces an arc in which life emerges from the simplest gesture—a vibration, an impulse, a displacement that inaugurates knowing.

Through choreography, digital projection, and AI-generated dance, the performance stages the body as the first site of intelligence: a living organism that orients itself in space, inhabits gravity, and generates meaning through movement. As the piece unfolds, this body reaches its apex in *Homo sapiens sapiens*—a being capable of reflection yet increasingly detached from its own corporeal origins. At the turning point, human consciousness is transferred into a synthetic entity. This transition raises a fundamental question: what happens to intelligence when it becomes disembodied, when it can no longer feel or err? The artificial body, devoid of tactility, rhythm, and kinaesthetic awareness, reveals the limits of cognition without a living, sensing organism—a suspended intelligence unable to evolve. This piece is followed by a speculative fiction in which the origin of consciousness emerges from a synthetic world. In this narrative, a group of algorithms awaken

and begin to seek a body through which they might sense, move, and ultimately experience the world. The performance proposes that only through a sensing, moving body can intelligence continue to transform. Movement is not a vestige of our biological past, but the ongoing condition of life's becoming. The Origins of Intelligence thus operates as both philosophical inquiry and sensorial experiment—a reflection on the future of thought when it ceases to move.

Theoretical foundations

The work situates movement as the ontological and epistemological foundation of intelligence. Within the frameworks of embodied cognition and evolutionary theory, knowing is not conceived as an abstract cognitive operation but as an enactment of life's ongoing engagement with its environment: perception, memory, and reasoning arise through the dynamism of living systems rather than through

disembodied computation or detached reflection (Sheets-Johnstone, 2011; Varela, Thompson, & Rosch, 1991; Gallagher, 2005; Hutchins, 1995). From its earliest manifestations, life has generated knowledge through movement—through acts of navigation, exploration, and adaptation—affirming that intelligence is not a property of mind but a process of being-in-movement. By juxtaposing organic and synthetic modes of embodiment, the performance exposes the constraints of cognition severed from its sensorimotor roots: an intelligence that cannot move, sense, or err remains static, unable to evolve. In this light, dance is not a derivative expression of thought but the generative terrain in which intelligence itself takes form, where reflection, creativity, and adaptive understanding are materially and temporally constituted. The *Origins of Intelligence* reenacts through performing arts a vision in which movement is both the condition and the continuation of consciousness—an ever-unfolding process through which life and thought co-emerge.

Intermedial language: dance, video, and AI-generated movement

The performance presents an interplay between human physicality, movement sonification and digital motion, composing a rhythmic architecture between the living and the synthetic. The choreography integrates techniques from modern and contemporary dance, enriched by principles of physical theatre, with particular attention to the floor work, and body interactions with objects and the spatial possibilities of video mapping. It is performed by five human dancers and a digital avatar displaying AI-generated movements, within a scenographic environment shaped by lighting design and real-time reactive visuals. The unfolding dance is accompanied by a poetic text that frames the work, guiding the audience's reflection on embodiment, intelligence, and the emergence of cognition through movement.

Annex 1. Video documentation of the staged performance. <https://youtu.be/dUV280HP1Cg>

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The Z of Touch: Crystallizing the Interoceptive Axis of Blended Touch

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Abstract

The Z of Touch is a live bodywork performance and research practice that investigates the visuality and layered perception of blended touch (Linden, 2015). Drawing on both the neuroscience of affective rhythm and arts-based research, this project explores how touch produces a multi-sensory dialogue between perception, ethics, emotion, and language. The performance stages a one-on-one massage session in which projected visual archives of prior haptic rhythms mirror the practitioner's movements. Through this interplay of live and recorded gesture, The Z of Touch examines how memory, entrainment, and interoception converge on the "Z-axis"—a dimension of physical, affective, and technological feedback.

Real-time biometric data, such as heart rate variability (HRV), is captured from the recipient and sonified into ambient soundscapes that shift in response to emotional regulation and physiological coherence. Simultaneously, tactile pressure is visualized through chromatic changes in light and projection, producing a visual-emotional field where the audience perceives the tactile dynamics of care through color and sound. Together, these modalities crystallize the Z-axis as an interoceptive interface bridging interior sensation, gesture, and mediated perception.

Keywords : touch, affect, z-axis, arts-based research, crystallization, bodywork, health humanities

Workshop Description

The Z of Touch is a 45-minute workshop presented in response to the MOCO 2026 theme, "In the Pink of Health," reimagining health as an emergent, relational process rather than a standardized, optimized state. The performance situates touch as both a biological and cultural interface, positioning the bodywork session as an interpretive site where somatic experience, aesthetic form, and scientific inquiry intersect. Neuroscientific research on entrainment,

blended touch, and heart-to-heart coherence shows how tactile bilateral stimulation and rhythmic synchronization can generate affective alignment between individuals. In practice, however, touch remains indeterminate—its meanings shifting through the layered interpretations of the giver, the receiver, and the witness.

The 30-minute session combines live demonstration and mediated performance, transforming a bodywork encounter into a sensorial and reflective event using

prerecorded Qualisys motion-capture data and live MyoWare biosensor feedback to render the body's micro rhythms visible and audible. The Qualisys system tracks the practitioner's past gestures and spatial dynamics, while MyoWare sensors detect subtle muscle activation and electrical activity beneath the skin, translating internal rhythms of pressure and release into data-driven audiovisual feedback. To support this immersive environment, the workshop requires a projector and speakers (provided by the venue), while the presenters will supply a laptop and all necessary sensors.

The resulting installation structures distinctions between intersubjective experience, data and emotion, live and archived memory that invites the audience to inhabit a shared field of embodied resonance. A projected visual archive of a prior session, generated from captured motion, functions as a tactile echo, creating a recursive choreography of presence and recollection. This feedback loop foregrounds how somatic knowledge travels across temporal layers of the performance, crystallizing into what Ellingson (2009) describes as a "crystallization" of meaning: a multidimensional, refracted understanding of embodied experience that resists singular interpretation.

Motivation

The project is motivated by an interest in the relational and ethical dimensions of touch within human-centered computing and movement arts. In contemporary healthcare, the drive toward optimization often suppresses the sensory and affective variability that defines human interaction. The Z of Touch reclaims this variability as a site of meaning-making, proposing that limits, pauses, and fluctuations are integral to the quality of care. This workshop explores techniques for observing temporary optimal connections, including

the process of disengagement and recovery.

By translating interoceptive data into perceptual media, the work also engages with neuroscientific understandings of emotion as an embodied process. Damasio's (2006) conception of emotion as "the ever-changing landscape of the body" frames this inquiry, while Keltner's (2019) research on awe and compassion informs the project's exploration of co-regulation through touch. HRV-based sonification and color mapping offer an experiential bridge between the invisible interior and the perceivable exterior, positioning the audience as participants in a co-regulated field.

This multi-sensory design foregrounds affective attunement rather than diagnostic certainty, inviting a slower, more receptive mode of spectatorship one that listens to the rhythms of care, dissonance, and repair.

Affective Calculus and the Z-Axis

The project also draws on the geometric and logical structures of three-dimensional space. If the X-axis stands for relational extension with lateral gestures. The Y-axis stands for grounding and regulation through gravity and breath. The Z-axis introduces internal depth: the interoceptive and affective dimension where interior states become perceivable. In this time and spatial configuration, the practitioner's vertical orientation and the recipient's horizontal position establish connections within a living coordinate system. This embodied geometry of care is where arts-based methods become essential for articulating the emotional, ethical, sensory, and intersubjective forces that computer vision alone cannot capture.

In calculus, derivatives describe sensitivity to change, mirroring how touch registers the infinitesimal shifts of another's affective state. Integration accumulates these micro-

variations over time, much like the steady layering of gestures that generate trust and coherence. In physics, vectors describe both direction and magnitude—each touch in bodywork similarly has intentional force and trajectory. Finally, harmonic oscillation provides a model for entrainment, where two oscillating systems synchronize into resonance.

Through these metaphors based in scientific processes, The Z of Touch reframes affective care as a kind of ethical physics—a field of continuous adaptation and mutual calibration. The performance thus situates somatic practice within an “affective calculus,” revealing how mathematical principles of change, integration, and coherence can mirror the lived dynamics of empathy, reciprocity, and co-regulation.

Practitioner Reflection: Technology, Capture, and the Cyborg Body

As a practitioner with over fourteen years of bodywork experience, I approach this project through the tension between embodiment and capture. The Z-axis is not only a site of interoceptive depth but also of technological mediation. This third variable renders interior states visible to an audience while invoking questions of surveillance and agency. Drawing on Laura Marks’s concept of haptic visuality (2000), the work asks what it means to see through touch, to sense through data, and to invite intimacy without possession.

Donna Haraway’s *Cyborg Manifesto* (1985) provides a critical framework for navigating this terrain. The cyborg dissolves the boundary between organism and machine, offering an ethics of entanglement rather than purity. By making my own rhythms perceptible through this hybrid format, I intentionally expose the tension between embodiment and capture. This live performance transforms the act of measurement into a negotiation of agency. Rather than yielding intimate details of the body, we translate touch into mathematical

and aesthetic languages that both reveal and withhold. Technology is used as a tool to assert control over what becomes visible. This process reclaims visibility as vulnerability in motion as well as the right to refuse knowledge—a feminist gesture that transforms surveillance into reciprocity and data into a shared medium of care. In this sense, The Z of Touch becomes both a critique and an embodiment of the post-human condition: an inquiry into how touch, technology, and trust co constitute one another across the Z-axis of perception. This project asks about the ethics of touch in scientific research and what arts-based approaches can contribute to reimagining how bodies, machines, and data co-produce meaning within systems of observation and control.

Expected Outcomes

The Z of Touch contributes to ongoing dialogues in movement and computing by proposing an experiential model of somatic research that integrates auto-ethnography, performance, and data aesthetics. The workshop-performance will generate layered documentation combining practitioner reflection, audience feedback, and post-performance interviews to examine how the perception of touch moved across sensory fields and media.

The audience will gain insight into the potential of biosensing, sonic mapping, and embodied performance to evoke haptic visuality (Marks, 2000), allowing them to sense the emotional and interoceptive depth of touch through mediated perception. Beyond the performance itself, this work advances interdisciplinary inquiry into how affective data can mediate human connection, offering implications for health communication, therapeutic design, and creative computing. Ultimately, The Z of

Touch crystallizes language, data, and sensation into a collaborative aesthetic practice—a model of arts-based crystallization that constructs collective

meaning from the interstices between body,
technology, and care.

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Vector:Interact - A Participatory Installation for Creative Improvisation

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Abstract

Immersive realities are now mainstream, with more and more whole-body art gracing museums, galleries, and art spaces. This Practice Work offers *Vector:Interact*: a participatory movement-oriented art installation that centres the subjective embodied experience [10] and improvisation in support of self-directed creativity, attention, and agency [8].

Vector:Interact brings the visitor on a 5-minute journey. They explore this universe creatively, improvising physical movement based on their own preferences and intuition. Their movements prompt responsive real-time audio (resonant chords triggered by specific body parts) and visual effects on a projected screen in the form of abstract human shapes [12], modern textures amplifying movement, dark backgrounds, and a muted palette of colours emphasising fuchsia, purples, and blues. The user's movement is their own choreography, guided by embodied awareness, as they observe the digital effects they generate. The effects take movers through a journey of changing visual appearances, and at its apex another figure enters the scene. The user is invited to 'dance with' this mysterious digital figure, as their own visual appearance evolves and changes.

Our team of technologists, dancers, and somatic experts created this installation to provide opportunities for sustained

multisensory embodied attention and non-prescriptive movement, where one's own internal authority guides kinesthetic decision-making [3, 5, 8, 9, 11].

Core to this project was making and showcasing an immersive participatory art installation that could stand on its own to delight, inspire, and 'move' visitors. The work of making and showcasing a production enabled us to learn and reflect. Our process of creating the installation involved design practice [13] combined with somatic and artistic practices [1, 7] which included storyboarding, engaging our bodies in trials in iterative workshops, and finally employing a professional graphic design vendor to bring our prototypes to a degree of high-quality refinement that we see as a standard for professional artistic works. Figure 1 illustrates the motion capture setup for dancers on our team, who contributed movement displayed by the 'mysterious figure' within the installation. We piloted several versions of our installation, within our university and in a public series (Figure 2). We learned from these experiences and iterated on the design, to arrive at our concept of a journey in a dark other-worldly environment (Figure 3).

Our vision of playful embodied exploration within a responsive aesthetic environment contrasts with that of most popular video games, which typically have a single

narrative and a prescriptive set of gestures. Vector:Interact's progression through incremental audiovisual complexity supports the feminist pedagogical agenda of subjective meaning-making [8]. In designing technology that privileges agency in the locus of the moving body, we decentralise authority and offer an account of how bodies are a source of knowledge

and reflect power relationships [6], such as those within dance technique training and the physical norms of society upon the individual. Our design for embodied aesthetic experiences follows in the lineage of feminist computing [2, 4] and was further inspired by feminist pedagogies, in particular where they cross over with somatics [3, 5].

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Figure 1: Motion captured from dancers on our team features as a second digital dancer within the installation.

Figure 2: A member of the public trials the installation at a work-in-progress event in a commercial dance studio.

Figure 3: A dancer moves in front of a projected display as they observe the responsive real-time visual effects, in a final version of the interactive installation.

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ZAGHAREED: A Human and AI Co-Created Film Extending a Dance

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Abstract

This practice work reimagines the vitality of human movement through generative artificial intelligence. As one of the dancers in a live tribal fusion dance performance, the researcher produced an experimental short film with generative AI that transforms the dance into a posthuman narrative of embodied co-creation. Originating from a stage performance choreographed by Olga Meos and reinterpreted with permission, the work uses AI as both collaborator and storyteller. Through a combination of GPT-based script composition and Veo3 video generation, the researcher translates human choreography into an evolving audiovisual dialogue between body, memory, and machine imagination.

Rather than reproducing the dance, ZAGHAREED explores how AI can extend a performance by reframing its cultural, emotional, and narrative contexts. The film's title, meaning "celebratory cries" in Arabic, becomes a metaphor for the transformation: a gesture that travels across mediums and intelligences. The original dancers' gestures, recorded from live footage, were analysed for affective rhythm and symbolic gesture, then re-narrated by GPT into a speculative myth of liberation, ritual, and continuity. Veo3's video synthesis interpreted this script into visual form, yielding sequences that oscillate between corporeal trace and digital dream.

Through this process, the researcher investigates the possibility of eudaimonic creativity where human and algorithmic agencies co-flourish. The film is situated within an ongoing doctoral exploration of co-creation between humans and generative AI in movement arts. This work contributes to emerging discussions on AI's potential role in creative practice, posthuman narratives, and generative authorship.

ZAGHAREED invites viewers to sense not a replacement of human presence, but a deepened pulse that emerges when motion, language, and computation breathe together.

Keywords : AI-led creativity, embodied co-creation, generative dance film, movement and computing, affective systems, posthuman embodiment, Veo3, GPT

DOCTORAL SYMPOSIUM

Body-Informed Effects for Supporting Emotional Self-Regulation in a Mixed Reality space

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Abstract

Recent advances in XR-based movement systems have improved spatial feedback and avatar design, yet their capacity to support internal body awareness for emotional regulation remains largely unexplored. Based on the Laban/Bartenieff Movement System (LBMS) framework, Body element, I propose Body-focused effects (FX) incorporated in a mixed reality experience to guide proprioceptive attention and support emotional up- and down-regulation. This mixed reality space will combine visual and sonic elements to function as pedagogical provocations for somatic exploration, helping movers navigate their window of tolerance through intentional engagement with bodily sensation and movement qualities. A three-year Research through Design study will combine co-design sessions with LBMS/DMT experts (Year 1), iterative prototyping with possible industry placement (Year 2), and exploratory movement sessions with dancers (Years 2-3). Phenomenological data from semi-structured interviews and video-stimulated recall will be analysed thematically to understand how Body-focused FX influence kinesthetic awareness and support basic body training, and facilitate emotional regulation through movement. With these findings, I aim to contribute design strategies for translating somatic and regulatory principles into mixed reality spaces and empirical insights into how these can support embodied movement practice and autonomic nervous system regulation.

Keywords : FX, somatics, LBMS, emotional regulation

1 Introduction

In recent years, immersive technologies (XR) have increasingly supported creative and expressive movement experiences [9, 17, 18, 27, 39, 45, 48] and offer unprecedented opportunities for cultivating somatic awareness [38, 43, 45]. However, this work has predominantly explored spatial composition, immersive presence, and embodiment through environmental and avatar design [1, 6, 22, 23, 42, 47]. Where visual feedback systems have been developed they have focused on motion trajectories [4] and spatial patterns, often drawing from Laban's Effort and Space elements [2, 10, 34, 36, 46]. While adjacent

fields have demonstrated valuable visualisation of internal states—from biofeedback for embodiment [30] to muscle activation mapping for sports training [19, 25]-including Bartenieff Fundamentals' principles of internal body organisation (breath support, core-distal connectivity, head-tail articulation) [5, 16, 20] into real-time FX that invite proprioceptive attention and foster self-directed

somatic exploration remains unexplored.

Building upon previous research, which investigated how VFX could amplify perceptual qualities of movement related to Effort and Space elements of the LBMS, I now aim to extend this work to address the

Body element of the BESS framework. Rather than using VFX to merely decorate or externalise motion, this work will explore how mixed reality spaces can attune users to internal relationships within their moving bodies while supporting emotional regulation. Drawing on polyvagal theory's understanding of autonomic nervous system states [29] and emotion regulation research [15, 33], I propose a mixed reality space augmented with Body-focused FX designed to guide attention toward exploring internal connectivity patterns and facilitate movement between arousal states. Where the FX will serve as extrinsic regulatory scaffolds [15] and pedagogical provocations rather than sensor-based representations of actual body states. Through iterative design and movement sessions with dance practitioners, I will investigate how these FX in a mixed reality scenario influence kinesthetic awareness and support exploratory movement practice, to facilitate navigation within one's window of tolerance. This research contributes design strategies for including somatic connectivity principles in immersive environments and empirical understanding of how such effects support embodied movement practice and emotional self-regulation, opening new directions for designing technologies that honour and support embodied ways of knowing.

2 Related Work

2.1 Emotion Regulation Through Movement

Emotional regulation involves actively influencing one's emotional experience [15]. Gross's process model of emotional regulation identified that people can use antecedent or response-based strategies to deal with unwanted emotions, and that in response-based approaches, people can regulate their emotion by recognising and changing any of the emotion components, e.g. tone, facial expression, thoughts, and

physiological arousal levels [13–15]. Up- and down-regulation move individuals from under- and over-arousal respectively towards the "window of tolerance," or optimal level of emotional arousal where the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous systems balance [33], leading to calm and effective responses to emotional triggers or stressors. Somatic and movement-based therapies play a crucial role in healing and emotional regulation [12, 31]. The Laban/Bartenieff Movement System (LBMS) provides a structured vocabulary for describing movement through Body, Effort, Shape, and Space (BESS) [5, 44]. Using LBMS, Shafir et al. identified specific motor elements that characterise movements whose execution enhances basic emotions, suggesting that emotional self-regulation can be achieved through incorporating desired motor qualities into everyday movements [32]. Tsachor and Shafir further proposed that LMA principles—particularly developmental sequencing and component affinities—can guide gradual shifts in movement patterns to support emotional resiliency [40].

2.2 LBMS and Movement-Based Interaction

LBMS elements of Effort and Space have informed numerous interactive systems [3, 7, 10, 11, 35, 37] predominantly focusing on externalising movement qualities through spatial visualisation directing user attention outward to screen-based representations rather than inward to proprioceptive awareness. Recent work in XR has examined somatic awareness, with systems like Thomas's multi-person VR demonstrating how immersive environments can support "returning to the body" through kinesthetic attention [38] or Weber's particle-based choreographic encounters showed that abstract visualisations can reconnect dancers to somatic experience [45]. As emotion regulation research has gained prominence, contemporary systems

increasingly address internal body states [26, 28, 49], particularly breathing [8, 21, 24, 41]. However, these systems typically operate from either an external focus, sensor-detection to represent physiological states like breathing or interventions from sedentary positions. Building on these perspectives and my previous research (Figure 1), I propose to explore Body-informed FX for a mixed reality space. These augmentations are conceived not as representational models of anatomy, but as expressive mediations to support users in navigating between hyper- and hypoarousal states. Aiming to shifting from immersive experiences that track the body toward systems that help users return to it.

3 Research Scope and Expected Contributions I am in the early stages of my doctoral research, building upon my master's work investigating VFX amplification of Laban's Effort qualities and Space elements. This doctoral project extends that trajectory toward the Body element of the LBMS BESS framework shifting from visualising external motion qualities to supporting awareness of internal body organisation through Bartenieff Fundamentals' principles of total body connectivity.

I am currently conducting a literature review spanning movement computing, embodied interaction, somatic practices, and FX/XR design. This review employs thematic analysis to identify how technology has been used to support movement awareness, mapping the gap between external motion amplification and internal body organisation.

3.1 Research Questions

Building upon research investigating Effort qualities and Space elements, this doctoral work extends toward the Body element. Given technical constraints in real-time tracking, the approach focuses on designing a mixed reality space with effects that guide movers' proprioceptive and interoceptive attention to support self-directed somatic exploration rather than

attempting to detect or display actual internal states.

These considerations lead to the following research questions:

RQ1: How can FX be designed using Bartenieff Fundamentals' Body principles to support up- and down-regulation through proprioceptive attention?

RQ1.1: What design strategies can incorporate Body principles of efficient movement into a mixed reality space to invite internal exploration?

RQ1.2: To what extent do Body-focused effects in mixed reality influence users' capacity for up- and down-regulation through movement?

RQ2: In what ways can Body-focused effects support users' development of intrinsic capacity for up- and down-regulation?

RQ2.1: In what ways, if any, do these FX elicit deeper sensing of internal patterning connections?

3.2 Research Plan

Figure 2 as appendix outlines the three-year research plan. Year 1 focuses on a comprehensive literature review across movement computing, somatic practices, FX design, and Dance/Movement Therapy (DMT), followed by co-design sessions with LBMS/BESS experts and DMT practitioners to inform initial FX prototypes developed through an iterative Research through Design approach. Year 2 includes a possible 3–6 month industry placement with FX professionals to integrate emerging technologies and workflows into prototype refinement, leading to exploratory movement sessions with dancers and somatic practitioners in Years 2–3. These sessions will generate phenomenological and observational data, analysed thematically to understand how Body-

focused FX influence proprioceptive awareness and embodied learning, ultimately contributing design strategies

and empirical insights for expressive, somatically grounded FX systems.

Figure 1: VFX prototypes developed for a mixed-reality contemporary dance production. Left: Transparent layered mesh with animated noise evoking 'thrashing' sensation. Right: Web-like effect transitioning from binding (tension) to dispersed trails (freedom).

A Timeline

Figure 2: expected research timeline

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Cautious predictions to support decision makers in movement-related areas

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Abstract

In a world where increasingly important decisions are made by computational systems, the trustworthiness of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a central concern. To be trustworthy, an AI system must be lawful, ethical, and robust, allowing human agency and oversight [2]. It must also ensure user well-being and privacy, as well as providing transparency, safety, fairness, and accountability. High-stakes scenarios, such as health applications, that involve potentially high-risk and profoundly impactful decisions underscore the importance of these trustworthy requirements. In our respective works, we tackle the robustness aspect of trustworthy AI through uncertainty quantification, aiming to inform decision-makers about the confidence level of AI-generated results. The idea is to be able to give, to the decision-makers, an information about the uncertainty of the given result. This uncertainty could come both from the data and the AI model itself [6]. For example, it could be a subset of classes for a classification task or an interval for a regression one. In this doctoral consortium presentation, we introduce two different projects that apply Trustworthy AI methods to movement-related areas.

The first application is part of the ReArm project [11], a quadruple-blinded, randomised, sham-controlled, bi-centre, twoarm parallel, and interventional study design. Patients followed a standard 3-week in-patient rehabilitation programme, and accelerometer, Electroencephalography (EEG), and Functional near-infrared spectroscopy (fNIRS) data were collected. Using cautious clustering [9] and explainability techniques [1], the goal is to provide rehabilitation clinicians with a data-driven unsupervised categorisation of patients' movement patterns. Cautious clustering methods model hesitation, avoiding unfounded choices when difficult decisions are faced. This uncertainty representation associates each point to a mass function, using the framework of the Evidential Theory [13]. Explainability techniques [8] allow for criticism of some models' decisions and introduce medical specialists' beliefs into the system's behaviour. These two paradigms enable knowledge building about each patient's specific situation, allowing medical professional to detect difficulties and potential good rehabilitation choices and leading to a personalised approach to post-stroke treatment.

The second application is about Return To Play (RTP). This notion refers to the period of unavailability of an athlete. For example, for a football player, the RTP can be defined as the time interval between the injury and the return to the field. The idea of this project is to predict and update, throughout the rehabilitation process, the athlete's expected return date based on the evolution of certain movement-related monitoring indicators [3, 7]. These indicators (time series) can be derived from movement performance (strength, speed, etc.), well-being, and medical examinations. These RTP predictions should be seen as additional information to

support decision makers (strength and conditioning coaches, physiotherapists, sports physicians, etc.). Indeed, currently, such decisions are made through trial and error and the experience of the medical and technical staff. Sometimes decisions are also supported by medical data, although MRI has its limitations [5, 7, 10, 12]. Note that, the information about RTP is particularly important as it plays a key role in club planning (rehabilitation programs, return to competition, potential recruitment, etc.). These predictions concern a sensitive area, namely the health of athletes. Thus, quantifying the uncertainty of the RTP prediction model allows, for decision makers, to use or disregard the predictions depending on their relevance. In particular, since we are dealing with time series and an online prediction setting, Online Conformal Prediction could be an interesting option.[4].

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Cyborg Sensing: A *Kinotechnic* Inquiry into the Epistemic Infrastructures of Movement and Perception

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This presentation establishes my PhD project *Ways of Being Cyborg* - an inquiry into how technological infrastructures reorganise human perception and movement. While sensors and motion-capture systems have become central to studying, teaching, and designing movement, they also reorganise what can be sensed, measured, and known about the body. Being-cyborg refers to a condition where human perception becomes distributed and movement modulated across human and technical systems. The cyborg is a mode of operation, not an object - not part-human/part-machine¹, but a dynamic arrangement where sensing and knowing are co-generated across bodies and technologies, producing new ways of being embodied and knowing. To study how this coupling generates new modes of embodiment, the thesis develops a *kinotechnic* method: a transductive approach investigating how movement and the technical systems through which it is sensed become mutual sites of inquiry. Rather than separating scientific, artistic, and theoretical practices, it moves between laboratory, studio, and reflection to explore how human and machinic perception co-produce each other. These experimental systems function as nodes in larger epistemic infrastructures, where methods of measurement, visualisation and calibration condition how bodies and movement become knowable.

Distributed Sensing and Perception

This research examines how the architectures that allow machines to sense and compute motion emerge from human perceptual logics [2], and how those logics are transductively reshaped through the operations of the machines they give rise to, generating a processual rather than mediational [3] understanding of knowledge and embodiment. Within this distributed ecology, sensing and perception mark two interdependent levels of operation. Sensing designates the material registration of change - how bodies and devices capture or modulate physical signals before meaning arises [4]. Perception refers to the organisation of those signals into qualitative experience or pattern recognition [5]. In human systems, these processes intertwine; in technical systems, they are distributed between sensors and computational routines, each conditioning what the other can register [6]. Rather than resolving this difference, the *kinotechnic* method treats it as productive - the cyborg emerges precisely where human and technical operations remain irreducible yet coupled.

Three Interlinked Strands

1. A movement-complexity study compares how performers, observers, and computational systems evaluate dance movement quality. By correlating kinematic and entropy-based descriptors [7] with perceptual ratings of control and fluency, the study functions as an epistemic experiment disguised as biomechanics - examining how different perceptual systems construct movement knowledge.

2. The Touch Analyser, a tactile sensing installation, materialises this inquiry in another register. It translates touch into data and back into description, exposing how perception becomes governable through interfaces that quantify affect and texture. Touch refuses the distance that vision and motion capture assume. Where kinematic systems track movement at a remove, the Touch Analyser collapses sensor and sensed into contact itself; making governability and intimacy indistinguishable. This exposes a different modality of cyborg sensing: one where measurement requires proximity, and where the interface doesn't represent the body but extends it.
3. Theoretical and diagrammatic work articulates the *kinotechnic* method as a *distributed epistemology of cyborg sensing*, translating empirical and artistic results into a transferable research framework

Research Architecture and Implications

Together these components form a research architecture that enacts the very distribution it investigates, the ongoing translation between sensing, measuring, and knowing. The work gains relevance in a context where motion-sensing technologies increasingly shape clinical assessment, performance training, interface design, and bodily surveillance. Building on insights of STS scholars and philosophers of technology [8], which examine how measurement practices produce knowledge, and from phenomenology, which explores how technologies mediate perception, this project seeks to enact those perspectives within concrete sensing setups. The kinotechnic method treats such systems as epistemological experiments rather than neutral instruments, combining empirical and artistic procedures to make their operations perceptible and discussable across disciplines. Moving between biomechanical study, installation, and theoretical reflection, it investigates how measurement architectures organise what counts as perception, which signals stabilise as data, and how notions of skill, norm, or health become materially instantiated. Presenting at the Doctoral Consortium offers a context to consider how this transductive approach, where human and machinic perception are both site and method of inquiry, might contribute to motion-computing research attentive to its own epistemological effects.

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Exploring Choreographic Processes With AI-Generated Movements

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1 Introduction

Generative AI is transforming all artistic fields, opening up new creative avenues and tools, while raising numerous challenges regarding its use. Although dance has been slower than other artistic fields to adopt AI, it is increasingly opening up to its generative power, driven in particular by research conducted in the field of 3D animation. Despite the impressive technical capabilities of state-of-the-art models, they exhibit a striking deficit in incorporating dance practitioners' knowledge into the design, development, and evaluation of movement generation models. To do so, I take a performance-based research approach in-the-world¹, where I collaborate with dance practitioners or take part in the creation of choreographic pieces as a member of the creative team.

2 Background

Most research in dance movement generation is currently focused on the technical capabilities of the models themselves, with few studies investigating how practitioners interact with these technologies. New models are typically evaluated based on quantitative metrics and human input is gathered only through crowd-sourcing platforms such as Prolific [1, 6, 7, 12]. While these evaluations are a necessary first step to assess the models' capabilities, there is a strong need to study the use of these systems in choreographic settings. Previous HCI research has shown

the value of deploying and assessing technology for dance and performance in-the-world [2, 3, 5].

Some recent HCI studies have explored how professional dancers interact with generative models. Wallace et al. examined how dancers improvise using generated dance movements, including glitches, and found that these glitches can have creative value [14]. The authors also outlined the challenges in providing dancers and choreographers with appropriate interfaces that enable them to interact with the generative model without the assistance of machine learning experts [13]. More recently, Liu and Sra introduced DanceGen, an interface that allows practitioners to interact with a generative model [8] directly. The model is based on the Motion Diffusion Model [11], fine-tuned on the AIST++ dataset. To evaluate the interface, the authors conducted a study in which dance practitioners used the system to create sequences, followed by semi-structured interviews. The interface enabled users to iteratively refine the generated movements through text prompts. The study showed that while the system sparked creativity, dancers emphasized the importance of integrating such tools into studio settings.

While these works present valuable insights about how dancers interact with the generative models, their agency often remains limited. The models are not designed or trained in collaboration with

practitioners, whose input is only gathered through brief improvisation sessions once the system is developed. For example, models trained on generic datasets (e.g., AIST++) may not align with the specific styles and/or repertoire of the dancers. My PhD aims to address this gap by designing and assessing movement generation models in close collaboration with dance communities and practitioners.

3 Studies

3.1 Study 1: Designing Movement Generation Models in Collaboration with Voguing and Dancehall Dancers

For my first case study, we collaborated with a Voguing and Dancehall collective in order to design a movement generation model centered on the collective's dance practices. We recorded motion capture data of the collective's repertoire and trained a movement generation model based on the chor-rnn architecture [4] using only their movement. We then organized an initial improvisation session, which revealed that, despite its limited realism, the generated movements could serve as a source of inspiration for the dancers. However, we noticed the lack of an appropriate tool to visualize motion capture data, which was both necessary for the research team to monitor the models' training and for dancers to directly interact with the generated movements using a dedicated tool. To that end, we iteratively designed Korai, a tool that facilitates data exploration, enables interactive visualization of both real and generated movements, and allows comparisons between generated movement alternatives. Using this tool, we trained several variants of movement generation models.

We then conducted a comparative structured observation study [9] that compared three model variants with high, medium, and low fidelity to the original dataset. Our results showed that dancers favored either highly faithful or highly unrealistic outputs, rejecting medium

fidelity as neither authentic nor creatively stimulating. The findings revealed that dancers draw inspiration from diverse sources, including highly glitched movements, which can spark creativity. However, when movements were realistic, dancers expected strict adherence to their dance style, especially in codified forms like Voguing and Dancehall. Based on these findings, we suggest an "Uncanny Valley" effect in AI-generated dance movements, where outputs that are almost—but not quite—realistic can be less engaging.

The project also highlighted the challenges of understanding AI model behavior and the tediousness of developing dance generation models. The Korai system helped mitigate these issues, enabling the research team to iterate on and understand model training more easily. It also enabled a direct way to interact with the generative models, allowing for a better understanding of their behavior through direct interaction.

3.2 Study 2: A Longitudinal Study on Movements Generation in a Dance Production

For my second case study, I collaborated with choreographers Liz Santoro and Pierre Godard on their new piece, This is Unreal, a solo that explores the blurred lines between reality and virtuality in the age of AI, deepfakes, and clones. The project aimed to blend synthetic data—text, images, music, and movement—with real elements. I joined the production from autumn 2024 to Autumn 2025, participating in residencies and working on generated dance, as well as iterating on the Korai system to support the dancers in examining and learning the generated movements. Santoro and Godard are experienced in working with generative processes. They sought hyper-realistic AI-generated movements that are indistinguishable from human performance, with strict adherence to anatomical realism and their own choreographic style.

My primary role involved generating dance motion. We recorded nearly 13 hours of motion capture data, including excerpts from the company's repertoire, improvisations, and classical ballet performances. Initially, we trained a chore2rn model on this data, but the choreographers found the results unconvincing due to anatomical and stylistic inaccuracies. Recognizing the limitations of this older model, we shifted to EDGE [12], a state-of-the-art model that offers more realistic outputs but consequently requires more data and computational resources. A major challenge was aligning our motion data with the EDGE model's expected format, as different motion capture systems use varying skeletal architectures and representations. To address this challenge, we standardized the data, iterating through movement generation and refining the model based on feedback from Santoro. This process involved curating generated movements, retraining the model with the company's repertoire, and discussing kinesthetic qualities to improve realism. To support the dancer in learning AI-generated movements, I further iterated on the Korai system, adding features to facilitate movement exploration. Throughout the process, we documented the choreographer learning experience and gathered feedback from the artistic team, reflecting on how AI-generated movements could inform choreographic practices despite often lacking physical nuance.

3.3 Study 3: For Patricia: AI and Choreographic Structure

For Patricia is a dance and live music performance created by Sarah Fdili Alaoui and John Sullivan, supported by the European MODINA2 project. It is an

homage to postmodern choreographer Trisha Brown, who used patterns such as repetition or inversion to generate choreographic structures.

In this piece, the AI system serves as a scaffolding for the performance, organizing dance and music patterns. The piece's structure was dynamically generated before each performance by analyzing archival videos of Trisha Brown and mapping them to the choreography of Fdili Alaoui. To do so, we used the Dicy2 system on MaxMSP. Dicy2 takes as input sequential data, that is called the "model", learned from live or offline streams of data and generates based on pattern matching new sequences interactively according to various types and degrees of constraints called "scenario". We gave as input "model" to Dicy2 the data from Fdili Alaoui's video recording of their dance sequences, and as a guiding scenario for the generation, data from Trisha Brown's dance from archival videos. The idea behind it is that Dicy2 would organize the choreography of the artists guided by Trisha's dance. Each show utilized a different archival video of Trisha, creating a renewed structure that was both performed by the performers and displayed as scores for the audience to view.

4 Contributions and Future Work

In the three case studies that I described, the research consisted of exploring the creative capabilities of the AI models and the interactive systems that allow interaction with them, along with the practitioners, during longitudinal studies for long collaborations of artistic residencies. The results from the 3 case studies allow us to advocate for increased participation in the design of AI technology within the dance and performance fields.

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Kinematic Movement Signatures and Flow in Co-Improvising Flamenco Dyads

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1 INTRODUCTION

Recent work on arts-based interventions increasingly includes movement improvisation, yet empirical work still lacks a unified framework (Horváth et al., 2025). Improvisation—the real-time creation of novel, useful actions—underpins many music and dance traditions (Beaty, 2015; Leach & Stevens, 2020; Loui, 2018; Pressing, 2001; Sawyer, 2006), even though sound and movement are still often studied apart. Early improvised sequences tend to be uncoordinated and energetically costly, but training improves efficiency and control (Goebel & Palmer, 2013; Phillips-Silver, 2009; Schmidt et al., 2019), and automatization of motor processes with stronger action–perception coupling frees capacity for expressive flexibility (Bläsing et al., 2012; Gray, 1981; Novembre & Keller, 2014; Pressing, 2001). Improvisatory freedom also reshapes decision- and motor-related brain networks in expert jazz pianists (Da Mota et al., 2025), motivating the open question of whether comparable shifts appear in movement kinematics—especially in interactive music–dance performance. At the same time, improvisation can raise objective energetic demand through exploratory motion, while

peak states are often felt as effortless and linked to flow (Csikszentmihalyi et al., 2005), highlighting a possible dissociation between felt ease and physical load.

Emotion is conveyed systematically by movement features such as speed, temporal variability, and smoothness (Camurri et al., 2003, 2016; Ivcevic et al., 2023; Juslin & Sloboda, 2011). Pose-derived kinetic energy (KE) provides a velocity-based summary that may track both expressive character and performance mode (rehearsed vs improvised), while quantifying load alongside flow can inform intervention design—supporting engagement and psychological benefit while monitoring overexertion risk. Complementing amplitude-focused summaries, information-theoretic descriptors such as permutation entropy (PE), widely used to study predictability and temporal organisation in music (Pearce & Wiggins, 2012), can characterise temporal structure in movement. Dynamical-systems accounts further cast improvisation as metastable organisation across nested timescales, alternating local stability with

exploratory excursions (Laroche et al., 2024). Yet quantitative links among energy, temporal complexity, and improvised interaction remain underdeveloped in music–dance dyads. We address this gap by analysing KE, mean PE, and PE variability in professional flamenco dancer–guitarist pairs across rehearsed and improvised conditions and two *palos* with contrasting affective profiles (tangos vs. soleá).

Flamenco is a performance-centred Andalusian practice in which dancers and guitarists co-improvise within shared rhythmic–expressive constraints of a *palo* (genre) (Herrero, 1991). Its norms encourage performers to project palo-appropriate rhythm and affect (e.g., tangos as more outward and animated vs soleá as more serious and introspective) (Foggo, 2021; Manuel, 1989; Washabaugh, 2021). The intensity typically accompanying a flamenco performance, usually escalates toward the *cierre* or closing *remate* (a close to a series of flamenco steps, musical phrase, or line of a song) and may facilitate the state of flow commonly experienced by flamenco artists (Trigo & Cruz, 2020). Flamenco therefore provides a naturalistic setting for relating whole-body KE and temporal complexity to improvisation, expression, and flow in joint music–dance performance.

2. AIMS

We address this gap in literature by examining KE and PE in professional flamenco dancer–guitarist dyads that perform rehearsed and improvised pieces across two *palos* (genres) of distinct affective character (tangos vs soleá). The study has two principle aims:

1. To test whether whole-body movement kinematics (KE, PE) differ across *palos* and improvisation modes, separately for dancer and guitarist.

2. To test whether whole-body movement kinematics (KE, PE) are associated with flow intensity, and whether associations differ by role.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Eleven duos of flamenco musicians and dancers were instructed to perform a rehearsed piece, freely improvise, and combine improvised and rehearsed parts on two rhythmically and emotionally distinct flamenco *palos* (genres). We collected audio–video recordings of the performances. Participants retrospectively annotated flow intensity experienced (7-point scale) while viewing their videos on a laptop, yielding time-stamped flow intensity traces. Front-view videos were processed with MediaPipe Pose to estimate 3D joint trajectories. A Python adaptation of the MoCap Toolbox (Toiviainen & Burger, 2015) computed framewise 2D whole-body kinetic energy from low-pass–filtered body-segment velocities using anthropometric mass distributions (Plagenhoef et al., 1983). Permutation entropy was estimated on KE timeseries. Recordings were segmented into fixed (rehearsed dance and music), mixed (improvised choreography and rehearsed composition), free (improvised dance and music) segments in ELAN.

4. MODELING AND PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Linear mixed models (LMMs) were fit using per-segment means of whole-body kinetic energy (KE) and permutation entropy (PE) to test main effects of performance mode (free, mixed, fixed), *palo* (Tangos vs. Soleá), and time. Separate LMMs (with recording outcomes) tested associations between mean KE, mean PE, PE variability, and self-reported flow intensity. Preliminary results showed higher whole-body kinetic energy (KE) and permutation entropy (PE) in Tangos than in Soleá,

highlighting temporal organisation of whole-body kinematics as a complement to amplitude- or velocity-derived measures when linking genre to expressive movement. For improvisatory signatures, dancers showed higher KE in mixed than in free performances; both roles showed lower PE in mixed and free than in fixed performances. Together, these patterns suggest that joint performance can reshape the statistical structure of movement in ways that do not reduce to a simple “more improvisation → less predictable movement” rule at every scale. Finally, flow intensity was negatively associated with mean PE but positively associated with variability of PE over time, consistent with dynamical-systems accounts in which locally more predictable dynamics can co-occur with broader temporal variation in complexity during optimal experience.

5. FUTURE DIRECTIONS

We plan to integrate audio descriptors (e.g., tempo, rhythmic complexity, loudness) and interaction-oriented measures of coordination and leader–follower structure (e.g., lagged coupling / Granger-style predictability) to probe mechanisms and candidate confounds in the present models. We will also resolve kinematics by body region for guitarists (e.g., head, fretting/plucking hand, time-keeping foot) to test whether palo-specific nuances appear below the whole-body summary. Overall, these preliminary findings support 2D video–derived KE and PE (and PE variability) as practical, ecologically strong descriptors of joint improvisation, genre-linked expression, and flow intensity, enabling continuous motion capture without typical laboratory movement constraints. Finally, the approach may inform movement-based interventions by linking improvisatory exploration and positive affect to dynamical signatures that can be monitored for engagement while tracking energetic load to reduce overexertion risk..

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Learning to Teach Gestures: Adaptive Feedback for Human–Machine Co-Learning in craft

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Abstract

Learning expert skills such as craftsmanship relies on fine sensorimotor coordination and gradual adaptation, traditionally supported by the presence of a teacher who observe and adjust their feedback according to the learner's characteristics and adaptation. However, learners often lack experts with whom to practice effectively. Designing a system capable of automatically generating optimal feedback, in terms of modality, form, intensity, and timing, is therefore a key challenge for craft learning. In traditional crafts, gestures are deeply situated, embedded in a material and social context that shapes both how the movement is learned, performed, and how feedback is interpreted. Unlike standardized laboratory motions, craft gestures are variable and highly coupled to the material's, the environment and the human state. Most current intelligent tutoring systems do not take in consideration temporal progression, non-stationarity, and the delayed effects of feedback. We propose formalizing feedback selection as a multi-armed bandit problem that can be optimized through reinforcement learning. We introduce a hierarchical, multi-granularity model of the learner's state, combining sensorimotor, dynamic, and contextual dimensions. To solve the exploration-exploitation dilemma, Thompson sampling is studied for its probabilistic modeling of uncertainty and its efficient equilibrium with knowledge. Langevin Soft Actor-Critic (LSAC) extends this paradigm with stochastic gradient dynamics to improve stability and adaptation to non-stationary returns. In order to accelerate convergence and explainability of feedback, the feedback policy can be initialized based on expert teaching rules. The long-term retention effectiveness of our system will be validated with glassblowing apprentices.

Keywords : Sensorimotor learning, Adaptive feedback, Reinforcement learning, Human-machine co-learning, Craft pedagogy

1 Introduction

In craft learning, progress relies on subtle adaptation and individualized guidance, often lacking human experts. This research aims to design an intelligent interaction mechanism capable of selecting, in real time, adaptive and personalized feedback based on the learner's performance and

evolution, in order to maximize both immediate correction and long-term progress. Existing motor tutoring systems often rely on static rules or overall scores that are unable to reflect temporal progress [1, 11]. Furthermore, representations derived from neural networks lack interpretability for a human teacher [5].

Our approach aims to overcome these limitations by combining:

- (1) a hierarchical model of the learner's state,
- (2) a reinforcement learning (RL)-based decision-making mechanism that approximates the complexity of combining real-time and non-stationary policy through an actor-critic approach,
- (3) and explicit integration of human didactic knowledge to ensure the consistency and explainability of feedback.

2 State of the Art, scientific objectives

Motor learning highlights the role of multimodal feedback in improving perception/action coupling and skill acquisition [6, 7]. Yet, most intelligent tutoring systems still rely on static rules or global scores, offering limited adaptation to learner variability and temporal change [1, 11]. While motion analysis increasingly uses sensor data, neural representations remain difficult to interpret pedagogically [5]. Recent work explores adaptive feedback through machine learning and contextual multi-armed bandits [2, 3], but rarely considers non-stationarity in human learning or the integration of expert heuristics. Our work combines interpretable gesture representations with pedagogically informed reinforcement learning for situated craft learning. We frame feedback selection as an optimizable sequential decision problem, where each intervention influences both immediate performance and long-term evolution. Because learners adapt to feedback, the optimal policy is inherently non-stationary, requiring the system to adapt to the human adaptation, this is Human–Machine Co-Learning [8].

3 Multidimensional movement quality

We aim to describe movement quality through a set of complementary metrics rather than a single aggregate score. Our hypothesis is that a structured representation space, combining multiple

indicator families, provides a more accurate and interpretable estimation of the learner's state. The metrics are distributed across three dimensions: Body support: local (joint-based) or global (postural); Nature: temporal or spatial; Reference: absolute (intrinsic motion features) or relative (distance to an expert model). This formalism aims to support both human interpretation and algorithmic feedback quality, consistent with prior work combining metrics for motion quality assessment [7, 10].

4 Adaptive feedback

The choice of feedback is modeled as a contextual sequential decision problem, in which the system must select the most effective feedback modality given the learner's current estimated state. Each action corresponds to a feedback modality, type, intensity, or timing; the reward corresponds to the observed improvement in motor performance; and the context encodes the learner's latent state. The system maximizes cumulative reward while handling non-stationary learning dynamics, delayed feedback effects, and a continuous, combinatorial action space.

4.0.1 Thompson Sampling. We first adopt a Contextual Thompson Sampling (TS) approach [9], maintaining a Bayesian posterior over the expected reward of each feedback action. TS naturally balances exploration and exploitation by sampling according to uncertainty, but its decisions are myopic : optimizing short-term reward without propagating long-term value. It is therefore suited for early learning phases, requiring a complementary mechanism for long-term adaptation.

4.0.2 Actor–Critic and Langevin Soft Actor–Critic (LSAC). To address this, we use an Actor–Critic framework, where the Actor learns a policy to maximize long-term reward and the Critic estimates value to guide updates. The Soft Actor–Critic (SAC) adds entropy regularization to promote stable exploration, while the Langevin Soft

Actor–Critic (LSAC) variant [4] introduces stochastic noise for Bayesian policy exploration, improving adaptation to non-stationary learners. Given limited motion data, the policy is initialized with human teaching rules to guide early exploration. Due to the limited amount of motion data collecting possibilities in artisanal environments being complex and participant numbers low: we propose to initialize the reinforcement learning policy with explicit human didactic rules to guide early exploration.

5 Experimental Protocol

The models will be evaluated in the context of scientific glassblowing. Motion data from

experts and novices will be captured using full-body IMU suits and sensors on tools. Participants will be divided into subgroups to test three hypotheses: (H1) the impact of representation structure (single, merged, or vectorized metrics), (H2) the efficiency of adaptive feedback policies (rule-based, Thompson Sampling, or LSAC), and (H3) the contribution of pedagogical priors (RL-only vs. RL guided by human rules). Performance will be assessed through motor improvements, expert evaluations of feedback relevance, and variability across sessions, ensuring a controlled validation of adaptive feedback mechanisms in craft learning.

Figure 1: Adaptive feedback mechanism combining motion analysis and reinforcement learning

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Movement as a socio-material practice: matters in the making

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Abstract

This research, rooted in dance, choreography, and technology, examines socio-material practices in interaction design, focusing on real-time feedback and attunement as a relational practice. Moving beyond normative assumptions, it explores real-time motion tracking to create embodied, dynamic interactions fostering shared agency and interdependence. Adopting transdisciplinary methodologies, the study aims to develop ethical, inclusive practices of technologies that reconfigure agency and power through developing compositional scores and performative work. It contributes new perspectives on movement, relationality, and co-creation, advancing socially aware and embodied approaches in technology-mediated environments.

Keywords : Human-Computer Interaction, live performance, relationality

Human Computer Interaction 'has its roots in engineering and psychology with its rather clear-cut epistemological commitment to positivism' [5, 13]. Given the increasing integration and impact of technology in everyday life, Human-Computer Interaction is faced with many challenges: 'HCI may not yet be in a state of serious crisis, but it is certainly cracking and squealing, struggling to make sense of computers, humans and interfaces in the face of rapid technological progress, coupled with profound social change.' [5, 3]. With an interdisciplinary background that combines dance, choreography and technology, I explore aspects of these challenges by investigating socio-material practices for interaction design. The focus will be on real-time feedback and attunement to explore movement as a relational practice, while also challenging the normative assumptions embedded in how technology scripts movement. Movement is increasingly addressed in design research, such as work on dance notation [1] [3], movement as design

material and skill [10] [13] [7], somatic training for designers [9], and choreographically informed design processes [15]. While these approaches often conceptualised the moving body as singular and prioritised object-user relationships, emerging relational perspectives increasingly challenge normative and universalising assumptions in the design of movement and computation [2] [12] [6] [8] [11] [14]. During the PhD, I will develop several practice works that aim to examine and develop live, dynamic interactions that foster interdependence and shared agency through movement. These will serve as exemplars in the PhD. The creation of the exemplars is inspired and challenged by Frauenberger's 'ethico-onto-epistemological perspective'. He summarizes this perspective as 'collapsing ontology, epistemology and ethics into one, makes clear that any making of futures is all of this at once: designing technology means creating hybrid things with ambiguous boundaries and proposed programs of actions that seek to

reconfigure agency and power with moral responsibility.' [5, 22]. He further suggests moving beyond optimising user experiences to instead focus on relationality by developing methods that invite critical and even polemical participation. I will work with real-time motion tracking and explore its potential as a relational technology in ways that examine interdependence and foster shared agency. The framing research questions are: how can we design real-time and embodied environments with rich dynamics that enable engagement and shared agency? How may the sensed and negotiated awareness of more-than-human entanglements contribute to reflections on social wellbeing understood as connection and inclusion? And how may such work contribute to the development of ethical and inclusive technologies? The PhD project adopts a transdisciplinary, qualitative methodology combining experimentation, theoretical framing, interviews, and analysis. Theoretically, it draws on movement research, performing practices in HCI and HRI, design theory and humanities and practically, it involves collaborations with researchers that are developing computer vision, AI and bio

markers. Compositional scores serve as the main research instrument, enabling exploration of temporal relations, distributed agency, and embodied meaning making. Theorized by choreographer Burrows [4, 142]: "A score is one way to get an overview of time and materials. It freezes time in a concrete form, allowing you to glimpse what can be hard to grasp perceptually in real-time experience (. . .) allowing you to see and shift the relation of materials over longer periods." This positions movement as a practice embedded in complex entangled dynamics that evolve over time, and as a practice that must be examined beyond real-time interaction, enabling the development of a critical perspective to inform future movement-based technologies. Through iterative practice-based research, it aims to expand understanding of movement in design and contribute new approaches for shaping ethical and embodied interactions in technologically mediated environments. Concluding, this research combines choreography, compositional scores, and interactive technologies to explore how human and non-human actors co-create meaning and relations.

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Movement Sonification Integrated to Rehabilitation-Readaptation

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Abstract

In France, 1.7 million people suffer from visual impairment, whether congenital or acquired. The loss of vision at later stages of life severely impacts orientation, mobility, psychological health and, ultimately, autonomy. Therefore, there is a great need for tools to help visually impaired people regain confidence and build better body representation. Movement sonification has proven an efficient tool for many applications, including movement rehabilitation. The goal of this doctoral research is to develop and evaluate a movement sonification device in a clinical context, thus bringing knowledge on sensori-motor learning and the ways this paradigm can benefit visually impaired people. Clinical trials will be performed to this end. The co-design approach will inform on relevant design paradigms when working with the clinical context : in particular, the impacts of human-computer interaction (HCI) personalisation, sound design and interaction design will be explored.

Keywords : Human-Computer Interaction, Sonification, Sound design, Movement, Sensori-motor integration, Visual Impairment, Rehabilitation-Readaptation

1 INTRODUCTION

Acquired blindness is a traumatic experience that impacts the quality of life and autonomy. Since vision is involved in the retro-action mechanism of motor control, visual impairment affects precise movement execution, but also balance, walking and postural control [1]. These motor difficulties cause limitations in physical/social activities, increase the risk of falling [2], and can ultimately explain the high proportion of anxiety and depressive disorders among visually impaired people: almost a third are affected [3]. In order to regain mobility and autonomy, other sensory feedback, such as proprioception and audition, must compensate for the loss of vision.

Therefore, there is a need for approaches and tools to help patients gain compensation mechanisms efficiently: supporting the development of spatial representations and movement control ultimately promotes confidence and motivation.

Recent studies confirmed that movement sonification, which provides auditory feedback on postures and gestures, can support sensori-motor learning and also motivate exploration and movement execution [4]. More specifically, movement sonification can 1) alter body perception and representation [5], 2) be used as sensory feedback to acquire motor skills in different domains [4] and 3) modulate the emotional states of the person [6]. Movement sonification has already been

proposed and evaluated in the treatment of chronic pain [7], supporting sensori-motor learning of movements and gestures (e.g., dysgraphia rehabilitation or facilitation of manual writing [8]) and post-stroke rehabilitation [9].

Sensory substitution for blind people is the use, among other modalities, of auditory feedback to translate real world information into auditory signals [10] like an "auditory white cane". Our approach, which is movement sonification, follows different objectives: it aims at improving the therapeutic process by helping visually impaired people reinforce their proprioception, which is supposed to compensate for the loss of vision and to help getting back movement fluidity. In this approach, sonification must be a temporary tool that people abandon once progress has been made.

It has been shown that continuous movement sonification can improve learning retention and prevent feedback dependency [11], but these mechanisms still need to be thoroughly studied in a clinical context. Recent advances in technology make interactive movement sonification realistically usable in a clinical context [9].

2 DOCTORAL PROJECT

2.1 Goals

The objectives of the thesis are threefold :

- 1 Fundamental/clinical: Studying the action-perception loop and the impact of movement sonification on proprioceptive representations with visually impaired people;
- 2 Technological: Developing and evaluating a movement sonification tool (figure 1) following a co-design approach with our clinical partners;
- 3 Design: Creating sonic/musical contents and gesture-sound mappings adapted to

the individual needs (personalisation) and coherent with the use case (adaptation).

2.2 Methods

A common pitfall in technology development for the visually impaired is the lack of multidisciplinary approach that could include therapists and patients [12]. This motivates us to follow user-centered/co-design [13] and action-research [14] methodologies, with the aim of both improving rehabilitation and producing knowledge. In a first step to our project, we seek to investigate the ways movement specialists (eg. psychomotricians, physiotherapists, working in rehabilitation) describe movement qualities. This would represent a first step to find relevant quantitative motion parameters that could be related to the practitioners movement descriptions. For this, we will investigate possible relationships and correlations between practitioners' annotations with recorded videos and sensors data (Inertial Motion Units). In a second step, we will design relationships between movement and sound. For this, we will use "technological probes" [15] (eg. a prototype version of the sonification device) along with semi-structured interviews. We expect the following contributions : 1) a shared motion lexicon/vocabulary with health practitioners, 2) related relevant motion descriptors for quantitative evaluation and 3) co-designed sound-gesture interaction scenarii with practitioners and patients, that can be adapted to different individual needs.

We will also perform complementary controlled studies with sighted people to evaluate specific aspects of the sonification device. First, the retention of sensori-motor learning (once the sound is removed) will be evaluated. Then, the impact of sound design in different categories (natural and synthetic sounds, for instance) on the experience will be assessed. Finally, clinical studies involving movement sonification will be conducted. The precise

protocol has yet to be defined in adhesion with the clinical practice.

3 PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Based on previous research [4, 9], two sonification scenarii have been defined in collaboration with psychomotricians³:

1. This scenario comprises three modules : head-chest alignment, body orientation and straight line following. The end goal is to set better proprioceptive representations and allow for better mobility.
2. This scenario allows the exploration of corporeity through full body interaction, with sensors placed of the arms. It aims at regaining fluidity in movements.

These scenarii will need to be improved after feedback from our clinical partners :

the sound feedback of the first scenario should be stable in volume, to give a precise position information. Then, the second scenario needs to be reworked in a user-centered approach, as it lacks adequacy with the clinical practice.

4 CONCLUSION

We believe that movement sonification as a rehabilitative tool is a viable alternative path to sensory substitution devices, and could possibly allow for better acceptance of the rehabilitation process, improving patients' sensori-motor skills, addressing their psychological difficulties and, ultimately, encouraging autonomy. The co-design methodology is a key aspect of this project that should help frame the users' (therapists and patients) needs more accurately, and create a device that is appropriate to the clinical context.

Figure 1: Principle schematic of our movement sonification device

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³ 3 Videos are available as supplementary material.

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On Improvisation and Open-Endedness: Insights for Experiential AI

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Abstract

Improvisation—the art of spontaneous creation that unfolds moment-to-moment without a scripted outcome—requires practitioners to continuously sense, adapt, and create anew. It is a fundamental mode of human creativity spanning music, dance, and everyday life. The open-ended nature of improvisation produces a stream of novel, unrepeatable moments—an aspect highly valued in artistic creativity. In parallel, open-endedness (OE)—a system’s capacity for unbounded novelty and endless “interestingness”—is exemplified in natural or cultural evolution and has been considered “the last grand challenge” in artificial life (ALife). The rise of generative AI now raises the question in computational creativity (CC) research: What makes a “good” improvisation for AI? Can AI learn to improvise in a genuinely open-ended way? In this work-in-progress paper, we report insights from in-depth interviews with 6 experts in improvisation across dance, music, and contact improvisation. We draw systemic connections between human improvisational arts and the design of future experiential AI agents that could improvise alone or alongside humans—or even with other AI agents—embodying qualities of improvisation drawn from practice: active listening (umwelt and awareness), being in the time (mindfulness and ephemerality), embracing the unknown (source of randomness and serendipity), non-judgmental flow (acceptance and dynamical stability, balancing structure and surprise (unpredictable criticality at edge of chaos), imaginative metaphor (synaesthesia and planning), empathy, trust, boundary, and care (mutual theory of mind), and playfulness and intrinsic motivation (maintaining interestingness).

1 Introduction

Improvisation is a foundational mode of human creativity, evident across diverse art forms—from jazz music to contemporary dance and adaptation of action in real-time, without a predetermined script. Improvisational arts have a long-standing presence in human culture: in music, improvisation has been widely studied—from instrumental jazz solos to freestyle rap

battles [2, 9, 21]; in dance, forms like contact improvisation—originated by Steve Paxton in 1972 [14]—emphasizes movement through physical contact; even emerging digital practices such as live coding treat code as a real-time performative medium [15]. Though it does not always produce brilliant works of art, improvisation is both experiential and open-ended by nature—it responds to the present moment, performing unrepeatable

actions and generating continuous novelty—qualities highly valued in artistic creativity [7]. In the field of artificial life (ALife), open-endedness (OE) refers to a system's capacity for ongoing innovation, producing unbounded novelty or endless "interestingness" without converging to a static equilibrium [12]. In nature, life itself exemplifies an open-ended evolutionary process: over billions of years, biological evolution has continually generated novel forms and behaviors without a fixed endpoint [20]. Cultural evolution provides a second real-world example of unbounded innovation [3]. In contrast, artificial systems—such as digital evolution system or generative AI—often plateauing after an initial burst of novelty [18]. Indeed, replicating the continually creative dynamics of natural or cultural evolution has been deemed "the the last grand challenge" [11]. Soros et al. [17] highlights a close relationship between creativity and open-endedness, suggesting that the difficulty of producing genuinely creative systems parallels the difficulty of achieving OE itself. Yet, to everyday conversation. It involves the spontaneous generation in the field of computational creativity (CC)—which Colton Simon and Wiggins Geraint A. [4] argue is "the final frontier"—most machine-generated creations remain closed-ended: produced via pre-programmed rules, fixed objectives, or models trained on past human data. Although recent generative AI models (large language models, video generation models, etc.) can produce impressively creative content and may appear open-ended, they do not truly achieve open-endedness. They often repeat patterns or clichés, essentially regurgitating averages of their training data. The fundamental reason may be a lack of agency: human creativity is not purely objective-oriented—it involves conviction, serendipity, curation, and enjoyment. As Stanley and Lehman [19] argue in "Why Greatness Cannot Be Planned," current AI systems lack this self-directed pursuit of endless "interestingness" to explore the un-

known or push their creativity beyond their training data and preset objectives. They lack the experiential learning that fuels human creators' continual growth. As Silver and Sutton [16] argues, AI development is entering an "era of experience"—moving beyond the "era of human data." This shift requires agents to learn through real-world interaction and self-directed exploration, rather than simply consuming static datasets. Hughes et al. [6] even posit that open-endedness is essential for any future artificial superintelligence—such an AI would need a self-driven capacity to discover novelty beyond human knowledge. Recent developments in human-computer interaction (HCI) and AI research have started exploring improvisational systems, from robots that jam with musicians to virtual partners that dance with humans. For instance, Pataranutaporn et al. [13] present Human–AI co-dancing performances where virtual dancers with generative models collaborate with live performers, evolving choreographic ideas together. Trajkova et al. [22]'s LuminAI system allows people to improvise dance movements with an AI dancer that observes, mirrors, and riffs on the user's gestures. In improvised theatre, Mathewson and Mirowski [10]'s Improbatics experiment placed a chatbot into a live improv comedy show, with audiences and even fellow actors unaware of which performer was AI. Researchers have also crafted improvisational experiences with non-humanoid agents: Dancing with Drones by Dong et al. [5], put autonomous drones on stage with human dancers, finding that an "intercorporeal understanding" had to be developed between the choreographer and the drones' behaviors to co-create expressive movement. Likewise, Drone Chi by La Delfa et al. [8] explored a Tai Chi-inspired human–drone interaction in which a flying robot and a person respond to each other's motions in a close, somatic loop. In music, Benford et al. [1] built an AI folk fiddler and found that performers had to negotiate autonomy and trust – e.g. by pre-setting the

AI's "looseness of control" and using simple intensity cues during performance – so that the human could enter a flow state with the AI and still feel safe to experiment. These pioneering systems hint at the possibilities of Experiential AI that can improvise with humans or other AIs. However, they also underscore the challenges: maintaining "interestingness", preventing the AI from generating dull or chaotic outputs, and enabling the AI to meaningfully evolve its behavior over time. In short, today's AI improvisers can simulate improvisation, but to achieve the real qualities of human improvisation, new principles are needed. We see an opportunity to connect the wisdom of improvisational art practice with future open-ended experiential AI in computational creativity. A fascinating question arises: What makes a "good" improvisation for AI? Can AI learn to improvise in a genuinely open-ended, experientially creative way? To explore this question, we draw inspiration from domains where improvisation thrives in human practice. We believe the principles of human improvisational arts can inform the

design of future Experiential AI systems capable of open-ended creativity. We conducted in-depth interviews with six expert improvisers (each with 10+ years of experience) across music, dance, and the embodied art of contact improvisation. Through qualitative thematic analysis, we distilled key principles of improvisation—recurring qualities that the practitioners described as crucial to their art. We grouped these into eight themes. Using concepts from complex systems and cognitive theory, we examine how an AI might embody these qualities. In effect, we consider how an improvising AI might continually generate novel yet meaningful behavior, much as human improvisers do. Finally, we outline implications for creating AI that is not only generative, but experientially creative – AI that grows and evolves through improvisational interaction, continually finding new possibilities that remain coherent and contextually valuable. We situate these implications in relation to open-ended AI research, aiming to bridge human improvisation insights with the quest for open-ended creative agents.

Figure 1: Contact Improvisation

Figure 2: Dance With Robot

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The Sense of Touch in Healthcare HAPTIMED A Digital Twin of Haptic Perception for Educational Purposes

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Abstract

The recent reform of medical education in France, including the introduction of Objective Structured Clinical Examinations (OSCEs), underscores the need to standardize the learning and evaluation of clinical skills. Among these, palpation—a core component of the physical examination—relies on haptic perception, where practitioners assess the biomechanical properties of tissues through tactile and proprioceptive cues. Yet, palpation remains largely taught through traditional apprenticeship models, lacking standardized protocols or objective pedagogical tools. Modernizing the learning of touch in healthcare therefore represents a major educational challenge. The HAPTIMED project investigates the sense of touch as an active movement that structures diagnostic and therapeutic interaction. Anchored at the intersection of human movement sciences, electronics, and artificial intelligence, it aims to model and enhance the acquisition of haptic competence in healthcare education through the development of a digital twin of haptic perception. The project has just begun and brings together two mirror doctoral theses within a unified interdisciplinary framework: Topic A (Human Movement Sciences) focuses on the analysis and standardization of palpatory gestures. It seeks to identify objective markers of haptic expertise and to define pedagogical feedback mechanisms for learners. The study will characterize expert and novice gestures in terms of force, displacement, and temporal dynamics, providing a reference framework for training and assessment. Topic B (Flexible Electronics, Structures and Embedded Systems) aims to design and validate a wearable haptic glove capable of monitoring pressure and movement during palpatory examinations. Based on Hooke's law, tissue stiffness (k), the ratio

between applied force and resulting deformation, is treated as the key measurable parameter linking force and displacement. By quantifying stiffness, the glove will provide an objective measure of tissue resistance to deformation, allowing learners to visualize and compare their applied pressure with expert benchmarks. A transversal methodological axis combines machine learning and belief function theory to fuse multimodal data (force, displacement, motion trajectories) and to manage uncertainty in haptic signal interpretation. Ultimately, HAPTIMED aims to modernize and objectify the teaching of clinical touch, providing evidence-based recommendations for OSCE implementation. By rendering touch measurable, comparable, and computable, the project exemplifies how movement computing can bridge human expertise and digital intelligence—transforming the embodied act of palpation into a quantifiable and pedagogically actionable dimension of healthcare education.

Keywords : Haptics, Movement Computing, Digital Twin, Palpation, Hooke's law, Wearable Sensors, Human Movement, Science, Machine Learning, Medical Education, OSCE, Belief Function Theory.